

Exposure	Outcome	SNP	Beta	SE	P
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10305525	-6.733417722	8.775063291	0.442882057
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11963172	-1.240177778	5.155838889	0.809912817
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12215108	-6.02642487	6.151761658	0.32727083
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs142878626	9.496129032	6.769930876	0.160708653
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs228817	7.589883721	6.50479845	0.243285876
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs28360624	-2.262137725	6.505508982	0.72804561
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs880347	3.402550239	3.901822967	0.383185922
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs9462535	-3.339541935	5.36243871	0.533438619
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	0.596744939	1.882520187	0.751249229
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.596744939	2.01385895	0.766986375
GLP1R	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	7.912062154	8.59295486	0.392690823
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10766392	3.253125	2.293804688	0.156125868
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10766393	3.218372703	2.313388451	0.164166531
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10766395	0.98983208	2.067902256	0.63217709
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs147673442	-6.154715026	4.504015544	0.171783628
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs189603359	-7.666400778	6.868035019	0.264317836
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2285676	1.151019512	2.013782927	0.567612785
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2355016	0.102746111	2.764616667	0.970353695
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs35271178	0.757609302	1.264103876	0.54895605
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4148631	-4.832748252	6.455776224	0.454102612
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs5210	1.150086207	2.033391626	0.57166576
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs5219	-0.068126783	1.125812921	0.951746733
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs7110037	0.441794737	2.620563158	0.86612095
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs7112030	1.13201737	2.052699752	0.581306506
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs739688	-5.00742515	4.973179641	0.313989542
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs77902362	-0.224708442	5.556266234	0.967740471
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs79506407	-7.02863747	7.71379562	0.362201826
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	0.582261154	0.454443682	0.200101862
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	0.582261154	0.557981163	0.296710301
KCNJ11	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	1.306575512	1.541379311	0.410881829

RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs1078523	-0.36613	5.028475	0.941956247
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11654396	-19.84044118	6.848764706	0.003768252
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11869741	-0.275507242	5.48362117	0.959929667
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12603201	-3.177801619	3.287797571	0.333771949
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12941945	-8.282401747	4.769388646	0.082462191
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs59795094	-0.558030769	6.222269231	0.928539254
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs9892728	-0.641894737	5.298796053	0.903580359
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs9905939	-0.672090909	5.253162338	0.898196257
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-3.552928121	1.894212623	0.060699858
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.552928121	1.745337552	0.041783686
RAMP2	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	-1.689376385	7.265620659	0.823865205
KCNJ8	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs10841887	2.802711765	2.776238235	0.312717763
KCNJ8	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs117973841	3.534536424	6.088377483	0.561551654
KCNJ8	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12816749	-4.053745562	5.562656805	0.466159065
KCNJ8	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs59406438	-1.008828753	4.314038055	0.815103059
KCNJ8	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs74732083	1.461600897	4.910515695	0.7659725
KCNJ8	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	1.176423066	1.199970687	0.326900304
KCNJ8	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	1.176423066	1.875669865	0.530527121
KCNJ8	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	4.65561854	5.544320689	0.462716418
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs111327339	-0.082591239	4.608353474	0.985701022
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs1373641	-4.688468468	3.840256757	0.222133844
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs1699348	11.28256	6.533488	0.084188935
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2120825	-1.423768279	1.481833521	0.336645058
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2881654	-1.862018038	1.378252537	0.176695697
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2920503	-4.667255814	5.211244186	0.370459718
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs310752	-0.251093077	6.241676923	0.967910985
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4135247	-4.816702413	2.189839142	0.027837485
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4684833	0.740460526	4.2305	0.861056783
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs76763697	0.186554018	6.643705357	0.977598493
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-1.920956093	0.751550349	0.010588579
PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.920956093	0.824865199	0.01986902

PPARG	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	-2.455175611	1.313916058	0.098619879
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11150624	-0.827418033	6.687467213	0.901531696
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11865835	-4.967765217	7.752252174	0.521642405
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs12448775	-1.105391026	6.571025641	0.86640864
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs142133957	-0.400342577	5.13766721	0.937889283
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs34497199	-3.198488372	6.26444186	0.609646341
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4561482	-9.608034188	6.981367521	0.168747477
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8054784	-1.990891892	7.41636036	0.788356075
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8057029	-4.722163793	7.302482759	0.517857309
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8057326	-6.668580952	7.64192381	0.382864143
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-3.295853509	1.02843074	0.001351844
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.295853509	2.235502762	0.140394601
SLC5A2	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	0.824743117	5.454752165	0.884085224
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs111917515	-2.361154982	5.552693727	0.670671245
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs112898001	-4.079163347	6.007011952	0.497095436
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs112968754	-2.725597561	6.098211382	0.654910927
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs113126535	-2.772204	6.00096	0.644109944
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs1659215	-3.266589189	8.080324324	0.686018144
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs34359922	-1.898474576	5.976144068	0.750731095
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4924660	-2.100017241	6.890517241	0.760541962
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs73402785	-2.980248945	6.210295359	0.631306722
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs8037100	-2.74705641	7.672974359	0.720330479
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-2.752176334	0.223249681	6.42E-35
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.752176334	2.121918692	0.194623438
GANC	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	-3.416596583	14.49828603	0.820446281
KCNJ1	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs116842927	3.103529412	6.79956427	0.648080343
KCNJ1	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4937311	-8.381587302	7.165761905	0.242133201
KCNJ1	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs7110898	3.675668085	10.02987234	0.71401285
KCNJ1	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-1.166944088	4.009573373	0.771021137
KCNJ1	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.166944088	4.426144179	0.792051163
KCNJ1	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	8.709765146	9.282929149	0.520272905

RAMP3	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs11772021	-2.527556936	2.289440994	0.26959047
RAMP3	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4724382	3.149207207	7.361108108	0.668784357
RAMP3	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs73111954	-0.563340426	4.060744681	0.889664812
RAMP3	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs75390434	8.786324786	8.645213675	0.309475859
RAMP3	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	-1.202779173	1.550990443	0.438049565
RAMP3	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.202779173	1.878907815	0.522076353
RAMP3	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	-4.985620721	3.435232111	0.283796803
ETFDH	Acute myeloid leukemia	Wald_ratio	6.0333	5.419471429	0.265595256
GANAB	Acute myeloid leukemia	Wald_ratio	1.533865922	5.424	0.777335988
PRKAB1	Acute myeloid leukemia	Wald_ratio	-2.14104461	6.155464684	0.72796916
DPP4	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs188581353	-0.688767209	6.12718398	0.910496973
DPP4	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2080714	4.92275974	5.475675325	0.368640246
DPP4	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4233648	10.62193548	6.710790323	0.113463776
DPP4	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs75850673	-0.197900621	7.751428571	0.979631535
DPP4	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	3.828583628	2.51672519	0.128195574
DPP4	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	3.828583628	3.18082738	0.228727225
DPP4	Acute myeloid leukemia	All - MR Egger	-3.332798084	7.322682519	0.693646238
ABCC8	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs2074312	2.066645946	2.360891892	0.381374458
ABCC8	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs77023203	0.831995327	1.950514019	0.669705788
ABCC8	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	1.332856531	0.606239763	0.027908984
ABCC8	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	1.332856531	1.503705396	0.375412025
INSR	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs4031066	4.731089041	5.781068493	0.41314239
RAMP1	Acute myeloid leukemia	Wald_ratio	-4.758529412	8.386637255	0.570446383
AMY2A	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs72681706	3.274379391	6.137798595	0.593702863
AMY2A	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs72692396	4.975868263	5.464311377	0.362499773
AMY2A	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	4.223561318	0.845030269	5.79E-07
AMY2A	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	4.223561318	4.081272685	0.300732527
AMY2A	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs72681706	3.274379391	6.137798595	0.593702863
AMY2A	Acute myeloid leukemia	rs72692396	4.975868263	5.464311377	0.362499773
AMY2A	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(random effects)	4.223561318	0.845030269	5.79E-07
AMY2A	Acute myeloid leukemia	IVW(fixed effects)	4.223561318	4.081272685	0.300732527

GLP1R	Anal cancer	rs10305525	5.763841772	15.01955696	0.701159467
GLP1R	Anal cancer	rs11963172	1.165794444	8.800166667	0.894609282
GLP1R	Anal cancer	rs12215108	-5.605906736	10.45305699	0.591755708
GLP1R	Anal cancer	rs142878626	-5.58764977	11.57562212	0.629302814
GLP1R	Anal cancer	rs228817	9.538372093	11.11023256	0.390604635
GLP1R	Anal cancer	rs28360624	0.168933533	11.08778443	0.987843898
GLP1R	Anal cancer	rs880347	1.395100478	6.666889952	0.834246788
GLP1R	Anal cancer	rs9462535	-4.377225806	9.155225806	0.632570298
GLP1R	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.063935753	1.691437391	0.969847418
GLP1R	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.063935753	3.437562944	0.98516088
GLP1R	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-10.21733553	14.68526251	0.512616449
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs10766392	-5.200598958	3.911223958	0.183630243
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs10766393	-5.277270341	3.944593176	0.18094564
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs10766395	-4.328671679	3.531478697	0.220296854
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs147673442	-11.6588601	7.723937824	0.131185075
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs189603359	23.16031128	11.78107004	0.049311088
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs2285676	-3.294756098	3.438878049	0.338017168
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs2355016	0.797102778	4.73025	0.866180689
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs35271178	-2.161984496	2.157968992	0.316410837
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs4148631	10.6027972	11.04391608	0.337026152
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs5210	-3.335123153	3.47226601	0.336801943
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs5219	-3.574508748	1.920444145	0.062702848
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs7110037	1.685297368	4.484789474	0.70707993
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs7112030	-3.614516129	3.504590571	0.302369142
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs739688	13.50802395	8.493353293	0.111739502
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs77902362	9.36275974	9.439058442	0.32123816
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	rs79506407	10.6113382	13.12875912	0.418945863
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.520211798	1.009109147	0.012508585
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.520211798	0.952559417	0.008151567
KCNJ11	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.829283539	2.631799747	0.021186139
RAMP2	Anal cancer	rs1078523	-0.53846125	8.5895	0.950014705

RAMP2	Anal cancer	rs11654396	9.854558824	11.69220588	0.399322717
RAMP2	Anal cancer	rs11869741	3.565348189	9.389052925	0.704142439
RAMP2	Anal cancer	rs12603201	-0.167760729	5.609838057	0.976143028
RAMP2	Anal cancer	rs12941945	-1.780759825	8.18279476	0.827723293
RAMP2	Anal cancer	rs59795094	-2.060415385	10.62753846	0.846273659
RAMP2	Anal cancer	rs9892728	0.415491447	9.050855263	0.963384918
RAMP2	Anal cancer	rs9905939	-2.107116883	8.977467532	0.814432487
RAMP2	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.302422659	1.122470544	0.787601942
RAMP2	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.302422659	2.982853456	0.91924323
RAMP2	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.236689574	10.65889476	0.983003834
KCNJ8	Anal cancer	rs10841887	7.795382353	4.748676471	0.10067489
KCNJ8	Anal cancer	rs117973841	-15.21609272	10.48119205	0.146570543
KCNJ8	Anal cancer	rs12816749	1.645378698	9.477751479	0.862176429
KCNJ8	Anal cancer	rs59406438	11.29940803	7.369894292	0.125230391
KCNJ8	Anal cancer	rs74732083	-4.594506726	8.326793722	0.581103331
KCNJ8	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.770157516	3.957567926	0.340769941
KCNJ8	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.770157516	3.203960605	0.239308156
KCNJ8	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	8.027762559	13.22133261	0.586602888
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs111327339	4.840679758	7.789441088	0.534309359
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs1373641	5.204594595	6.564369369	0.427862173
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs1699348	17.82448	11.15704	0.110132168
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs2120825	-1.321552306	2.510506187	0.59860427
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs2881654	-3.64934611	2.339334837	0.118761521
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs2920503	1.139953488	8.91005814	0.898196398
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs310752	0.619993077	10.65753846	0.953609923
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs4135247	3.110965147	3.736621984	0.405092451
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs4684833	0.445162281	7.234824561	0.950936735
PPARG	Anal cancer	rs76763697	6.8403125	11.37723214	0.547688022
PPARG	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.449543308	1.258333634	0.720902506
PPARG	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.449543308	1.401697461	0.748427511
PPARG	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.850978241	2.23170776	0.122703398

SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs11150624	-22.93770492	11.42590164	0.04469452
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs11865835	-9.102	13.22034783	0.491147945
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs12448775	-17.67794872	11.26490385	0.116579394
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs142133957	15.6434584	8.682365416	0.071584629
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs34497199	-6.681186047	10.69193798	0.532049338
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs4561482	-25.81905983	11.93700855	0.030545624
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs8054784	-28.13486486	12.67558559	0.026445208
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs8057029	-30.81198276	12.50767241	0.01376084
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	rs8057326	-18.76504762	13.05009524	0.150455565
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-12.81546671	5.56628425	0.021316129
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-12.81546671	3.81300143	0.000776631
SLC5A2	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	14.15246348	9.254576016	0.170053479
GANC	Anal cancer	rs111917515	1.892236162	9.491476015	0.84197987
GANC	Anal cancer	rs112898001	-0.911936255	10.25888446	0.929167471
GANC	Anal cancer	rs112968754	-1.332719512	10.41804878	0.898209039
GANC	Anal cancer	rs113126535	4.02016	10.2572	0.69510593
GANC	Anal cancer	rs1659215	4.700913514	13.81891892	0.733721323
GANC	Anal cancer	rs34359922	-2.174114407	10.2204661	0.831544079
GANC	Anal cancer	rs4924660	1.673396552	11.78821839	0.88711555
GANC	Anal cancer	rs73402785	-3.270886076	10.61008439	0.757868619
GANC	Anal cancer	rs8037100	5.320871795	13.11753846	0.685014221
GANC	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.736429527	1.00731147	0.464727708
GANC	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.736429527	3.62688098	0.839097817
GANC	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.3772127	24.79013842	0.804385295
KCNJ1	Anal cancer	rs116842927	3.176034858	11.74366013	0.786816569
KCNJ1	Anal cancer	rs4937311	12.89142857	12.24603175	0.29247735
KCNJ1	Anal cancer	rs7110898	-15.77476596	17.26417021	0.360859476
KCNJ1	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.245617809	7.286440018	0.656007169
KCNJ1	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.245617809	7.608523172	0.669687757
KCNJ1	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.56937331	18.58595923	0.783706558
RAMP3	Anal cancer	rs11772021	-1.968877847	3.883291925	0.612145994

RAMP3	Anal cancer	rs4724382	11.77387387	12.56297297	0.348661601
RAMP3	Anal cancer	rs73111954	-7.838382979	6.930170213	0.2580332
RAMP3	Anal cancer	rs75390434	11.08589744	14.71162393	0.451121387
RAMP3	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.712174713	3.02620907	0.571541963
RAMP3	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.712174713	3.192899286	0.591789575
RAMP3	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.771942038	5.835556845	0.365656713
ETFDH	Anal cancer	Wald_ratio	-14.362	9.301357143	0.122569983
GANAB	Anal cancer	Wald_ratio	-1.864357542	9.242793296	0.840143977
PRKAB1	Anal cancer	Wald_ratio	-10.20825279	10.49836431	0.330868487
DPP4	Anal cancer	rs188581353	-4.340863579	10.27638298	0.672724598
DPP4	Anal cancer	rs2080714	-17.31980519	9.325649351	0.063279514
DPP4	Anal cancer	rs4233648	-13.59016129	11.46540323	0.235891309
DPP4	Anal cancer	rs75850673	2.028745342	13.21838509	0.878020501
DPP4	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-9.680622554	4.231053592	0.022137907
DPP4	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-9.680622554	5.399630515	0.073000023
DPP4	Anal cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.13586468	12.29472525	0.878076421
ABCC8	Anal cancer	rs2074312	-4.183432432	4.026945946	0.298869925
ABCC8	Anal cancer	rs77023203	-3.805280374	3.329228972	0.253042126
ABCC8	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.958809299	0.185704465	7.76E-101
ABCC8	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.958809299	2.565887854	0.122864411
INSR	Anal cancer	rs4031066	-7.777465753	9.853150685	0.429914512
RAMP1	Anal cancer	Wald_ratio	0.812757843	14.32166667	0.954744163
AMY2A	Anal cancer	rs72681706	13.10250585	10.42030445	0.208608307
AMY2A	Anal cancer	rs72692396	5.488323353	9.293033932	0.554798741
AMY2A	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	8.861430856	3.782274699	0.019135332
AMY2A	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	8.861430856	6.935597129	0.201364461
AMY2A	Anal cancer	rs72681706	13.10250585	10.42030445	0.208608307
AMY2A	Anal cancer	rs72692396	5.488323353	9.293033932	0.554798741
AMY2A	Anal cancer	IVW(random effects)	8.861430856	3.782274699	0.019135332
AMY2A	Anal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	8.861430856	6.935597129	0.201364461
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10305525	1.092917722	2.390386076	0.647517314

GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11963172	-0.002733744	1.403794444	0.998446203
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12215108	-0.147359585	1.670430052	0.929704559
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	rs142878626	-2.110571429	1.840299539	0.251438252
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	rs228817	2.772868217	1.771689922	0.117559951
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	rs28360624	0.260588623	1.769389222	0.88291415
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	rs880347	-1.057980861	1.0624689	0.319359071
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	rs9462535	0.946470968	1.460741935	0.517024715
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.003951027	0.482064306	0.993460565
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.003951027	0.548109391	0.994248527
GLP1R	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-5.023870077	2.337565035	0.075190357
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10766392	-0.609213542	0.623846354	0.328794853
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10766393	-0.640742782	0.629136483	0.308465109
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10766395	-0.560766917	0.562726817	0.318998944
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs147673442	0.812233161	1.222303109	0.506363678
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs189603359	1.350468872	1.880110895	0.472577178
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2285676	-0.427678049	0.547995122	0.435131141
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2355016	-0.420091667	0.753358333	0.577100276
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs35271178	-0.395947287	0.344294574	0.250133671
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4148631	-0.369443357	1.759	0.833643998
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs5210	-0.440019704	0.553330049	0.426484927
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs5219	-0.243851952	0.306678331	0.426532556
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs7110037	-0.267610526	0.714223684	0.707893057
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs7112030	-0.482846154	0.55848139	0.387274944
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs739688	-0.172852096	1.354634731	0.89846512
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs77902362	1.245616883	1.513256494	0.410430288
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	rs79506407	-1.106659367	2.109326034	0.599826039
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.358996552	0.076117062	2.40E-06
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.358996552	0.151918856	0.018123712
KCNJ11	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.317706594	0.419882675	0.461800538
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs1078523	-1.09765625	1.36925625	0.422758836
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11654396	0.976441176	1.862544118	0.600103764

RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11869741	-0.669545961	1.49502507	0.654261946
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12603201	-1.212125506	0.895036437	0.175648646
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12941945	-2.396908297	1.299912664	0.06519779
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs59795094	-1.332653846	1.694138462	0.431500667
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs9892728	-0.878736842	1.442953947	0.542534596
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs9905939	-0.679909091	1.430623377	0.634606137
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.073932069	0.28190779	0.000139239
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.073932069	0.475305842	0.023855109
RAMP2	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.994567092	1.698286306	0.284709217
KCNJ8	Basal cell carcinoma	rs10841887	0.636864706	0.755814706	0.399440914
KCNJ8	Basal cell carcinoma	rs117973841	1.261119205	1.660715232	0.447623375
KCNJ8	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12816749	1.582674556	1.512254438	0.295299644
KCNJ8	Basal cell carcinoma	rs59406438	0.299915433	1.179260042	0.799244407
KCNJ8	Basal cell carcinoma	rs74732083	-0.43594843	1.337183857	0.744409365
KCNJ8	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.584011112	0.285357596	0.040697975
KCNJ8	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.584011112	0.511060493	0.253145058
KCNJ8	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.70828783	1.509904471	0.670987989
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs111327339	1.245119335	1.250907855	0.319555106
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs1373641	-1.252490991	1.045927928	0.231114596
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs1699348	-1.335408	1.779592	0.453013099
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.522200225	0.403591676	0.195705995
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.242417136	0.375319053	0.518346604
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2920503	-2.885244186	1.421843023	0.042435036
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs310752	-1.139515385	1.700415385	0.502768916
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4135247	-0.586790885	0.596270777	0.325065677
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4684833	0.50245614	1.154570175	0.663425309
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	rs76763697	-0.238886607	1.804602679	0.894686668
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.447372486	0.196046423	0.022490982
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.447372486	0.224633528	0.046418702
PPARG	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.092402557	0.357836258	0.802751675
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11150624	0.538408197	1.82107377	0.76749414

SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11865835	-3.583608696	2.107834783	0.089105088
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs12448775	-0.027657276	1.793163462	0.987694129
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs142133957	1.398249592	1.397327896	0.316991399
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs34497199	-0.212387597	1.705875969	0.900916598
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4561482	0.538669231	1.901547009	0.776962613
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8054784	0.034147207	2.019927928	0.986512275
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8057029	-0.24995	1.988758621	0.899984113
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8057326	-0.513688571	2.081533333	0.805075598
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.012636998	0.438523653	0.97701043
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.012636998	0.608727725	0.983437355
SLC5A2	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	1.429521281	1.48486515	0.367753779
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs111917515	-1.263738007	1.510239852	0.402716426
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs112898001	-1.707729084	1.633836653	0.295918379
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs112968754	-1.630861789	1.657691057	0.325206346
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs113126535	-1.245712	1.631984	0.445277702
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs1659215	-1.713540541	2.197448649	0.435516621
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs34359922	-1.519389831	1.626351695	0.350184222
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4924660	2.734206897	1.875908046	0.144967984
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs73402785	-1.333852321	1.689270042	0.429759784
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	rs8037100	-1.650476923	2.086779487	0.428990316
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.083930282	0.441014035	0.013978572
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.083930282	0.577174868	0.060382142
GANC	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-6.395127512	3.944518257	0.148990628
KCNJ1	Basal cell carcinoma	rs116842927	4.73546841	1.866466231	0.011176528
KCNJ1	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4937311	6.006611111	1.952174603	0.00209178
KCNJ1	Basal cell carcinoma	rs7110898	5.891021277	2.72752766	0.030785116
KCNJ1	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	5.450334605	0.430934534	1.15E-36
KCNJ1	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	5.450334605	1.209241951	6.57E-06
KCNJ1	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	4.444419934	2.543553095	0.330917982
RAMP3	Basal cell carcinoma	rs11772021	0.947281573	0.623722567	0.128824255
RAMP3	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4724382	-1.631540541	2.005504505	0.41591355

RAMP3	Basal cell carcinoma	rs73111954	-2.171851064	1.106238298	0.049614116
RAMP3	Basal cell carcinoma	rs75390434	-1.735008547	2.351803419	0.460675279
RAMP3	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.01547926	0.802041435	0.984601923
RAMP3	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.01547926	0.511840319	0.975873764
RAMP3	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	1.594766197	1.172608105	0.306839481
ETFDH	Basal cell carcinoma	Wald_ratio	1.124141429	1.485442857	0.449186524
GANAB	Basal cell carcinoma	Wald_ratio	4.817497207	1.479379888	0.001128227
PRKAB1	Basal cell carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-2.518033457	1.676245353	0.133048901
DPP4	Basal cell carcinoma	rs188581353	-0.734081352	1.655356696	0.657434412
DPP4	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2080714	-3.335844156	1.488019481	0.024974211
DPP4	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4233648	3.957951613	1.828709677	0.030438177
DPP4	Basal cell carcinoma	rs75850673	0.401576398	2.109273292	0.849006559
DPP4	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.373529175	1.557625102	0.810479994
DPP4	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.373529175	0.863752076	0.66541473
DPP4	Basal cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.953848051	4.191454485	0.686949661
ABCC8	Basal cell carcinoma	rs2074312	-0.8399	0.642267568	0.190971543
ABCC8	Basal cell carcinoma	rs77023203	-0.421116822	0.530693925	0.427474286
ABCC8	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.591030403	0.205636389	0.004051129
ABCC8	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.591030403	0.4091056	0.148545232
INSR	Basal cell carcinoma	rs4031066	-1.59190411	1.574589041	0.312018075
RAMP1	Basal cell carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-3.121960784	2.283323529	0.171535062
AMY2A	Basal cell carcinoma	rs72681706	1.199761124	1.676700234	0.474269893
AMY2A	Basal cell carcinoma	rs72692396	1.5589002	1.494830339	0.297012694
AMY2A	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.399857818	0.178392418	4.26E-15
AMY2A	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.399857818	1.115785029	0.209625983
AMY2A	Basal cell carcinoma	rs72681706	1.199761124	1.676700234	0.474269893
AMY2A	Basal cell carcinoma	rs72692396	1.5589002	1.494830339	0.297012694
AMY2A	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.399857818	0.178392418	4.26E-15
AMY2A	Basal cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.399857818	1.115785029	0.209625983
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	rs10766395	0.001153739	0.002608496	0.658271726
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	rs2285676	0.001631454	0.002541561	0.520931556

KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	rs35271178	0.001776775	0.001595364	0.265403087
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	rs5210	0.001702845	0.002566453	0.507009599
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	rs5219	0.00216782	0.00142245	0.127507558
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	rs7112030	0.001773804	0.002588685	0.493208681
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	rs739688	-0.001539066	0.006238024	0.805122371
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.001765112	0.000214668	1.99E-16
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.001765112	0.000812271	0.029775982
KCNJ11	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	0.002999001	0.002269194	0.243535589
RAMP2	Bladder cancer	rs1078523	0.007825375	0.006349125	0.217757755
RAMP2	Bladder cancer	rs12603201	-1.21E-04	0.004146721	0.976794167
RAMP2	Bladder cancer	rs59795094	0.008999615	0.007831231	0.250475364
RAMP2	Bladder cancer	rs9892728	0.007926842	0.006688882	0.235986863
RAMP2	Bladder cancer	rs9905939	0.005805396	0.006606169	0.379518351
RAMP2	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.004456078	0.001927236	0.020768865
RAMP2	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.004456078	0.002630369	0.090248498
RAMP2	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.011132373	0.011293401	0.396940233
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	rs11150624	-0.020955492	0.008447049	0.013108563
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	rs34497199	-0.007991938	0.007893178	0.311293297
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	rs4561482	-0.021516838	0.008805214	0.014539628
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	rs8054784	-0.010760901	0.00934045	0.249290192
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	rs8057029	-0.016108621	0.009191466	0.079677079
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	rs8057326	-0.017813714	0.009654	0.065006139
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.015646275	0.002339204	2.25E-11
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.015646275	0.003603936	1.42E-05
SLC5A2	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	0.008242502	0.054527491	0.887164748
PPARG	Bladder cancer	rs1373641	0.002666995	0.004825045	0.580441445
PPARG	Bladder cancer	rs1699348	-8.48E-04	0.00821368	0.917790691
PPARG	Bladder cancer	rs310752	-0.002274523	0.007862	0.772347289
PPARG	Bladder cancer	rs4135247	-4.68E-04	0.002750509	0.864934095
PPARG	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.63E-05	0.000832654	0.984427917
PPARG	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.63E-05	0.002202532	0.994112748

PPARG	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	2.72E-04	0.005107694	0.96235625
DPP4	Bladder cancer	rs2080714	-0.005250675	0.006897922	0.446539606
DPP4	Bladder cancer	rs4233648	-0.00268129	0.008372097	0.748767385
DPP4	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.004211742	0.001260967	0.000837514
DPP4	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.004211742	0.005323699	0.428867703
GLP1R	Bladder cancer	rs228817	-0.018548605	0.008200698	0.023707753
GLP1R	Bladder cancer	rs880347	-0.012609713	0.004914115	0.010287314
GLP1R	Bladder cancer	rs9462535	-0.004852555	0.006746129	0.471950231
GLP1R	Bladder cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.011560044	0.003353854	0.000567281
GLP1R	Bladder cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.011560044	0.003574781	0.001221648
GLP1R	Bladder cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.008205055	0.02364235	0.787341321
INSR	Bladder cancer	rs4031066	-0.001932548	0.007287397	0.790862774
RAMP1	Bladder cancer	Wald_ratio	0.003743853	0.010355196	0.717693257
RAMP3	Bladder cancer	rs4724382	-0.002892847	0.009285315	0.755381977
ABCC8	Bladder cancer	rs77023203	0.001938318	0.002454907	0.429779601
ABCC8	Bladder cancer	rs77023203	0.001938318	0.002454907	0.429779601
GLP1R	Breast cancer	rs10305525	-0.696202532	0.702531646	0.321689979
GLP1R	Breast cancer	rs11963172	-0.011111111	0.405555556	0.978142883
GLP1R	Breast cancer	rs12215108	0.134715026	0.476683938	0.777476814
GLP1R	Breast cancer	rs142878626	0.255760369	0.580645161	0.659592253
GLP1R	Breast cancer	rs228817	0.565891473	0.527131783	0.28303365
GLP1R	Breast cancer	rs28360624	-0.245508982	0.497005988	0.621323197
GLP1R	Breast cancer	rs880347	0.244019139	0.325358852	0.453254705
GLP1R	Breast cancer	rs9462535	0.058064516	0.412903226	0.888166197
GLP1R	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.092674182	0.103921292	0.372514718
GLP1R	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.092674182	0.161306627	0.565614717
GLP1R	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.183359523	0.719711309	0.807409568
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs10766392	0.473958333	0.182291667	0.009322376
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs10766393	0.477690289	0.183727034	0.009322376
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs10766395	0.501253133	0.162907268	0.002091493
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs147673442	-0.113989637	0.344559585	0.740775114

KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs189603359	0.998054475	0.570038911	0.079971193
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs2285676	0.451219512	0.158536585	0.004425081
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs2355016	-0.211111111	0.219444444	0.336036887
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs35271178	0.192248062	0.097674419	0.049038823
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs4148631	-0.377622378	0.503496503	0.453254705
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs5210	0.460591133	0.160098522	0.004015735
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs5219	0.165545087	0.086137281	0.054621488
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs7110037	-0.221052632	0.207894737	0.287649942
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs7112030	0.476426799	0.161290323	0.003138404
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs739688	-0.592814371	0.383233533	0.121893391
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs77902362	0.103896104	0.487012987	0.831066976
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	rs79506407	-0.712895377	0.615571776	0.246822101
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.245888972	0.064939736	0.000152835
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.245888972	0.043550418	1.64E-08
KCNJ11	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.352053206	0.181058069	0.072217058
RAMP2	Breast cancer	rs1078523	-0.15	0.3875	0.698684566
RAMP2	Breast cancer	rs11654396	-0.139705882	0.522058824	0.789002894
RAMP2	Breast cancer	rs11869741	0.189415042	0.437325905	0.664926853
RAMP2	Breast cancer	rs12603201	-0.63562753	0.255060729	0.012700333
RAMP2	Breast cancer	rs12941945	-0.593886463	0.366812227	0.105437018
RAMP2	Breast cancer	rs59795094	-0.038461538	0.476923077	0.93572415
RAMP2	Breast cancer	rs9892728	-0.151315789	0.407894737	0.710661558
RAMP2	Breast cancer	rs9905939	0.623376623	0.402597403	0.121529126
RAMP2	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.217302417	0.154572404	0.159774813
RAMP2	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.217302417	0.13491669	0.107257888
RAMP2	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.830386996	0.542287429	0.176583817
KCNJ8	Breast cancer	rs10841887	-0.020588235	0.217647059	0.924636843
KCNJ8	Breast cancer	rs117973841	0.251655629	0.533112583	0.636891322
KCNJ8	Breast cancer	rs12816749	-0.082840237	0.455621302	0.855725415
KCNJ8	Breast cancer	rs59406438	-0.137420719	0.350951374	0.695378718
KCNJ8	Breast cancer	rs74732083	-0.266816143	0.403587444	0.50854106

KCNJ8	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.061825138	0.062741759	0.324432253
KCNJ8	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.061825138	0.151264544	0.682743728
KCNJ8	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.150743068	0.451892365	0.76065055
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs111327339	0.487915408	0.374622356	0.19277307
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs1373641	-0.54954955	0.297297297	0.064532234
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs1699348	0.96	0.504	0.056811028
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs2120825	-0.085489314	0.11136108	0.442679242
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs2881654	-0.17361894	0.105975197	0.101359571
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs2920503	-1.680232558	0.401162791	2.81E-05
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs310752	-0.984615385	0.492307692	0.045500264
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs4135247	-0.407506702	0.168900804	0.015834916
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs4684833	0.456140351	0.328947368	0.165543429
PPARG	Breast cancer	rs76763697	0.598214286	0.575892857	0.298916513
PPARG	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.176541326	0.124076611	0.154782167
PPARG	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.176541326	0.063282918	0.005275441
PPARG	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.075311103	0.204159453	0.721786012
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs11150624	-0.647540984	0.540983607	0.231318366
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs11865835	-0.565217391	0.660869565	0.392405479
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs12448775	1.25	0.621794872	0.044398465
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs142133957	-0.097879282	0.597063622	0.869782765
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs34497199	-0.465116279	0.496124031	0.348501424
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs4561482	-0.427350427	0.572649573	0.455505141
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs8054784	-0.621621622	0.594594595	0.295812938
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs8057029	-0.637931034	0.586206897	0.276491247
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	rs8057326	-0.6	0.6	0.317310508
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.337579663	0.192215294	0.079044352
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.337579663	0.193431582	0.080947484
SLC5A2	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.802010076	0.587901379	0.214744566
GANC	Breast cancer	rs111917515	0.239852399	0.442804428	0.588048157
GANC	Breast cancer	rs112898001	0.15936255	0.482071713	0.740962879
GANC	Breast cancer	rs112968754	0.243902439	0.483739837	0.61411966

GANC	Breast cancer	rs113126535	0.224	0.48	0.640738382
GANC	Breast cancer	rs1659215	0.102702703	0.637837838	0.872080051
GANC	Breast cancer	rs34359922	0.38559322	0.466101695	0.408082498
GANC	Breast cancer	rs4924660	-0.235632184	0.534482759	0.659314198
GANC	Breast cancer	rs73402785	0.202531646	0.489451477	0.679025635
GANC	Breast cancer	rs8037100	0.21025641	0.6	0.726018003
GANC	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.184503661	0.055128597	0.000817541
GANC	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.184503661	0.167764553	0.271429131
GANC	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.942412995	1.140798119	0.435995415
KCNJ1	Breast cancer	rs116842927	0.20043573	0.498910675	0.687870434
KCNJ1	Breast cancer	rs4937311	0.452380952	0.547619048	0.408754766
KCNJ1	Breast cancer	rs7110898	-0.463829787	0.910638298	0.610509864
KCNJ1	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.205004907	0.208432561	0.325334315
KCNJ1	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.205004907	0.341833474	0.548691813
KCNJ1	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.033796068	0.695002839	0.969067305
RAMP3	Breast cancer	rs11772021	-0.15942029	0.188405797	0.397466925
RAMP3	Breast cancer	rs4724382	-0.342342342	0.567567568	0.546392541
RAMP3	Breast cancer	rs73111954	-0.178723404	0.323404255	0.580515714
RAMP3	Breast cancer	rs75390434	0.273504274	0.692307692	0.692797333
RAMP3	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.155905739	0.06218481	0.012171408
RAMP3	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.155905739	0.15263451	0.307049914
RAMP3	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.176983256	0.278519329	0.590146417
INSR	Breast cancer	rs144057856	0.821309656	0.473917869	0.083091923
INSR	Breast cancer	rs4031066	0.157534247	0.479452055	0.742479647
INSR	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.493274949	0.331865339	0.137181068
INSR	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.493274949	0.337050132	0.143328926
ETFDH	Breast cancer	Wald_ratio	0.14	0.497142857	0.778243189
GANAB	Breast cancer	Wald_ratio	0.396648045	0.446927374	0.374809766
PRKAB1	Breast cancer	Wald_ratio	0.635687732	0.486988848	0.191775904
DPP4	Breast cancer	rs188581353	0.324155194	0.64330413	0.61433794
DPP4	Breast cancer	rs2080714	0.103896104	0.474025974	0.826511328

DPP4	Breast cancer	rs4233648	-0.427419355	0.572580645	0.455378189
DPP4	Breast cancer	rs75850673	0.565217391	0.627329193	0.367593584
DPP4	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.110626658	0.201568389	0.583122533
DPP4	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.110626658	0.283319414	0.696191838
DPP4	Breast cancer	All - MR Egger	0.587940889	0.75773244	0.518983895
ABCC8	Breast cancer	rs2074312	0.537837838	0.183783784	0.003428319
ABCC8	Breast cancer	rs77023203	0.490654206	0.151869159	0.001234576
ABCC8	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.509799893	0.023169068	2.67E-107
ABCC8	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.509799893	0.117070369	1.33E-05
RAMP1	Breast cancer	Wald_ratio	-0.843137255	0.637254902	0.185809798
AMY2A	Breast cancer	rs72681706	-0.173302108	0.494145199	0.725805247
AMY2A	Breast cancer	rs72692396	-0.043912176	0.497005988	0.929595787
AMY2A	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.108980601	0.064693888	0.092073899
AMY2A	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.108980601	0.350420484	0.75580099
AMY2A	Breast cancer	rs72681706	-0.173302108	0.494145199	0.725805247
AMY2A	Breast cancer	rs72692396	-0.043912176	0.497005988	0.929595787
AMY2A	Breast cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.108980601	0.064693888	0.092073899
AMY2A	Breast cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.108980601	0.350420484	0.75580099
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	rs10305525	-2.349474684	3.384753165	0.487597728
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	rs11963172	-1.722338889	1.984933333	0.38555521
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	rs12215108	1.809362694	2.355170984	0.442338021
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	rs142878626	-6.064101382	2.593963134	0.019398939
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	rs228817	-1.414875969	2.504713178	0.572151698
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	rs28360624	-1.761449102	2.503017964	0.481600867
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	rs880347	-1.318856459	1.5025311	0.380075869
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	rs9462535	2.4948	2.067322581	0.227517541
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.035084244	0.856074411	0.226622332
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.035084244	0.774765325	0.181550214
GLP1R	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.336651617	3.299151541	0.103167197
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs10766392	-1.564986979	0.881203125	0.075738486
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs10766393	-1.765619423	0.888685039	0.046947061

KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs10766395	-1.814175439	0.796443609	0.022735788
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs147673442	0.908963731	1.745709845	0.602586704
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs189603359	2.975311284	2.656167315	0.26264897
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs2285676	-1.679936585	0.775653659	0.030323922
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs2355016	2.123988889	1.066572222	0.046435182
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs35271178	-0.31208062	0.487263566	0.521863187
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs4148631	2.962678322	2.488804196	0.233888296
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs5210	-1.724689655	0.783197044	0.027657214
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs5219	-0.182196501	0.433769852	0.674463286
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs7110037	2.023936842	1.012342105	0.045580041
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs7112030	-1.833305211	0.79042928	0.020374486
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs739688	4.052317365	1.917071856	0.034531868
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs77902362	0.311594156	2.121331169	0.883221889
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	rs79506407	3.803187348	3.00406326	0.205507927
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.5220812	0.34614943	0.131489578
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.5220812	0.214960356	0.015151708
KCNJ11	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.192565317	0.971288474	0.239759488
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	rs1078523	3.02330625	1.93694375	0.118555784
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	rs11654396	-0.923852941	2.639882353	0.726368799
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	rs11869741	1.32721727	2.117225627	0.530746918
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	rs12603201	2.679639676	1.266323887	0.034338204
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	rs12941945	-0.608375546	1.84450655	0.741527619
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	rs59795094	3.541884615	2.396538462	0.139430031
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	rs9892728	3.07275	2.041111842	0.132213687
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	rs9905939	3.335831169	2.024363636	0.099385124
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.09606671	0.568655406	0.000227802
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.09606671	0.672853486	0.001838262
RAMP2	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.756851923	2.404464914	0.763595527
KCNJ8	Bronchial cancer	rs10841887	0.760061765	1.071467647	0.478097934
KCNJ8	Bronchial cancer	rs117973841	0.54318543	2.362390728	0.818145858
KCNJ8	Bronchial cancer	rs12816749	-0.479820118	2.137710059	0.82240313

KCNJ8	Bronchial cancer	rs59406438	-1.60356871	1.665794926	0.335725841
KCNJ8	Bronchial cancer	rs74732083	-0.726047085	1.868652466	0.69761612
KCNJ8	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.068604237	0.467531413	0.883339478
KCNJ8	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.068604237	0.722475602	0.924348848
KCNJ8	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.544408786	2.130682967	0.814846616
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs111327339	0.454957704	1.74978852	0.79485818
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs1373641	-0.721959459	1.480423423	0.62578295
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs1699348	-3.239392	2.516184	0.197947052
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs2120825	1.502215973	0.568809899	0.008266642
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs2881654	1.321307779	0.529443067	0.012572445
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs2920503	3.442767442	2.009930233	0.086734788
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs310752	1.905315385	2.404661538	0.428161033
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs4135247	0.725042895	0.842675603	0.389565443
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs4684833	1.785552632	1.6335	0.274356942
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	rs76763697	2.028209821	2.564674107	0.429045796
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.189854736	0.283388375	2.68E-05
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.189854736	0.316948074	0.000173965
PPARG	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	1.516307157	0.504803434	0.016974204
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs11150624	-1.883680328	2.576918033	0.464790235
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs11865835	-6.738947826	2.977069565	0.023597629
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs12448775	-0.807179487	2.536003205	0.750266456
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs142133957	-0.226362153	1.948091354	0.907496503
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs34497199	-3.245379845	2.412914729	0.178623958
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs4561482	2.411111111	2.689034188	0.36990797
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs8054784	-0.992207207	2.857081081	0.728380951
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs8057029	0.036111724	2.812439655	0.989755444
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	rs8057326	-3.753209524	2.945657143	0.202610204
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.476204706	0.813022203	0.069416349
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.476204706	0.858553533	0.085539917
SLC5A2	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.084752063	2.078565944	0.968614428
GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs111917515	-0.911789668	2.135690037	0.669430477

GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs112898001	-1.598601594	2.308816733	0.488692451
GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs112968754	-1.541373984	2.344621951	0.510918402
GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs113126535	-0.411464	2.30764	0.858483367
GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs1659215	-1.031978378	3.109567568	0.739985921
GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs34359922	-1.908881356	2.30259322	0.407096647
GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs4924660	0.076533333	2.654178161	0.976996155
GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs73402785	-1.130156118	2.387700422	0.635981981
GANC	Bronchial cancer	rs8037100	-1.103687179	2.952379487	0.708531011
GANC	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.091666519	0.203937919	8.65E-08
GANC	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.091666519	0.81632201	0.181125093
GANC	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.786272838	5.579714728	0.632837086
KCNJ1	Bronchial cancer	rs116842927	-0.333930283	2.640152505	0.899350842
KCNJ1	Bronchial cancer	rs4937311	-0.654364286	2.76197619	0.812719728
KCNJ1	Bronchial cancer	rs7110898	-2.513174468	3.876114894	0.51674269
KCNJ1	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.882296403	0.576810874	0.126112983
KCNJ1	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.882296403	1.712193662	0.606342171
KCNJ1	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.770732679	3.599430272	0.865710845
RAMP3	Bronchial cancer	rs11772021	0.451318841	0.880004141	0.608049322
RAMP3	Bronchial cancer	rs4724382	1.714585586	2.836324324	0.545504818
RAMP3	Bronchial cancer	rs73111954	-0.139976596	1.562923404	0.928636274
RAMP3	Bronchial cancer	rs75390434	-2.732974359	3.313512821	0.409487034
RAMP3	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.255575592	0.45530331	0.574572317
RAMP3	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.255575592	0.722426992	0.723508566
RAMP3	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.573907047	1.320615116	0.706264318
ETFDH	Bronchial cancer	Wald_ratio	0.972372857	2.106385714	0.644345989
GANAB	Bronchial cancer	Wald_ratio	0.908022346	2.082223464	0.662776479
PRKAB1	Bronchial cancer	Wald_ratio	2.030156134	2.36305948	0.39027327
DPP4	Bronchial cancer	rs188581353	1.198033792	2.297121402	0.601992741
DPP4	Bronchial cancer	rs2080714	-0.568448052	2.101512987	0.786779721
DPP4	Bronchial cancer	rs4233648	-2.959379032	2.587064516	0.25265935
DPP4	Bronchial cancer	rs75850673	2.104484472	2.984360248	0.48070379

DPP4	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.158718621	1.024542149	0.87688704
DPP4	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.158718621	1.21479541	0.89604854
DPP4	Bronchial cancer	All - MR Egger	2.213928272	2.749788868	0.505249279
ABCC8	Bronchial cancer	rs2074312	-2.272040541	0.908302703	0.01236987
ABCC8	Bronchial cancer	rs77023203	-1.534030374	0.750850467	0.041046787
ABCC8	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.833624024	0.362417997	4.21E-07
ABCC8	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.833624024	0.578716329	0.00153263
INSR	Bronchial cancer	rs4031066	-1.465109589	2.224575342	0.51015143
RAMP1	Bronchial cancer	Wald_ratio	1.440509804	3.228470588	0.655460339
AMY2A	Bronchial cancer	rs72681706	-0.811428571	2.364262295	0.731443629
AMY2A	Bronchial cancer	rs72692396	-0.545794411	2.10998004	0.79588772
AMY2A	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.663563449	0.131961863	4.94E-07
AMY2A	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.663563449	1.574233892	0.673378944
AMY2A	Bronchial cancer	rs72681706	-0.811428571	2.364262295	0.731443629
AMY2A	Bronchial cancer	rs72692396	-0.545794411	2.10998004	0.79588772
AMY2A	Bronchial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.663563449	0.131961863	4.94E-07
AMY2A	Bronchial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.663563449	1.574233892	0.673378944
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	rs10305525	0.088545627	1.883284497	0.9625
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	rs11963172	-2.194951839	1.155269687	0.05744
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	rs12215108	1.309730942	1.361045251	0.3359
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	rs142878626	-0.17346236	1.509277002	0.9085
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	rs228817	0.702236007	1.430518876	0.6235
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	rs28360624	-0.708368368	1.448431616	0.6248
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	rs880347	0.259073335	0.867454383	0.7652
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	rs9462535	1.441797656	1.179081849	0.2214
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.079255484	0.432711569	0.854672419
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.079255484	0.446161779	0.859006931
GLP1R	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.749790852	1.967726261	0.716297676
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs10766392	-0.94398783	0.504448804	0.0613
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs10766393	-0.943257396	0.508808794	0.06376
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs10766395	-0.737564178	0.457595659	0.107

KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs147673442	1.560831097	1.015792785	0.1244
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs189603359	-0.897275012	1.508998413	0.5521
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs2285676	-0.700199125	0.445968252	0.1164
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs2355016	0.531003255	0.614991412	0.3879
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs35271178	-0.254795449	0.281327465	0.3651
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs4148631	1.827878155	1.436778644	0.2033
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs5210	-0.69696057	0.449360034	0.1209
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs7110037	0.446195807	0.584709894	0.4454
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs7112030	-0.648601926	0.454322531	0.1534
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs739688	1.387202277	1.148476595	0.2271
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs77902362	0.136650804	1.237889972	0.9121
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	rs79506407	-0.768707338	1.705030206	0.6521
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.378107108	0.159598493	0.017830731
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.378107108	0.142501881	0.007969761
KCNJ11	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.094365294	0.484841116	0.041850088
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	rs1078523	-0.470516651	1.117053216	0.6736
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	rs11654396	-1.203334859	1.529739265	0.4315
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	rs11869741	2.906964215	4.993934408	0.5605
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	rs12603201	0.334645523	0.727014143	0.6453
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	rs12941945	-0.056731691	1.018963195	0.9556
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	rs59795094	-0.773102758	1.38387456	0.5764
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	rs9892728	-0.574872759	1.178188915	0.6256
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	rs9905939	0.587061341	1.163288582	0.6138
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.095036166	0.221652471	0.668096406
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.095036166	0.404707248	0.814343055
RAMP2	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	1.486497968	1.675601227	0.409150801
KCNJ8	Cervical cancer	rs10841887	0.414709541	0.615854567	0.5007
KCNJ8	Cervical cancer	rs117973841	0.069463513	1.341382631	0.9587
KCNJ8	Cervical cancer	rs12816749	2.059083168	1.219906663	0.09143
KCNJ8	Cervical cancer	rs59406438	1.602573222	0.93472664	0.08644
KCNJ8	Cervical cancer	rs74732083	1.147713829	1.048541174	0.2737

KCNJ8	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.911353326	0.326720078	0.005280563
KCNJ8	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.911353326	0.411052129	0.026614655
KCNJ8	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	0.353054474	1.208282885	0.789179422
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs111327339	-0.300614225	0.989170552	0.7612
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs1373641	0.429973552	0.847466962	0.6119
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs1699348	0.851452808	1.44756375	0.5564
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs2120825	-0.012380264	0.341725289	0.9711
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs2881654	0.221043175	0.307750228	0.4726
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs2920503	0.831499111	1.148051318	0.4689
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs310752	0.517118905	1.374249854	0.7067
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs4135247	0.57817099	0.481355078	0.2297
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs4684833	-0.161981221	0.935266133	0.8625
PPARG	Cervical cancer	rs76763697	0.313598881	1.499111035	0.8343
PPARG	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.215026387	0.088209282	0.014781675
PPARG	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.215026387	0.185039896	0.245213454
PPARG	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	0.02646013	0.295567723	0.930866903
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs11150624	0.77413597	1.480695058	0.6011
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs11865835	0.390426545	1.717763276	0.8202
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs12448775	2.257130266	1.402351651	0.1075
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs142133957	-2.037014389	1.220214381	0.09504
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs34497199	0.00775155	1.767092161	0.9965
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs4561482	1.247265154	1.539369966	0.4178
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs8054784	1.713333859	1.636423453	0.2951
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs8057029	1.173017535	1.607989584	0.4657
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	rs8057326	-0.12389007	1.732733591	0.943
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.484454076	0.482534198	0.315388861
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.484454076	0.512273156	0.344304259
SLC5A2	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.898669617	1.256125413	0.497506218
GANC	Cervical cancer	rs111917515	-0.462039873	1.235381566	0.7084
GANC	Cervical cancer	rs112898001	-0.455552893	1.337476489	0.7334
GANC	Cervical cancer	rs112968754	-0.749151848	1.357344503	0.581

GANC	Cervical cancer	rs113126535	-0.678217626	1.339760175	0.6127
GANC	Cervical cancer	rs1659215	-0.88834089	1.794627441	0.6206
GANC	Cervical cancer	rs34359922	0.216654635	1.316667667	0.8693
GANC	Cervical cancer	rs4924660	-0.450033282	1.528970118	0.7685
GANC	Cervical cancer	rs73402785	-0.227235117	1.386319349	0.8698
GANC	Cervical cancer	rs8037100	-0.957603347	1.70920299	0.5753
GANC	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.474471786	0.118552082	6.28E-05
GANC	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.474471786	0.471831455	0.314609987
GANC	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	0.080630093	3.222611301	0.980737239
KCNJ1	Cervical cancer	rs116842927	0.70734619	1.544177891	0.6469
KCNJ1	Cervical cancer	rs4937311	2.868178303	1.598017855	0.07268
KCNJ1	Cervical cancer	rs7110898	0.537022611	2.226460582	0.8094
KCNJ1	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.508974762	0.764417659	0.048379615
KCNJ1	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.508974762	0.993708813	0.12888132
KCNJ1	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.376006351	2.098921994	0.887151298
RAMP3	Cervical cancer	rs11772021	-0.105860236	0.500833407	0.8326
RAMP3	Cervical cancer	rs4724382	-1.518659195	1.636460468	0.3534
RAMP3	Cervical cancer	rs73111954	-0.855178796	0.913324286	0.3491
RAMP3	Cervical cancer	rs75390434	-0.351147696	1.929616317	0.8556
RAMP3	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.361840685	0.245391731	0.14033542
RAMP3	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.361840685	0.414246842	0.382395776
RAMP3	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	0.160521928	0.755438142	0.851415766
INSR	Cervical cancer	rs144057856	-0.377523625	1.031239587	0.7143
INSR	Cervical cancer	rs4031066	-0.823793165	1.277726931	0.5191
INSR	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.553554916	0.218106368	0.011148659
INSR	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.553554916	0.802480269	0.490316813
ETFDH	Cervical cancer	Wald_ratio	0.060126354	1.261993315	0.962
GANAB	Cervical cancer	Wald_ratio	2.309154385	1.223908481	0.0592
PRKAB1	Cervical cancer	Wald_ratio	-1.311175245	1.374728742	0.3402
DPP4	Cervical cancer	rs188581353	-0.667724349	1.24825208	0.5927
DPP4	Cervical cancer	rs2080714	0.123259564	1.227272705	0.92

DPP4	Cervical cancer	rs4233648	-2.74313537	5.242490548	0.6008
DPP4	Cervical cancer	rs75850673	-3.579448002	1.704694253	0.03575
DPP4	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.995283848	0.808739334	0.218449731
DPP4	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.995283848	0.770092541	0.196211354
DPP4	Cervical cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.604219891	1.981041527	0.789178859
ABCC8	Cervical cancer	rs2074312	-1.131464976	0.519670042	0.02946
ABCC8	Cervical cancer	rs77023203	-0.663539124	0.431374084	0.124
ABCC8	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.854430565	0.229964123	0.000202806
ABCC8	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.854430565	0.331919211	0.010046856
RAMP1	Cervical cancer	Wald_ratio	5.915904805	6.059317124	0.3289
AMY2A	Cervical cancer	rs72681706	-1.082328426	1.35844019	0.4256
AMY2A	Cervical cancer	rs72692396	0.204638253	1.20999755	0.8657
AMY2A	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.364712578	0.639198857	0.568285976
AMY2A	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.364712578	0.90353889	0.68647084
AMY2A	Cervical cancer	rs72681706	-1.082328426	1.35844019	0.4256
AMY2A	Cervical cancer	rs72692396	0.204638253	1.20999755	0.8657
AMY2A	Cervical cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.364712578	0.639198857	0.568285976
AMY2A	Cervical cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.364712578	0.90353889	0.68647084
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10305525	-18.61037975	8.01943038	0.020305144
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11963172	-3.00825	4.720194444	0.523919782
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12215108	6.253160622	5.632176166	0.26688848
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	rs142878626	5.279400922	6.186843318	0.393477949
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	rs228817	3.464186047	5.958046512	0.560950789
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	rs28360624	-5.586047904	5.941179641	0.347101964
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	rs880347	3.507291866	3.570521531	0.32595641
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	rs9462535	2.203677419	4.910870968	0.653623166
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.735085759	2.200489865	0.738337673
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.735085759	1.842749626	0.689961718
GLP1R	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	8.303485284	9.625383702	0.421458733
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10766392	1.325083333	2.098036458	0.527659656
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10766393	1.318286089	2.115538058	0.533189512

KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10766395	-0.089167168	1.892646617	0.962423626
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs147673442	-0.536598446	4.106554404	0.896037332
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs189603359	-5.577782101	6.290389105	0.375232384
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2285676	-0.522039024	1.843126829	0.776996286
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2355016	0.690544444	2.533336111	0.785173755
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs35271178	0.219722481	1.158122481	0.849526191
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4148631	9.936153846	5.916342657	0.09306595
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs5210	-0.541071429	1.861108374	0.771261364
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs5219	0.113006057	1.031497981	0.912762074
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs7110037	0.593578947	2.402644737	0.804867736
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs7112030	0.262225806	1.877727047	0.888936018
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs739688	4.412832335	4.562796407	0.333477402
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs77902362	1.761175325	5.061298701	0.727863424
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	rs79506407	-1.793019465	7.049562044	0.79922919
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.305733991	0.310590479	0.324936722
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.305733991	0.510890052	0.549550367
KCNJ11	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.655773237	1.41260159	0.260699904
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs1078523	-12.015625	4.61028125	0.009153501
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11654396	1.337830882	6.270588235	0.831053867
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11869741	-0.23203844	5.029832869	0.963204694
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12603201	5.407368421	3.009862348	0.072407077
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12941945	1.832161572	4.36768559	0.674864562
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs59795094	-17.16107692	5.707592308	0.002640913
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs9892728	-12.93973684	4.859388158	0.007748597
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs9905939	-10.76311688	4.809512987	0.025228828
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.548063239	3.108890141	0.253760234
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.548063239	1.599052204	0.026496665
RAMP2	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	18.32488367	7.57910885	0.05201755
KCNJ8	Cervix uteri cancer	rs10841887	0.882423529	2.539538235	0.728235242
KCNJ8	Cervix uteri cancer	rs117973841	-6.161821192	5.611324503	0.272158821
KCNJ8	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12816749	4.022236686	5.085449704	0.428984617

KCNJ8	Cervix uteri cancer	rs59406438	-0.302928118	3.989048626	0.93946688
KCNJ8	Cervix uteri cancer	rs74732083	7.623026906	4.516860987	0.091472207
KCNJ8	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.337704168	1.764779395	0.448450512
KCNJ8	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.337704168	1.721730794	0.43718641
KCNJ8	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	0.658632331	6.007735482	0.919624365
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs111327339	2.559516616	4.249486405	0.546966481
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs1373641	-2.165824324	3.515301802	0.53781972
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs1699348	-7.288264	5.991272	0.223802034
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2120825	0.609	1.361394826	0.654632963
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2881654	0.926614431	1.268286359	0.465021384
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2920503	-8.551569767	4.779703488	0.073591899
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs310752	-0.813623077	5.714469231	0.886780281
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4135247	2.022206434	2.006924933	0.31363962
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4684833	3.490008772	3.901320175	0.371016339
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	rs76763697	-6.198348214	6.077678571	0.307797442
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.478161534	0.742389317	0.519520569
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.478161534	0.75791646	0.52811278
PPARG	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	2.057907495	1.207377822	0.126697666
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11150624	-0.428056557	6.124721311	0.94428124
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11865835	-2.794782609	7.096069565	0.693692244
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs12448775	-2.14461859	5.990160256	0.720325671
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs142133957	-4.213115824	4.738711256	0.373957544
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs34497199	-0.015035039	5.745697674	0.99791214
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4561482	8.09925641	6.402025641	0.205832472
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8054784	1.060747748	6.799045045	0.876021808
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8057029	-2.330836207	6.690439655	0.727552482
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8057326	-3.687447619	7.006333333	0.598678357
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.930402517	1.233388678	0.450641147
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.930402517	2.050003097	0.64993377
SLC5A2	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.475796111	5.015269676	0.401796285
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs111917515	-5.687896679	5.081808118	0.263026539

GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs112898001	-5.903067729	5.498247012	0.282989787
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs112968754	-5.848780488	5.576666667	0.294272449
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs113126535	-6.37392	5.48996	0.245636237
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs1659215	-8.148864865	7.390540541	0.270197685
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs34359922	-9.026779661	5.475889831	0.099258525
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4924660	-3.459752874	6.321436782	0.584169327
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs73402785	-6.21185654	5.68350211	0.274410121
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	rs8037100	-8.511487179	7.016820513	0.225125249
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-6.477335291	0.545090324	1.45E-32
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.477335291	1.942256196	0.000853135
GANC	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-7.089152801	13.27812751	0.609940224
KCNJ1	Cervix uteri cancer	rs116842927	5.997755991	6.27130719	0.338880026
KCNJ1	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4937311	6.406484127	6.553111111	0.328259913
KCNJ1	Cervix uteri cancer	rs7110898	14.49114894	9.265617021	0.117824566
KCNJ1	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	7.794431215	2.319160989	0.000776934
KCNJ1	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	7.794431215	4.070260721	0.055496203
KCNJ1	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	8.078631667	8.553196271	0.518160076
RAMP3	Cervix uteri cancer	rs11772021	-2.540393375	2.094679089	0.225212398
RAMP3	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4724382	-2.469378378	6.748261261	0.714418732
RAMP3	Cervix uteri cancer	rs73111954	-3.142357447	3.719331915	0.398182602
RAMP3	Cervix uteri cancer	rs75390434	-2.838529915	7.898470085	0.719312943
RAMP3	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.678584731	0.144797803	2.11E-76
RAMP3	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.678584731	1.719574206	0.11930383
RAMP3	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.556714777	3.143681072	0.501476293
ETFDH	Cervix uteri cancer	Wald_ratio	-7.406414286	5.034614286	0.14126444
GANAB	Cervix uteri cancer	Wald_ratio	6.465251397	4.985346369	0.194682461
PRKAB1	Cervix uteri cancer	Wald_ratio	-3.417494424	5.616579926	0.542878862
DPP4	Cervix uteri cancer	rs188581353	-5.18951189	5.587684606	0.353023318
DPP4	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2080714	7.032792208	5.008785714	0.160291678
DPP4	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4233648	7.000604839	6.16216129	0.255930104
DPP4	Cervix uteri cancer	rs75850673	-15.11459627	7.090186335	0.033026342

DPP4	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.018534178	4.946196556	0.997010208
DPP4	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.018534178	2.909687755	0.994917656
DPP4	Cervix uteri cancer	All - MR Egger	-8.384082205	12.25823407	0.564615353
ABCC8	Cervix uteri cancer	rs2074312	0.429235135	2.160054054	0.842485692
ABCC8	Cervix uteri cancer	rs77023203	-0.164794626	1.78389486	0.926396833
ABCC8	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.076074639	0.29165992	0.794221012
ABCC8	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.076074639	1.375470281	0.955893014
INSR	Cervix uteri cancer	rs4031066	-0.530744521	5.300869863	0.920245848
RAMP1	Cervix uteri cancer	Wald_ratio	-10.95676471	7.677539216	0.153545499
AMY2A	Cervix uteri cancer	rs72681706	8.819648712	5.626697892	0.117006178
AMY2A	Cervix uteri cancer	rs72692396	11.10734531	5.008103792	0.026563396
AMY2A	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	10.09611667	1.136134216	6.31E-19
AMY2A	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	10.09611667	3.740925557	0.006958402
AMY2A	Cervix uteri cancer	rs72681706	8.819648712	5.626697892	0.117006178
AMY2A	Cervix uteri cancer	rs72692396	11.10734531	5.008103792	0.026563396
AMY2A	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(random effects)	10.09611667	1.136134216	6.31E-19
AMY2A	Cervix uteri cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	10.09611667	3.740925557	0.006958402
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10305525	-0.240506329	3.696202532	0.948119466
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11963172	-0.405555556	3.227777778	0.900012593
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12215108	0.450777202	3.761658031	0.904614085
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs142878626	0.997695853	3.619815668	0.782839468
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs228817	-5.356589147	3.372093023	0.112172023
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs28360624	-1.419161677	4.107784431	0.729732755
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs880347	-2.732057416	2.200956938	0.214493339
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs9462535	-5.341935484	2.683870968	0.046548583
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-2.237481395	0.862131917	0.009451144
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.237481395	1.112049337	0.044216323
GLP1R	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.713461791	4.596171962	0.449958366
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10766392	-0.2265625	1.109375	0.838177401
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10766393	-0.267716535	1.118110236	0.810767037
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10766395	-0.711779449	1.027568922	0.488508556

KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs147673442	-7.049222798	2.507772021	0.00493954
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs189603359	1.031128405	3.949416342	0.794027928
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2285676	-0.685365854	1	0.493113086
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2355016	0.938888889	1.511111111	0.534386775
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs35271178	-0.120930233	0.634108527	0.848753551
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4148631	4.426573427	3.41958042	0.195500181
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs5210	-0.684729064	1.009852217	0.497740765
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs5219	-0.660834455	0.559892328	0.237885506
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs7110037	1.528947368	1.402631579	0.275688351
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs7112030	-1.081885856	1.019851117	0.288768416
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs739688	5.023952096	2.473053892	0.042206631
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs77902362	-4.100649351	3.642857143	0.260305883
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs79506407	-3.03892944	2.379562044	0.201568316
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.419516653	0.32250779	0.193328493
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.419516653	0.278976804	0.132640872
KCNJ11	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.710677275	0.85578469	0.065412129
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs1078523	0.61875	2.55	0.808278823
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11654396	-3.25	3.830882353	0.396232767
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11869741	0.512534819	2.991643454	0.863970457
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12603201	-0.44534413	1.647773279	0.786952335
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12941945	6.253275109	2.864628821	0.029041199
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs59795094	1.246153846	3.146153846	0.692040096
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs9892728	0.690789474	2.684210526	0.796906327
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs9905939	0.967532468	2.62987013	0.71294688
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.737143316	0.795199667	0.353930958
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.737143316	0.909756063	0.417788
RAMP2	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	1.564552922	3.291832333	0.651393105
KCNJ8	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs10841887	1.488235294	1.461764706	0.308626324
KCNJ8	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs117973841	3.443708609	3.798013245	0.3645585
KCNJ8	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12816749	0.514792899	3.118343195	0.868876773
KCNJ8	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs59406438	3.570824524	2.725158562	0.190088255

KCNJ8	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs74732083	1.230941704	3.002242152	0.681800469
KCNJ8	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.812631894	0.492871814	0.000235352
KCNJ8	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.812631894	1.062532063	0.088016457
KCNJ8	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.316986112	3.217442063	0.378405955
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs111327339	-7.427492447	2.959214502	0.012074687
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs1373641	1.040540541	2.009009009	0.604502072
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs1699348	-7.456	3.512	0.033753279
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2120825	-0.51856018	0.812148481	0.52314555
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2881654	-0.425028185	0.774520857	0.583168286
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2920503	-3.331395349	2.505813953	0.183694158
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs310752	3.915384615	3.161538462	0.215551911
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4135247	-0.243967828	1.091152815	0.823078506
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4684833	3.609649123	2.179824561	0.097734858
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs76763697	0.410714286	3.254464286	0.899573394
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.444292704	0.610990863	0.467123347
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.444292704	0.445868764	0.319024171
PPARG	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.599511618	1.042437293	0.581029647
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11150624	3.114754098	3.336065574	0.350478823
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11865835	0.27826087	4.060869565	0.945369723
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs12448775	1.990384615	3.830128205	0.603296896
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs142133957	4.32137031	3.323001631	0.193449582
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs34497199	2.976744186	3.503875969	0.395571137
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4561482	1.786324786	3.47008547	0.606707933
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8054784	3.279279279	3.675675676	0.37230886
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8057029	1.594827586	3.586206897	0.65652823
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8057326	2.552380952	4.714285714	0.588222162
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	2.529730044	0.391089567	9.90E-11
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.529730044	1.221252203	0.038319272
SLC5A2	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.923736783	3.409228897	0.28755888
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs111917515	-4.94095941	3.324723247	0.137245657
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs112898001	-4.398406375	3.589641434	0.220460244

GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs112968754	-4.601626016	3.695121951	0.213012481
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs113126535	-5.768	3.596	0.108713072
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs1659215	-3.983783784	4.048648649	0.325126016
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs34359922	-5.063559322	3.644067797	0.164670161
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4924660	-2.212643678	3.459770115	0.522475028
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs73402785	-4.64978903	3.772151899	0.217701823
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs8037100	-3.620512821	3.846153846	0.346534066
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-4.364628053	0.349834036	1.01E-35
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-4.364628053	1.215921139	0.00033123
GANC	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-9.805779748	7.874254122	0.253090081
KCNJ1	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs116842927	1.511982571	4.206971678	0.719296417
KCNJ1	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4937311	-3.206349206	3.5	0.359614567
KCNJ1	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs7110898	3.238297872	3.259574468	0.320479704
KCNJ1	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.553157039	2.014105718	0.78359167
KCNJ1	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.553157039	2.075003861	0.789791625
KCNJ1	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	5.751260543	5.041004841	0.458163397
RAMP3	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs11772021	2.182194617	1.33126294	0.101173427
RAMP3	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4724382	1.387387387	3.945945946	0.725139635
RAMP3	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs73111954	1.842553191	2.10212766	0.380748377
RAMP3	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs75390434	-1.230769231	4.179487179	0.768392269
RAMP3	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.827719544	0.4756106	0.000121594
RAMP3	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.827719544	1.047122844	0.080903417
RAMP3	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	2.817190538	1.928756808	0.281571276
INSR	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs144057856	14.11320755	9.807991121	0.150164727
INSR	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4031066	3.726027397	3.246575342	0.251100969
INSR	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	4.751759345	3.098763705	0.125168184
INSR	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	4.751759345	3.082110275	0.123140996
ETFDH	Cholangiocarcinoma	Wald_ratio	3.091428571	3.438571429	0.368628983
GANAB	Cholangiocarcinoma	Wald_ratio	2.044692737	3.05027933	0.502647657
PRKAB1	Cholangiocarcinoma	Wald_ratio	-5.933085502	3.851301115	0.123428649
DPP4	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs188581353	-3.227784731	3.04505632	0.28914086

DPP4	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2080714	-6.266233766	3.428571429	0.067601869
DPP4	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs4233648	-2.959677419	3.427419355	0.387846456
DPP4	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs75850673	-1.857142857	3.440993789	0.589396221
DPP4	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-3.558534512	0.915011129	0.000100633
DPP4	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.558534512	1.660910199	0.032151603
DPP4	Cholangiocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-3.262419756	3.643499602	0.465058913
ABCC8	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs2074312	-1.067567568	1.143243243	0.350403898
ABCC8	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs77023203	-1.025700935	0.962616822	0.286634357
ABCC8	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.043069441	0.020627551	0
ABCC8	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.043069441	0.736352668	0.156618879
RAMP1	Cholangiocarcinoma	Wald_ratio	-7.892156863	4.196078431	0.059993534
AMY2A	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs72681706	3.583138173	3.555035129	0.313500005
AMY2A	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs72692396	3.013972056	3.251497006	0.353952989
AMY2A	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	3.273223461	0.283453391	7.59E-31
AMY2A	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	3.273223461	2.399302112	0.172492102
AMY2A	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs72681706	3.583138173	3.555035129	0.313500005
AMY2A	Cholangiocarcinoma	rs72692396	3.013972056	3.251497006	0.353952989
AMY2A	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	3.273223461	0.283453391	7.59E-31
AMY2A	Cholangiocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	3.273223461	2.399302112	0.172492102
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs10305525	-4.953778481	8.231898734	0.547321685
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11963172	-2.555938889	4.820727778	0.59597485
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12215108	5.919481865	5.739430052	0.302366862
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs142878626	7.726635945	6.356290323	0.224141566
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs228817	8.082868217	6.092302326	0.184596495
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs28360624	-0.870844311	6.073952096	0.88599514
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs880347	3.461966507	3.654593301	0.343490075
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs9462535	2.138748387	5.025141935	0.670392382
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	2.579535136	1.455175088	0.076284554
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	2.579535136	1.885059335	0.171183595
GLP1R	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	6.183745111	8.059169404	0.472011303
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs10766392	0.06690026	2.148541667	0.975159867

KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs10766393	0.113274803	2.166992126	0.958311305
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs10766395	1.627175439	1.936411028	0.400737523
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs147673442	-3.298963731	4.210673575	0.433347357
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs189603359	-8.900583658	6.508560311	0.171462505
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2285676	1.394153659	1.885602439	0.459683712
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2355016	-1.626819444	2.590669444	0.530034529
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs35271178	0.557465116	1.183604651	0.637648382
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4148631	-7.992097902	6.051776224	0.186628035
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs5210	1.397972906	1.903938424	0.462794427
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs5219	-0.20573755	1.054606999	0.845326744
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs7110037	-1.080134211	2.455834211	0.660064765
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs7112030	2.196121588	1.921905707	0.253171828
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs739688	-5.414275449	4.654712575	0.24475588
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs77902362	2.099282468	5.19737013	0.686277106
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs79506407	-6.945085158	7.168077859	0.332599644
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	0.195148358	0.437062858	0.655236456
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	0.195148358	0.52257924	0.708826167
KCNJ11	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	1.655809844	1.443734948	0.270649347
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs1078523	0.340150625	4.7070625	0.942391905
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11654396	-2.493897059	6.409433824	0.697203748
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11869741	3.768913649	5.143481894	0.463707685
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12603201	2.777323887	3.07717004	0.366760621
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12941945	-4.781528384	4.477991266	0.285617861
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs59795094	1.995953846	5.823961538	0.73181354
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs9892728	0.105624342	4.959901316	0.983009811
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs9905939	1.735694805	4.918467532	0.724168348
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	0.766529614	1.009750272	0.447776045
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	0.766529614	1.634690598	0.639130975
RAMP2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	2.995848595	5.84149278	0.626379802
KCNJ8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs10841887	-0.479732353	2.602561765	0.853753935
KCNJ8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs117973841	-1.466039735	5.706125828	0.79723757

KCNJ8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12816749	-12.37278107	5.19612426	0.017258414
KCNJ8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs59406438	1.223890063	4.056088795	0.762849177
KCNJ8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs74732083	0.084175561	4.568295964	0.985298987
KCNJ8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	-1.529467699	1.984070597	0.44078184
KCNJ8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.529467699	1.756580675	0.383913966
KCNJ8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	9.2674749	5.185633795	0.171880575
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs111327339	5.350483384	4.296646526	0.213032659
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs1373641	5.602117117	3.596486486	0.119312946
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs1699348	-3.817728	6.116776	0.532535279
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2120825	0.347172103	1.389055118	0.802638388
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2881654	0.399700113	1.291431793	0.75694005
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2920503	0.169666279	4.887424419	0.972307107
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs310752	8.039307692	5.849215385	0.169309788
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4135247	3.79536193	2.04941555	0.064036731
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4684833	5.155614035	3.967517544	0.193787522
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs76763697	7.880982143	6.213214286	0.204647033
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	1.622909323	0.761117367	0.032984485
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	1.622909323	0.772739099	0.035710948
PPARG	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	0.20363969	1.231110238	0.872723746
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11150624	0.765089344	6.265254098	0.902806951
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11865835	8.371347826	7.260295652	0.248897555
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs12448775	-8.248782051	6.202083333	0.183517675
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs142133957	-2.719526917	4.775269168	0.56901529
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs34497199	-0.625220155	5.865372093	0.915110175
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4561482	2.120786325	6.533307692	0.745475179
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8054784	-2.721396396	6.943837838	0.695120786
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8057029	-2.633172414	6.832560345	0.699951528
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8057326	2.66147619	7.159228571	0.710075565
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	-0.808914223	1.450460287	0.577052779
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.808914223	2.092144534	0.699020101
SLC5A2	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	-6.229381525	5.09054824	0.260647577

GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs111917515	4.048708487	5.198118081	0.436050602
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs112898001	3.629406375	5.62310757	0.518638883
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs112968754	1.571861789	5.705447154	0.782930632
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs113126535	4.80624	5.61848	0.392310812
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs1659215	5.722432432	7.566594595	0.44948385
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs34359922	-1.315313559	5.59940678	0.81428456
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4924660	1.207810345	6.446321839	0.85137504
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs73402785	1.410658228	5.815400844	0.808336333
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs8037100	5.924564103	7.18425641	0.409565026
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	2.796839349	0.78520226	0.000368132
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	2.796839349	1.986526318	0.15915935
GANC	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	2.13503853	13.56993779	0.879422246
KCNJ1	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs116842927	-7.625686275	6.373420479	0.231508311
KCNJ1	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4937311	-6.88784127	6.705206349	0.304308513
KCNJ1	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs7110898	-6.480553191	9.399276596	0.490525273
KCNJ1	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	-7.120814691	0.322770808	7.41E-108
KCNJ1	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	-7.120814691	4.145870907	0.085875464
KCNJ1	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	-7.669556459	8.69899895	0.53998529
RAMP3	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs11772021	-0.625436853	2.146728778	0.770788131
RAMP3	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4724382	0.473513514	6.89381982	0.94523903
RAMP3	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs73111954	-3.209634043	3.804391489	0.398856323
RAMP3	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs75390434	-8.116401709	8.07557265	0.314869947
RAMP3	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	-1.463647938	1.076335803	0.173879544
RAMP3	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.463647938	1.761008723	0.405893535
RAMP3	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	-0.051914454	3.219070382	0.988597119
ETFDH	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	Wald_ratio	1.866371429	5.090714286	0.713900472
GANAB	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	Wald_ratio	-6.222346369	5.070776536	0.219785269
PRKAB1	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	Wald_ratio	-3.291910781	5.761003717	0.567719911
DPP4	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs188581353	10.81946183	5.7122403	0.058213887
DPP4	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2080714	4.366084416	5.122733766	0.394049943
DPP4	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4233648	8.084112903	6.28325	0.198229112

DPP4	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs75850673	-6.748881988	7.235714286	0.350965515
DPP4	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	5.069858317	3.402124999	0.136170757
DPP4	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	5.069858317	2.972412763	0.088075615
DPP4	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	All - MR Egger	10.26986264	8.657060337	0.357329073
ABCC8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs2074312	0.928697297	2.211021622	0.674462915
ABCC8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs77023203	1.506647196	1.826322243	0.409392981
ABCC8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	1.272246829	0.283774799	7.35E-06
ABCC8	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	1.272246829	1.408079051	0.366242728
INSR	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs4031066	2.736917808	5.415232877	0.613270253
RAMP1	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	Wald_ratio	3.124715686	7.855872549	0.6908105
AMY2A	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs72681706	12.79742389	5.733629977	0.025615404
AMY2A	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs72692396	8.444451098	5.121237525	0.099166421
AMY2A	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	10.37613763	2.16267567	1.60E-06
AMY2A	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	10.37613763	3.819486783	0.006595002
AMY2A	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs72681706	12.79742389	5.733629977	0.025615404
AMY2A	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	rs72692396	8.444451098	5.121237525	0.099166421
AMY2A	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(random effects)	10.37613763	2.16267567	1.60E-06
AMY2A	Chronic lymphocytic leuke	IVW(fixed effects)	10.37613763	3.819486783	0.006595002
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10305525	0.549093038	14.80835443	0.970421259
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11963172	7.877833333	8.694611111	0.364904461
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12215108	13.68518135	10.3246114	0.185008293
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs142878626	6.789930876	11.31582949	0.548480724
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs228817	8.609612403	10.95317829	0.43184533
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs28360624	9.177724551	10.98407186	0.403408962
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs880347	-18.72660287	6.596363636	0.004526534
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs9462535	-1.618748387	9.026	0.857668518
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-0.164557059	4.505893006	0.970867405
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.164557059	3.393056981	0.961319222
GLP1R	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-10.42467023	20.22181024	0.624629235
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10766392	-1.863635417	3.861848958	0.629396861
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10766393	-2.487769029	3.894829396	0.522994475

KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10766395	-1.28735589	3.482180451	0.711607364
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs147673442	0.862795337	7.581295337	0.909391745
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs189603359	1.045461089	11.49700389	0.92754555
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2285676	-0.819397561	3.391365854	0.809080166
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2355016	-3.955444444	4.655472222	0.395528966
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs35271178	-1.351702326	2.13124031	0.525928961
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4148631	8.055384615	10.87685315	0.458936723
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs5210	-0.838458128	3.424359606	0.806571746
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs5219	-1.563216689	1.897388964	0.410008982
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs7110037	-3.862605263	4.412368421	0.381354087
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs7112030	0.445622829	3.457419355	0.897445594
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs739688	-8.574371257	8.368682635	0.305562172
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs77902362	-2.129892857	9.35262987	0.819854614
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs79506407	-3.25136253	12.99817518	0.802479144
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-1.491700299	0.398586537	0.000182216
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.491700299	0.939971397	0.112520911
KCNJ11	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-1.28571054	2.596918195	0.628215584
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs1078523	13.097125	8.46925	0.122000106
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11654396	-3.765066176	11.49566176	0.743274156
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11869741	8.578467967	9.297019499	0.356157506
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12603201	-4.330202429	5.535101215	0.434028442
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12941945	7.19650655	8.031484716	0.370233064
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs59795094	14.85138462	10.48161538	0.156512619
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs9892728	13.56789474	8.925	0.128457628
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs9905939	11.08824675	8.847662338	0.210118278
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	5.799644991	2.890580951	0.044814202
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	5.799644991	2.940522807	0.048573358
RAMP2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-7.022624315	10.52064788	0.529269737
KCNJ8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs10841887	6.528176471	4.673411765	0.16245088
KCNJ8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs117973841	-3.029165563	10.22682119	0.767078758
KCNJ8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12816749	-3.462792899	9.356508876	0.711312046

KCNJ8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs59406438	-9.37807611	7.277272727	0.197509344
KCNJ8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs74732083	3.953139013	8.250134529	0.631824416
KCNJ8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	1.10994712	3.134124641	0.723227219
KCNJ8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	1.10994712	3.156843317	0.725138025
KCNJ8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	2.005524884	10.68317368	0.863070019
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs111327339	8.182643505	7.732145015	0.289935525
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs1373641	11.90833333	6.472477477	0.065791496
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs1699348	18.47352	11.00256	0.093148116
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2120825	-4.370044994	2.4884027	0.079060289
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2881654	-1.876471251	2.31464487	0.417540789
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2920503	-6.276802326	8.771337209	0.47423602
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs310752	2.612007692	10.50930769	0.803714832
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4135247	-0.636938338	3.685495979	0.862790586
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4684833	8.177675439	7.118114035	0.250616092
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs76763697	7.844241071	11.19638393	0.48354964
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-0.69777499	1.680488493	0.677979745
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.69777499	1.386229156	0.614709829
PPARG	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-4.809519814	2.207796025	0.061011988
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11150624	-1.338163934	11.28344262	0.905595942
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11865835	-3.164382609	13.04617391	0.808352052
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs12448775	-6.919679487	11.01913462	0.530023978
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs142133957	-11.97491028	8.612854812	0.164421649
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs34497199	-5.796023256	10.54906977	0.582707278
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4561482	-4.189854701	11.76376068	0.721716054
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8054784	-5.848117117	12.50873874	0.64012608
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8057029	-6.868189655	12.30775862	0.576818844
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8057326	-2.036790476	12.87428571	0.874294401
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-6.011016058	1.211588759	7.00E-07
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.011016058	3.761307396	0.110016541
SLC5A2	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-12.40093316	9.147065614	0.217295806
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs111917515	19.63940959	9.354391144	0.035774115

GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs112898001	21.46055777	10.12322709	0.034011741
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs112968754	21.21857724	10.27284553	0.038875579
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs113126535	20.9468	10.10924	0.038261247
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs1659215	27.32502703	13.60432432	0.044584399
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs34359922	32.66970339	10.34779661	0.001593111
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4924660	23.19706897	11.6112069	0.045736481
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs73402785	19.27835443	10.49101266	0.066120391
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs8037100	26.31502564	12.92061538	0.041683155
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	23.13879376	1.494624046	4.64E-54
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	23.13879376	3.587887647	1.12E-10
GANC	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	12.5805618	24.43522328	0.622508913
KCNJ1	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs116842927	-8.358148148	11.53570806	0.468730756
KCNJ1	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4937311	4.318468254	12.07857143	0.720694042
KCNJ1	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs7110898	23.14514894	16.88489362	0.170449559
KCNJ1	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	2.683625194	8.198270046	0.743410421
KCNJ1	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	2.683625194	7.47923415	0.719737112
KCNJ1	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	-5.840249053	22.36754625	0.837406296
RAMP3	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs11772021	4.974554865	3.847018634	0.195978716
RAMP3	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4724382	16.72234234	12.38387387	0.176909482
RAMP3	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs73111954	-0.341481702	6.835787234	0.960158254
RAMP3	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs75390434	-13.25940171	14.57316239	0.362901263
RAMP3	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	3.746805393	3.116276546	0.229234131
RAMP3	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	3.746805393	3.159131788	0.235612913
RAMP3	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	4.618000071	6.938759496	0.574190091
ETFDH	Chronic myelogenous leuk	Wald_ratio	-2.712771429	9.145028571	0.766742191
GANAB	Chronic myelogenous leuk	Wald_ratio	14.46424581	9.140614525	0.113554856
PRKAB1	Chronic myelogenous leuk	Wald_ratio	14.89185874	10.35026022	0.150209816
DPP4	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs188581353	22.05556946	10.33246558	0.03279458
DPP4	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2080714	9.233116883	9.228701299	0.317079016
DPP4	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4233648	0.922346774	11.29935484	0.934942321
DPP4	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs75850673	4.418124224	13.05726708	0.735088028

DPP4	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	10.00226499	4.586378162	0.02919351
DPP4	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	10.00226499	5.360106758	0.062033384
DPP4	Chronic myelogenous leuk	All - MR Egger	25.94352291	12.34738148	0.170409997
ABCC8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs2074312	0.971386486	3.974702703	0.806927053
ABCC8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs77023203	0.407514019	3.285607477	0.901291492
ABCC8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	0.63640944	0.27690199	0.021543571
ABCC8	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	0.63640944	2.532402641	0.80157709
INSR	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs4031066	-3.071726027	9.728972603	0.752207648
RAMP1	Chronic myelogenous leuk	Wald_ratio	-9.058970588	14.12303922	0.521241988
AMY2A	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs72681706	-5.57882904	10.38487119	0.591124401
AMY2A	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs72692396	-7.541377246	9.257744511	0.415300162
AMY2A	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-6.672347911	0.974833307	7.67E-12
AMY2A	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.672347911	6.910479228	0.334274136
AMY2A	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs72681706	-5.57882904	10.38487119	0.591124401
AMY2A	Chronic myelogenous leuk	rs72692396	-7.541377246	9.257744511	0.415300162
AMY2A	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(random effects)	-6.672347911	0.974833307	7.67E-12
AMY2A	Chronic myelogenous leuk	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.672347911	6.910479228	0.334274136
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs10766392	0.002043659	0.003370885	0.544337022
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs10766393	0.002104638	0.00339916	0.535808281
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs10766395	0.004345539	0.003038321	0.152647119
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs2285676	0.003854049	0.002960366	0.192956523
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs35271178	0.001592186	0.001858248	0.391543793
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs4148631	-0.013816853	0.009493776	0.145569887
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs5210	0.003911773	0.00298936	0.190681511
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs5219	0.00164319	0.001656837	0.321313153
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs7112030	0.003685385	0.003015236	0.221611503
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	rs739688	-0.015755988	0.007265928	0.030122518
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.002090541	0.000948207	0.027473058
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.002090541	0.000876116	0.017025984
KCNJ11	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	0.005701058	0.002286178	0.037306071
RAMP2	Coloc cancer	rs1078523	0.008402938	0.007395313	0.255851177

RAMP2	Coloc cancer	rs11654396	0.010381912	0.010057574	0.301955879
RAMP2	Coloc cancer	rs12603201	-0.008360607	0.00483	0.083456296
RAMP2	Coloc cancer	rs59795094	0.008622154	0.009121615	0.344534229
RAMP2	Coloc cancer	rs9892728	0.009044079	0.007791053	0.245711493
RAMP2	Coloc cancer	rs9905939	0.008160779	0.007694675	0.288883152
RAMP2	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.00247687	0.003708268	0.504177142
RAMP2	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.00247687	0.00293082	0.39804857
RAMP2	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.030905184	0.012632327	0.070710134
KCNJ8	Coloc cancer	rs10841887	-7.88E-04	0.004081294	0.846963212
KCNJ8	Coloc cancer	rs12816749	-0.002134716	0.008161124	0.793651964
KCNJ8	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.001057155	0.000538877	0.04978899
KCNJ8	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.001057155	0.003650289	0.772115809
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	rs11150624	-0.014380164	0.009839016	0.143865971
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	rs11865835	0.005818678	0.011398957	0.609731264
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	rs34497199	0.00283069	0.009193876	0.758167074
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	rs4561482	-0.023595556	0.010256154	0.021412883
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	rs8054784	-0.022584595	0.01087964	0.037907021
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	rs8057029	-0.027223707	0.010706034	0.010995633
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	rs8057326	-0.00117561	0.011244857	0.916735735
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.011361809	0.005148974	0.027340891
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.011361809	0.00393919	0.003922837
SLC5A2	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	0.025182322	0.089191759	0.788997694
GLP1R	Coloc cancer	rs11963172	-7.17E-04	0.007591833	0.924792248
GLP1R	Coloc cancer	rs228817	0.024070233	0.009551938	0.011737756
GLP1R	Coloc cancer	rs880347	-0.007660766	0.005723828	0.180766393
GLP1R	Coloc cancer	rs9462535	-0.004642123	0.007857677	0.554670915
GLP1R	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	-7.68E-04	0.006128872	0.900259066
GLP1R	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-7.68E-04	0.003650764	0.83334784
GLP1R	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.050793245	0.022221232	0.149600986
PPARG	Coloc cancer	rs1373641	-0.002071081	0.00562009	0.712490114
PPARG	Coloc cancer	rs1699348	0.004352248	0.00956712	0.649168766

PPARG	Coloc cancer	rs2920503	-0.002639552	0.007633198	0.729493757
PPARG	Coloc cancer	rs310752	-0.011423923	0.009157538	0.212218468
PPARG	Coloc cancer	rs4135247	0.001921075	0.003203727	0.548747747
PPARG	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	-7.32E-05	0.001874691	0.96885099
PPARG	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-7.32E-05	0.002431787	0.975984408
PPARG	Coloc cancer	All - MR Egger	0.004694209	0.005869568	0.482321872
ABCC8	Coloc cancer	rs2074312	0.004106811	0.003471811	0.236848119
ABCC8	Coloc cancer	rs77023203	0.004044696	0.002859439	0.157213153
ABCC8	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.004069801	3.05E-05	0
ABCC8	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.004069801	0.002207194	0.065200564
DPP4	Coloc cancer	rs2080714	1.65E-04	0.008034545	0.983635589
DPP4	Coloc cancer	rs4233648	0.014612984	0.009751613	0.133998283
DPP4	Coloc cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.006006949	0.007090681	0.396905307
DPP4	Coloc cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.006006949	0.006200921	0.332685456
INSR	Coloc cancer	rs4031066	0.00644863	0.008488151	0.447421105
RAMP1	Coloc cancer	Wald_ratio	-0.001744294	0.012061373	0.885012318
RAMP3	Coloc cancer	rs4724382	-0.019832072	0.010815225	0.06669588
KCNJ1	Coloc cancer	rs4937311	6.10E-04	0.010513651	0.953723531
KCNJ1	Coloc cancer	rs4937311	6.10E-04	0.010513651	0.953723531
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	rs10305525	9.363101266	8.666582278	0.27997818
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	rs11963172	5.340194444	5.095461111	0.294624936
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	rs12215108	6.310103627	6.068341969	0.298414325
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	rs142878626	-3.52859447	6.671451613	0.596868197
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	rs228817	7.313697674	6.439263566	0.25604144
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	rs28360624	-0.049613832	6.419461078	0.993833483
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	rs880347	-0.853497608	3.855822967	0.824817661
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	rs9462535	8.614258065	5.303658065	0.104330853
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.350239144	1.641950325	0.041310278
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.350239144	1.989490746	0.092187815
GLP1R	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-10.32402357	8.48085189	0.269178791
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs10766392	-0.209357292	2.265578125	0.926373972

KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs10766393	-0.235401575	2.284934383	0.917944446
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs10766395	0.650669173	2.044689223	0.750315033
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs147673442	-3.156709845	4.456813472	0.478766101
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs189603359	11.10920233	6.79463035	0.102049612
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs2285676	0.678641463	1.990941463	0.733205516
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs2355016	-2.293147222	2.735997222	0.401952386
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs35271178	-0.525875969	1.250750388	0.674157935
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs4148631	4.119426573	6.390013986	0.51914347
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs5210	0.673899015	2.010302956	0.737457163
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs5219	-0.779983849	1.113751009	0.483726508
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs7110037	-2.057276316	2.594184211	0.427758006
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs7112030	0.757933002	2.028779156	0.708708862
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs739688	5.240005988	4.918820359	0.28674142
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs77902362	-4.120454545	5.470909091	0.451355458
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	rs79506407	10.22187348	7.678053528	0.183086856
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.167547091	0.438224203	0.702215197
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.167547091	0.551820267	0.761412688
KCNJ11	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.716124071	1.524942097	0.279355724
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	rs1078523	-2.51636875	4.97433125	0.612947377
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	rs11654396	5.258933824	6.769639706	0.437252571
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	rs11869741	6.774568245	5.435041783	0.212595156
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	rs12603201	0.487238866	3.250433198	0.880843771
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	rs12941945	7.623799127	4.725458515	0.106669379
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	rs59795094	-3.253015385	6.155553846	0.597174309
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	rs9892728	-2.835197368	5.241756579	0.588585554
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	rs9905939	3.395480519	5.196149351	0.513459178
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.689747916	1.471051331	0.250693375
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.689747916	1.726851381	0.327820267
RAMP2	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	8.258912208	6.171121295	0.229276029
KCNJ8	Connective tissue cancer	rs10841887	-2.0209	2.744026471	0.461443205
KCNJ8	Connective tissue cancer	rs117973841	0.643692053	6.043145695	0.915172916

KCNJ8	Connective tissue cancer	rs12816749	1.726609467	5.493633136	0.753298649
KCNJ8	Connective tissue cancer	rs59406438	3.090443975	4.288879493	0.471173245
KCNJ8	Connective tissue cancer	rs74732083	-2.415784753	4.859484305	0.61909893
KCNJ8	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.440794618	1.083717776	0.684196756
KCNJ8	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.440794618	1.856839301	0.812354441
KCNJ8	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.524904287	5.486699386	0.799121739
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs111327339	-0.449034743	4.540075529	0.921213949
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs1373641	1.249738739	3.797900901	0.742110045
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs1699348	-10.79848	6.464376	0.094828434
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs2120825	0.135110236	1.465275591	0.926532725
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs2881654	0.409676437	1.363799324	0.763877029
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs2920503	-5.263895349	5.158854651	0.307557167
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs310752	2.275669231	6.174169231	0.712441537
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs4135247	3.404477212	2.165126005	0.115854273
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs4684833	-1.867149123	4.196557018	0.656374645
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	rs76763697	-5.674910714	6.57375	0.387989908
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.293198353	0.743348708	0.693264271
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.293198353	0.815889459	0.719325503
PPARG	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	1.341388157	1.299665582	0.332213912
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs11150624	4.977491803	6.615811475	0.451832788
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs11865835	-4.633226087	7.661973913	0.545375706
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs12448775	3.603429487	6.512788462	0.580068132
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs142133957	-1.109797716	5.024208809	0.825178048
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs34497199	6.40972093	6.194162791	0.300762227
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs4561482	2.112854701	6.904504274	0.759596222
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs8054784	10.20099099	7.336378378	0.164387157
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs8057029	7.697008621	7.219706897	0.286373488
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	rs8057326	3.958247619	7.558866667	0.600517664
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.377375816	1.449605722	0.019813646
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.377375816	2.206590126	0.12587176
SLC5A2	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.873285874	5.354260174	0.875047657

GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs111917515	2.492523985	5.490479705	0.649848989
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs112898001	1.327286853	5.937171315	0.823103252
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs112968754	4.261504065	6.031544715	0.479854813
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs113126535	3.321072	5.93288	0.575633597
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs1659215	5.237572973	7.988108108	0.512035659
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs34359922	3.92459322	5.923728814	0.507637545
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs4924660	1.070505747	6.815114943	0.875183246
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs73402785	5.929873418	6.145400844	0.334580544
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	rs8037100	4.98125641	7.584564103	0.511333714
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.490762698	0.554533079	3.07E-10
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.490762698	2.098871041	0.096279999
GANC	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	3.19640949	14.33676734	0.829939093
KCNJ1	Connective tissue cancer	rs116842927	1.566738562	6.701285403	0.815142794
KCNJ1	Connective tissue cancer	rs4937311	-1.955730159	7.087095238	0.78258146
KCNJ1	Connective tissue cancer	rs7110898	-4.275914894	9.956	0.667573068
KCNJ1	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.902826942	1.61505938	0.576158023
KCNJ1	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.902826942	4.374101746	0.836476267
KCNJ1	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	1.693206953	9.158520022	0.883617248
RAMP3	Connective tissue cancer	rs11772021	-2.312339545	2.263354037	0.306949953
RAMP3	Connective tissue cancer	rs4724382	-0.70734955	7.277684685	0.922572086
RAMP3	Connective tissue cancer	rs73111954	-3.008668085	4.022110638	0.454440763
RAMP3	Connective tissue cancer	rs75390434	-3.367555556	8.527264957	0.692904692
RAMP3	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.406424604	0.324243422	1.16E-13
RAMP3	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.406424604	1.858060452	0.195276358
RAMP3	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.542737455	3.39535364	0.532021461
ETFDH	Connective tissue cancer	Wald_ratio	5.926985714	5.406228571	0.272936397
GANAB	Connective tissue cancer	Wald_ratio	-7.616424581	5.363301676	0.155578577
PRKAB1	Connective tissue cancer	Wald_ratio	-6.19267658	6.066245353	0.307329416
DPP4	Connective tissue cancer	rs188581353	-0.816866083	6.05669587	0.892714723
DPP4	Connective tissue cancer	rs2080714	7.378376623	5.409383117	0.172568843
DPP4	Connective tissue cancer	rs4233648	9.306612903	6.643209677	0.161237655

DPP4	Connective tissue cancer	rs75850673	9.538509317	7.659130435	0.212992991
DPP4	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	5.965610571	2.430741404	0.014118469
DPP4	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	5.965610571	3.144393641	0.057798738
DPP4	Connective tissue cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.489568279	7.239002559	0.763705177
ABCC8	Connective tissue cancer	rs2074312	0.412443243	2.331764865	0.859602422
ABCC8	Connective tissue cancer	rs77023203	0.816873832	1.927619159	0.671731039
ABCC8	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.652689976	0.198606734	0.001014971
ABCC8	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.652689976	1.485689252	0.66043116
INSR	Connective tissue cancer	rs4031066	-2.954287671	5.721931507	0.605638253
RAMP1	Connective tissue cancer	Wald_ratio	3.401	8.298794118	0.681939037
AMY2A	Connective tissue cancer	rs72681706	-6.833512881	6.073583138	0.260537977
AMY2A	Connective tissue cancer	rs72692396	-2.895748503	5.406267465	0.592215638
AMY2A	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-4.636502057	1.955621231	0.017746803
AMY2A	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-4.636502057	4.038208728	0.250903303
AMY2A	Connective tissue cancer	rs72681706	-6.833512881	6.073583138	0.260537977
AMY2A	Connective tissue cancer	rs72692396	-2.895748503	5.406267465	0.592215638
AMY2A	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-4.636502057	1.955621231	0.017746803
AMY2A	Connective tissue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-4.636502057	4.038208728	0.250903303
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	rs10305525	-0.1132	1.693411392	0.946703258
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	rs11963172	3.338633333	0.984361111	0.000694667
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	rs12215108	0.045649534	1.162994819	0.968689708
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	rs142878626	0.64085023	1.383817972	0.643290552
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	rs228817	0.841	1.254868217	0.502736744
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	rs28360624	4.361047904	1.211652695	0.000319129
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	rs880347	1.480181818	0.765301435	0.053098856
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	rs9462535	0.289742581	1.016729032	0.775663126
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.520618894	0.541434189	0.00497726
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.520618894	0.388272678	8.99E-05
GLP1R	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	1.349587178	2.582236588	0.619951533
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs10766392	-0.00754474	0.437669271	0.986246389
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs10766393	-0.009447454	0.441349081	0.982921904

KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs10766395	-0.384989975	0.394305764	0.328879062
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs147673442	-0.769753886	0.839699482	0.35929901
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs189603359	0.367044747	1.32313035	0.781468114
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs2285676	-0.381117073	0.382946341	0.319627734
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs2355016	0.491736111	0.531080556	0.354489511
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs35271178	0.013976977	0.238524031	0.953272485
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs4148631	1.291538462	1.223804196	0.291266513
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs5210	-0.373660099	0.386738916	0.333953223
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs5219	-0.10065895	0.211403769	0.633970733
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs7110037	0.426939474	0.503647368	0.396607721
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs7112030	-0.409952854	0.391121588	0.294570962
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs739688	-1.055143713	0.939994012	0.261649711
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs77902362	-0.356668831	1.159698052	0.758422346
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	rs79506407	-1.394944039	1.438761557	0.332273351
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.124032361	0.080759929	0.124583607
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.124032361	0.105831327	0.241204471
KCNJ11	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.074279429	0.290936252	0.802194976
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	rs1078523	-0.22883625	0.96115	0.811814481
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	rs11654396	-1.193602941	1.294235294	0.356400428
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	rs11869741	-0.282306407	1.093740947	0.796321357
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	rs12603201	0.041489474	0.622643725	0.946872782
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	rs12941945	0.094378603	0.907078603	0.917132229
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	rs59795094	-0.453476154	1.187653846	0.702591034
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	rs9892728	-0.238645395	1.013019737	0.813759969
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	rs9905939	-0.93488961	0.991084416	0.34552764
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.275241094	0.148841836	0.064426253
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.275241094	0.333117193	0.408657162
RAMP2	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.623909349	1.202942485	0.622568124
KCNJ8	Endometrial cancer	rs10841887	0.260742647	0.533147059	0.6247969
KCNJ8	Endometrial cancer	rs117973841	0.007788642	1.287718543	0.995174101
KCNJ8	Endometrial cancer	rs12816749	1.665869822	1.078059172	0.122286054

KCNJ8	Endometrial cancer	rs59406438	0.837993658	0.829486258	0.312372547
KCNJ8	Endometrial cancer	rs74732083	0.294459641	0.95346861	0.757450903
KCNJ8	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.517217621	0.239394697	0.030732246
KCNJ8	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.517217621	0.364300744	0.155679166
KCNJ8	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.353916135	1.071967034	0.762993806
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs111327339	-0.08235997	0.89452719	0.926641668
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs1373641	0.178159459	0.723671171	0.805536382
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs1699348	1.922384	1.229024	0.117781179
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs2120825	0.338861642	0.276946007	0.221116095
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs2881654	0.798390079	0.261332582	0.002250059
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs2920503	1.25922093	0.980761628	0.199169427
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs310752	0.095911538	1.190430769	0.935784906
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs4135247	1.35172118	0.414892761	0.001121999
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs4684833	0.493232456	0.807802632	0.541474121
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	rs76763697	-0.313963839	1.396066964	0.822063545
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.667673123	0.1444303	3.79E-06
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.667673123	0.155980234	1.86E-05
PPARG	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.556160038	0.24799634	0.055199853
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs11150624	3.19692623	1.278221311	0.012381727
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs11865835	1.283713043	1.520104348	0.398395604
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs12448775	-2.015608974	1.530391026	0.187820228
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs142133957	-0.514417618	1.234862969	0.676986587
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs34497199	0.949682171	1.195046512	0.426798399
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs4561482	2.664974359	1.347854701	0.048019359
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs8054784	2.623423423	1.407891892	0.062410237
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs8057029	2.763034483	1.386465517	0.046276557
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	rs8057326	2.138028571	1.446561905	0.139405914
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.481060655	0.562153342	0.008423143
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.481060655	0.452640152	0.001067712
SLC5A2	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.088700572	1.288258353	0.14897619
GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs111917515	0.881199262	1.057143911	0.40452557

GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs112898001	1.37185259	1.145123506	0.230918843
GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs112968754	1.436865854	1.156069106	0.213908651
GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs113126535	0.958164	1.147104	0.403554692
GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs1659215	1.891118919	1.530205405	0.216510786
GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs34359922	1.507699153	1.122110169	0.179068563
GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs4924660	0.835649425	1.309017241	0.523226845
GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs73402785	1.40828692	1.180687764	0.232960134
GANC	Endometrial cancer	rs8037100	1.715087179	1.455815385	0.238759186
GANC	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.290683426	0.115923372	8.58E-29
GANC	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.290683426	0.402923162	0.001358628
GANC	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	0.777898468	2.754943781	0.785830427
KCNJ1	Endometrial cancer	rs116842927	-2.422200436	1.248043573	0.052282787
KCNJ1	Endometrial cancer	rs4937311	0.230111111	1.351349206	0.864787979
KCNJ1	Endometrial cancer	rs7110898	-2.305574468	2.088365957	0.269589305
KCNJ1	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.379737304	0.902889499	0.126478952
KCNJ1	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.379737304	0.83950637	0.100277411
KCNJ1	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.606018507	1.726191575	0.28422573
RAMP3	Endometrial cancer	rs11772021	-0.791846791	0.440178054	0.07203073
RAMP3	Endometrial cancer	rs4724382	0.656628829	1.39427027	0.637677852
RAMP3	Endometrial cancer	rs73111954	-0.108220851	0.785919149	0.890477736
RAMP3	Endometrial cancer	rs75390434	-0.59522735	1.65634188	0.719323838
RAMP3	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.540697275	0.243903895	0.026633645
RAMP3	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.540697275	0.361338042	0.134555915
RAMP3	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.06072302	0.658462089	0.248503387
ETFDH	Endometrial cancer	Wald_ratio	0.42517	1.12542	0.705588202
GANAB	Endometrial cancer	Wald_ratio	-2.078575419	1.056581006	0.049152604
PRKAB1	Endometrial cancer	Wald_ratio	-1.204446097	1.175657993	0.305605402
ABCC8	Endometrial cancer	rs2074312	-0.282440541	0.448624324	0.528975775
ABCC8	Endometrial cancer	rs77023203	-0.341897196	0.369457944	0.354756732
ABCC8	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.317869149	0.029176708	1.22E-27
ABCC8	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.317869149	0.285194941	0.265035599

DPP4	Endometrial cancer	rs2080714	0.706363636	1.103285714	0.522018944
DPP4	Endometrial cancer	rs4233648	2.401725806	1.336604839	0.072353805
DPP4	Endometrial cancer	rs75850673	-1.781714286	1.510509317	0.238181078
DPP4	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.628597682	1.088411875	0.563577029
DPP4	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.628597682	0.741338437	0.396481027
DPP4	Endometrial cancer	All - MR Egger	-11.00988256	7.198215163	0.368627681
INSR	Endometrial cancer	rs4031066	-1.744732877	1.143986301	0.127225575
RAMP1	Endometrial cancer	Wald_ratio	0.50524902	1.583294118	0.749641169
AMY2A	Endometrial cancer	rs72681706	-0.44542623	1.195126464	0.709370119
AMY2A	Endometrial cancer	rs72692396	-0.54160479	1.20155489	0.652167388
AMY2A	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.49325754	0.048088589	1.10E-24
AMY2A	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.49325754	0.847345675	0.560485317
AMY2A	Endometrial cancer	rs72681706	-0.44542623	1.195126464	0.709370119
AMY2A	Endometrial cancer	rs72692396	-0.54160479	1.20155489	0.652167388
AMY2A	Endometrial cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.49325754	0.048088589	1.10E-24
AMY2A	Endometrial cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.49325754	0.847345675	0.560485317
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	rs10305525	3.044303797	3.170886076	0.337015034
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	rs11963172	-1.477777778	1.805555556	0.413093695
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	rs12215108	-0.124352332	2.098445596	0.95274561
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	rs142878626	2.209677419	2.652073733	0.404738409
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	rs228817	-0.713178295	2.209302326	0.746841398
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	rs28360624	0.74251497	2.215568862	0.73752315
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	rs880347	0.421052632	1.354066986	0.755835543
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	rs9462535	1.793548387	1.819354839	0.324223608
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.448934594	0.471755118	0.341286521
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.448934594	0.701588949	0.522248896
GLP1R	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	1.638695815	3.169384804	0.623628011
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs10766392	-0.5546875	0.778645833	0.476232851
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs10766393	-0.582677165	0.784776903	0.457799644
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs10766395	-0.92481203	0.69924812	0.185974874
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs147673442	-1.274611399	1.455958549	0.381331911

KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs189603359	3.272373541	2.76848249	0.237201797
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs2285676	-0.929268293	0.680487805	0.172067248
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs2355016	2.383333333	0.955555556	0.012624635
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs35271178	0.291472868	0.426356589	0.494204816
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs4148631	2.874125874	2.223776224	0.196200371
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs5210	-0.933497537	0.687192118	0.17432952
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs5219	0.156123822	0.380888291	0.681883712
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs7110037	2.189473684	0.907894737	0.015882948
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs7112030	-0.873449132	0.697270471	0.210326178
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs739688	1.275449102	1.688622754	0.450057512
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs77902362	-3.551948052	2.292207792	0.12124354
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	rs79506407	-0.941605839	2.557177616	0.712708645
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.055732474	0.257089052	0.82837765
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.055732474	0.189479937	0.768655584
KCNJ11	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.181727362	0.735437794	0.808416908
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	rs1078523	1.35	1.76875	0.445313788
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	rs11654396	2.125	2.330882353	0.361941448
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	rs11869741	-0.342618384	2.487465181	0.890447516
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	rs12603201	1.291497976	1.129554656	0.252885345
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	rs12941945	2.388646288	1.602620087	0.136102482
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	rs59795094	1.353846154	2.184615385	0.535443259
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	rs9892728	1.440789474	1.868421053	0.4406318
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	rs9905939	0.824675325	1.844155844	0.654742864
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.388038249	0.24182675	9.48E-09
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.388038249	0.616807509	0.024426174
RAMP2	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.915182056	2.321211434	0.707014176
KCNJ8	Esophageal cancer	rs10841887	1.15	0.944117647	0.223197929
KCNJ8	Esophageal cancer	rs117973841	-3.208609272	2.413907285	0.183776023
KCNJ8	Esophageal cancer	rs12816749	-2.165680473	1.928994083	0.261565189
KCNJ8	Esophageal cancer	rs59406438	-1.173361522	1.509513742	0.436975351
KCNJ8	Esophageal cancer	rs74732083	-1.426008969	2.029147982	0.482203814

KCNJ8	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.313627641	0.774797726	0.685634471
KCNJ8	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.313627641	0.667561396	0.638490104
KCNJ8	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.982684344	2.518809862	0.722485191
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs111327339	0.658610272	1.632930514	0.686705291
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs1373641	2.472972973	1.306306306	0.058344114
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs1699348	8.36	2.2	0.000144696
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs2120825	-0.035995501	0.482564679	0.94053928
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs2881654	-0.210822999	0.449830891	0.639304333
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs2920503	1.581395349	1.813953488	0.383320293
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs310752	1.984615385	2.146153846	0.355105755
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs4135247	0.742627346	0.739946381	0.315560273
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs4684833	0.302631579	1.429824561	0.832375073
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	rs76763697	-4.138392857	2.611607143	0.113053747
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.301492819	0.430921774	0.484148229
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.301492819	0.27331074	0.269977796
PPARG	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.798822968	0.52509396	0.166679244
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs11150624	1.62295082	2.262295082	0.473132684
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs11865835	-0.87826087	2.660869565	0.741350577
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs12448775	-2.137820513	2.573717949	0.406179789
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs142133957	2.153344209	2.104404568	0.30618691
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs34497199	-1.186046512	2.139534884	0.579340825
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs4561482	-0.931623932	2.418803419	0.70011961
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs8054784	0.594594595	2.504504505	0.812338677
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs8057029	-0.422413793	2.456896552	0.863492699
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	rs8057326	-0.152380952	2.6	0.953264292
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.037751387	0.479905212	0.937299676
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.037751387	0.796617529	0.962202717
SLC5A2	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.929228033	2.192057859	0.684356174
GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs111917515	-1.815498155	1.974169742	0.357768147
GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs112898001	-2.93625498	2.131474104	0.16833606
GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs112968754	-3.630081301	2.162601626	0.093235599

GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs113126535	-1.924	2.136	0.367721755
GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs1659215	-2.237837838	2.87027027	0.43559043
GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs34359922	-3.43220339	2.122881356	0.1059287
GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs4924660	-3.58045977	2.402298851	0.136111046
GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs73402785	-3.594936709	2.219409283	0.105281293
GANC	Esophageal cancer	rs8037100	-0.435897436	2.692307692	0.871380853
GANC	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.689876544	0.344595452	5.91E-15
GANC	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.689876544	0.752236598	0.000349107
GANC	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.673330943	5.110949572	0.617076052
KCNJ1	Esophageal cancer	rs116842927	-2.673202614	2.31372549	0.247940075
KCNJ1	Esophageal cancer	rs4937311	1.658730159	2.420634921	0.493188763
KCNJ1	Esophageal cancer	rs7110898	0.753191489	3.587234043	0.833695448
KCNJ1	Esophageal cancer	rs7940894	-2.236956522	9.013043478	0.803986608
KCNJ1	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.414035423	1.168638559	0.723122544
KCNJ1	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.414035423	1.494896579	0.781806266
KCNJ1	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.847864768	3.088921215	0.339016132
RAMP3	Esophageal cancer	rs11772021	0.099378882	0.805383023	0.90179565
RAMP3	Esophageal cancer	rs4724382	0.432432432	2.486486486	0.861933802
RAMP3	Esophageal cancer	rs73111954	0.391489362	1.412765957	0.781696846
RAMP3	Esophageal cancer	rs75390434	1.769230769	3.008547009	0.556486529
RAMP3	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.265565345	0.209505325	0.204946979
RAMP3	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.265565345	0.657250341	0.686172209
RAMP3	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.155721302	1.19809951	0.908480489
INSR	Esophageal cancer	rs144057856	4.195338513	1.934517203	0.03010739
INSR	Esophageal cancer	rs4031066	2.082191781	2.191780822	0.342112253
INSR	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.27000403	1.048390973	0.001814233
INSR	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.27000403	1.450379553	0.024159388
ETFDH	Esophageal cancer	Wald_ratio	-1.248571429	2.088571429	0.549965905
GANAB	Esophageal cancer	Wald_ratio	1.379888268	1.865921788	0.459590718
PRKAB1	Esophageal cancer	Wald_ratio	2.814126394	2.163568773	0.193365516
DPP4	Esophageal cancer	rs188581353	4.941176471	2.755944931	0.072986432

DPP4	Esophageal cancer	rs2080714	-0.032467532	1.915584416	0.98647718
DPP4	Esophageal cancer	rs4233648	1.814516129	2.379032258	0.445635253
DPP4	Esophageal cancer	rs75850673	-0.546583851	2.782608696	0.844274735
DPP4	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.255916279	1.129035962	0.265975084
DPP4	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.255916279	1.186768134	0.289934223
DPP4	Esophageal cancer	All - MR Egger	4.857142646	3.239733557	0.272566361
ABCC8	Esophageal cancer	rs2074312	-0.775675676	0.8	0.332248608
ABCC8	Esophageal cancer	rs77023203	-0.971962617	0.682242991	0.15425622
ABCC8	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.889315386	0.09691237	4.45E-20
ABCC8	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.889315386	0.519108855	0.086683512
RAMP1	Esophageal cancer	Wald_ratio	-6.382352941	3.166666667	0.043854393
AMY2A	Esophageal cancer	rs72681706	0.995316159	2.072599532	0.631066709
AMY2A	Esophageal cancer	rs72692396	-1.405189621	1.956087824	0.472530815
AMY2A	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.274302573	1.198246794	0.818931149
AMY2A	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.274302573	1.422569957	0.847098489
AMY2A	Esophageal cancer	rs72681706	0.995316159	2.072599532	0.631066709
AMY2A	Esophageal cancer	rs72692396	-1.405189621	1.956087824	0.472530815
AMY2A	Esophageal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.274302573	1.198246794	0.818931149
AMY2A	Esophageal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.274302573	1.422569957	0.847098489
GLP1R	Eye cancer	rs10305525	9.622974684	11.46208861	0.401161811
GLP1R	Eye cancer	rs11963172	4.421866667	6.725722222	0.510887731
GLP1R	Eye cancer	rs12215108	2.833606218	7.977823834	0.722450733
GLP1R	Eye cancer	rs142878626	10.16460829	8.728778802	0.244223978
GLP1R	Eye cancer	rs228817	13.74914729	8.498604651	0.105703051
GLP1R	Eye cancer	rs28360624	0.753467066	8.487365269	0.929260613
GLP1R	Eye cancer	rs880347	3.585023923	5.090047847	0.48123334
GLP1R	Eye cancer	rs9462535	3.369903226	7.004	0.630417136
GLP1R	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	5.209924899	1.412609407	0.000225884
GLP1R	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	5.209924899	2.623736785	0.047067883
GLP1R	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	3.567669414	11.13649456	0.759559782
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs10766392	1.388507813	2.985520833	0.64187374

KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs10766393	1.378572178	3.010892388	0.647051835
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs10766395	1.230398496	2.697769424	0.6483325
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs147673442	-6.26007772	5.914689119	0.289875373
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs189603359	9.234708171	8.974727626	0.303494679
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs2285676	1.276426829	2.627219512	0.627075618
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs2355016	0.955644444	3.613666667	0.791430993
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs35271178	1.130065116	1.650837209	0.493633853
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs4148631	2.639629371	8.432867133	0.754267873
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs5210	1.27970936	2.652758621	0.629516841
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs5219	0.431951548	1.469111709	0.768740892
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs7110037	0.922447368	3.427026316	0.787800056
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs7112030	1.532320099	2.677741935	0.567157102
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs739688	5.457664671	6.49251497	0.400567174
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs77902362	-7.553116883	7.17762987	0.292655735
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	rs79506407	-5.438150852	10.24153285	0.595425755
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.916061088	0.416926527	0.028007857
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.916061088	0.728150519	0.208368049
KCNJ11	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	0.124253256	2.012132668	0.951633251
RAMP2	Eye cancer	rs1078523	2.84694375	6.56375	0.664479157
RAMP2	Eye cancer	rs11654396	-6.301125	8.944852941	0.481157913
RAMP2	Eye cancer	rs11869741	3.345988858	7.167465181	0.640621402
RAMP2	Eye cancer	rs12603201	-0.079349393	4.288906883	0.985239119
RAMP2	Eye cancer	rs12941945	-6.204585153	6.255851528	0.321292633
RAMP2	Eye cancer	rs59795094	1.200407692	8.120384615	0.882479729
RAMP2	Eye cancer	rs9892728	2.873394737	6.916644737	0.677825772
RAMP2	Eye cancer	rs9905939	1.037207792	6.85961039	0.87981396
RAMP2	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.052416694	1.249581765	0.966540638
RAMP2	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.052416694	2.279739057	0.981656328
RAMP2	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.482355491	8.144404694	0.954695906
KCNJ8	Eye cancer	rs10841887	5.655	3.626882353	0.118951332
KCNJ8	Eye cancer	rs117973841	0.11770298	7.992549669	0.988250308

KCNJ8	Eye cancer	rs12816749	-7.79443787	7.249940828	0.282328324
KCNJ8	Eye cancer	rs59406438	10.77295983	5.620676533	0.055280372
KCNJ8	Eye cancer	rs74732083	-12.3343722	6.342488789	0.051808547
KCNJ8	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.900777179	3.950531693	0.630413698
KCNJ8	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.900777179	2.445486796	0.437005845
KCNJ8	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	10.11498504	12.48229866	0.477056184
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs111327339	5.52929003	5.926691843	0.350847277
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs1373641	2.220522523	5.016846847	0.658045552
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs1699348	0.3524392	8.53176	0.96704949
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs2120825	0.316296963	1.923104612	0.869359546
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs2881654	-0.043536415	1.791149944	0.980608205
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs2920503	10.81784884	6.81622093	0.112495825
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs310752	12.20507692	8.151	0.134296561
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs4135247	0.189782842	2.856541555	0.947029136
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs4684833	2.871074561	5.529342105	0.603590997
PPARG	Eye cancer	rs76763697	12.35241071	8.679955357	0.154708296
PPARG	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.173685414	0.94317696	0.213353941
PPARG	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.173685414	1.072644042	0.273867965
PPARG	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.150891865	1.708254351	0.519473853
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs11150624	2.444221311	8.735	0.779616168
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs11865835	-0.915591304	10.09330435	0.927720846
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs12448775	-3.646730769	8.573173077	0.670570361
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs142133957	1.962903752	6.588531811	0.765758621
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs34497199	5.652294574	8.177131783	0.489419802
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs4561482	-12.22384615	9.113846154	0.179842859
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs8054784	-6.019324324	9.689369369	0.53444848
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs8057029	-7.908198276	9.534741379	0.406873131
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	rs8057326	10.1132381	9.980761905	0.310929707
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.791234954	2.219348688	0.72145362
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.791234954	2.908047876	0.785556994
SLC5A2	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	0.747004028	7.029714135	0.918354264

GANC	Eye cancer	rs111917515	2.772409594	7.248376384	0.702100184
GANC	Eye cancer	rs112898001	3.08436255	7.833545817	0.693774682
GANC	Eye cancer	rs112968754	2.756861789	7.960691057	0.729110239
GANC	Eye cancer	rs113126535	2.714004	7.83064	0.72890104
GANC	Eye cancer	rs1659215	2.988978378	10.55108108	0.776957258
GANC	Eye cancer	rs34359922	2.477355932	7.816567797	0.751291757
GANC	Eye cancer	rs4924660	1.904557471	9.011436782	0.832615009
GANC	Eye cancer	rs73402785	1.029620253	8.105443038	0.898918039
GANC	Eye cancer	rs8037100	3.192605128	10.0194359	0.749998604
GANC	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.526550409	0.225267423	3.41E-29
GANC	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.526550409	2.770691218	0.361829515
GANC	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	3.058002382	18.93884037	0.876286963
KCNJ1	Eye cancer	rs116842927	3.57912854	9.001132898	0.690902283
KCNJ1	Eye cancer	rs4937311	10.74785714	9.36515873	0.251116047
KCNJ1	Eye cancer	rs7110898	8.249574468	13.0593617	0.527584145
KCNJ1	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	7.264676138	2.29419843	0.00154263
KCNJ1	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	7.264676138	5.811619894	0.211290039
KCNJ1	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	1.442748223	12.25022512	0.925367051
RAMP3	Eye cancer	rs11772021	-1.359641822	2.988861284	0.649179059
RAMP3	Eye cancer	rs4724382	-19.23981982	9.619279279	0.045486107
RAMP3	Eye cancer	rs73111954	2.892885106	5.298510638	0.585079131
RAMP3	Eye cancer	rs75390434	-9.133846154	11.24264957	0.41654594
RAMP3	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.980687211	3.007912791	0.510221886
RAMP3	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.980687211	2.452339746	0.419279177
RAMP3	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	3.49435649	4.896850716	0.549513835
ETFDH	Eye cancer	Wald_ratio	-0.123942143	7.134514286	0.986139694
GANAB	Eye cancer	Wald_ratio	-2.81650838	7.064357542	0.690119585
PRKAB1	Eye cancer	Wald_ratio	-3.414743494	8.025539033	0.670483425
DPP4	Eye cancer	rs188581353	-12.75081352	7.770951189	0.100832611
DPP4	Eye cancer	rs2080714	8.672077922	7.114415584	0.222865249
DPP4	Eye cancer	rs4233648	3.956072581	8.763145161	0.651669308

DPP4	Eye cancer	rs75850673	11.67285714	10.11248447	0.248376535
DPP4	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.128770426	5.541642894	0.700874188
DPP4	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.128770426	4.112840336	0.604743445
DPP4	Eye cancer	All - MR Egger	-14.90636336	9.30298616	0.250255367
ABCC8	Eye cancer	rs2074312	2.65387027	3.074864865	0.38809064
ABCC8	Eye cancer	rs77023203	0.571619159	2.543364486	0.82217438
ABCC8	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.417505207	1.022655346	0.165715585
ABCC8	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.417505207	1.959816518	0.46950502
INSR	Eye cancer	rs4031066	-11.8669863	7.540753425	0.115553674
RAMP1	Eye cancer	Wald_ratio	1.345098039	10.9504902	0.90223815
AMY2A	Eye cancer	rs72681706	-4.83765808	8.053442623	0.548043533
AMY2A	Eye cancer	rs72692396	-2.292694611	7.196167665	0.750030318
AMY2A	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.422558909	1.264464326	0.006795024
AMY2A	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.422558909	5.366040367	0.523591946
AMY2A	Eye cancer	rs72681706	-4.83765808	8.053442623	0.548043533
AMY2A	Eye cancer	rs72692396	-2.292694611	7.196167665	0.750030318
AMY2A	Eye cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.422558909	1.264464326	0.006795024
AMY2A	Eye cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.422558909	5.366040367	0.523591946
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	rs10305525	-1.170886076	1.164556962	0.314687538
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	rs11963172	-3.744444444	2.933333333	0.201773474
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	rs12215108	-4.886010363	3.393782383	0.149953806
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	rs142878626	2.668202765	1.48156682	0.071713421
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	rs228817	1.565891473	1.418604651	0.269668999
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	rs28360624	-11.22155689	3.706586826	0.002466154
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	rs880347	-0.411483254	0.889952153	0.64381917
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	rs9462535	-0.95483871	1.04516129	0.36093745
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.468060578	0.798213494	0.557616688
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.468060578	0.491252635	0.340696502
GLP1R	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	1.641283895	3.216367188	0.628071012
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs10766392	-0.526041667	0.4140625	0.203927853
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs10766393	-0.527559055	0.417322835	0.206175855

KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs10766395	-0.456140351	0.393483709	0.246360136
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs147673442	-1.028497409	1.126943005	0.361429974
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs189603359	1.988326848	3.387159533	0.557190977
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs2285676	-0.42195122	0.382926829	0.270500441
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs2355016	-0.036111111	0.655555556	0.956070949
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs35271178	-0.364341085	0.249612403	0.144392524
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs4148631	1.083916084	1.48951049	0.466797538
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs5210	-0.416256158	0.386699507	0.281733596
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs5219	-0.255720054	0.218034993	0.240860172
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs7110037	-0.407894737	0.584210526	0.485053253
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs7112030	-0.751861042	0.392059553	0.055146332
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs739688	-1.479041916	0.97005988	0.127336098
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs77902362	-1.402597403	3.402597403	0.680182767
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	rs79506407	0.459854015	0.661800487	0.487147467
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.38631447	0.071780107	7.37E-08
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.38631447	0.108372507	0.000364285
KCNJ11	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.192020189	0.311348105	0.54730662
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	rs1078523	0.5125	1.0125	0.61273532
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	rs11654396	-2.948529412	1.522058824	0.052721136
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	rs11869741	-3.228412256	2.640668524	0.221490699
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	rs12603201	-0.149797571	0.643724696	0.81599095
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	rs12941945	2.615720524	2.541484716	0.303381182
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	rs59795094	0.692307692	1.246153846	0.578514722
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	rs9892728	0.578947368	1.065789474	0.586985307
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	rs9905939	-0.090909091	1.032467532	0.929836686
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.048947586	0.395691169	0.901551635
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.048947586	0.389811423	0.900074413
RAMP2	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.393892818	1.733578418	0.827801586
KCNJ8	Gastric cancer	rs10841887	-0.632352941	0.652941176	0.332810459
KCNJ8	Gastric cancer	rs117973841	3.443708609	3.427152318	0.314978274
KCNJ8	Gastric cancer	rs12816749	0.213017751	1.550295858	0.890711011

KCNJ8	Gastric cancer	rs59406438	1.627906977	2.501057082	0.515119063
KCNJ8	Gastric cancer	rs74732083	1.522421525	2.753363229	0.580310251
KCNJ8	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.204024459	0.452030244	0.651736344
KCNJ8	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.204024459	0.564460626	0.717762857
KCNJ8	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.417772099	1.833654589	0.834419126
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs111327339	3.258308157	2.833836858	0.250231701
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs1373641	0.418918919	0.855855856	0.624506381
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs1699348	0.624	1.592	0.695087918
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs2120825	-0.570303712	0.475815523	0.230690692
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs2881654	-0.128523112	0.435174746	0.767736617
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs2920503	0.994186047	0.930232558	0.285182335
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs310752	0.853846154	1.261538462	0.498514286
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs4135247	-0.053619303	0.420911528	0.89863289
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs4684833	-0.157894737	0.885964912	0.858551914
PPARG	Gastric cancer	rs76763697	0.098214286	1.21875	0.935771136
PPARG	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.034645723	0.160663535	0.829267219
PPARG	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.034645723	0.218439937	0.873979885
PPARG	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.508920662	0.381360624	0.21877706
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs11150624	-0.114754098	1.286885246	0.928945238
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs11865835	1.782608696	1.695652174	0.293129068
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs12448775	0.182692308	3.323717949	0.956165353
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs142133957	2.337683524	3.079934747	0.447850022
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs34497199	-0.441860465	1.751937984	0.800876902
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs4561482	0.41025641	1.341880342	0.759808338
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs8054784	-0.234234234	1.414414414	0.868467737
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs8057029	0.379310345	1.362068966	0.780643139
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	rs8057326	1.266666667	4.238095238	0.765034351
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.337924283	0.25983901	0.193424845
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.337924283	0.565840242	0.550368562
SLC5A2	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	1.515182197	3.016036231	0.630818734
GANC	Gastric cancer	rs111917515	-0.398523985	2.852398524	0.888884863

GANC	Gastric cancer	rs112898001	-0.358565737	3.083665339	0.907431373
GANC	Gastric cancer	rs112968754	-0.426829268	3.18699187	0.893459057
GANC	Gastric cancer	rs113126535	-0.48	3.092	0.876632645
GANC	Gastric cancer	rs1659215	0.416216216	1.632432432	0.798748674
GANC	Gastric cancer	rs34359922	0.186440678	3.173728814	0.953155222
GANC	Gastric cancer	rs4924660	1.362068966	1.33908046	0.30907381
GANC	Gastric cancer	rs73402785	-1.219409283	3.270042194	0.709220471
GANC	Gastric cancer	rs8037100	0.358974359	1.548717949	0.816702616
GANC	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.400757086	0.258353611	0.120854723
GANC	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.400757086	0.711787325	0.573414965
GANC	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.14871785	5.043498796	0.437862406
KCNJ1	Gastric cancer	rs116842927	-0.183006536	3.725490196	0.960821428
KCNJ1	Gastric cancer	rs4937311	-0.222222222	1.341269841	0.868408414
KCNJ1	Gastric cancer	rs7110898	-1.14893617	0.906382979	0.204938819
KCNJ1	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.832040607	0.312031945	0.007664018
KCNJ1	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.832040607	0.736179531	0.258385951
KCNJ1	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.863549406	2.297354346	0.566133388
RAMP3	Gastric cancer	rs11772021	-0.84679089	0.973084886	0.384184141
RAMP3	Gastric cancer	rs4724382	-2.27027027	1.774774775	0.200830925
RAMP3	Gastric cancer	rs73111954	-1.523404255	0.846808511	0.072019476
RAMP3	Gastric cancer	rs75390434	-0.547008547	1.52991453	0.720686165
RAMP3	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.243434385	0.292013537	2.06E-05
RAMP3	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.243434385	0.559425222	0.026236043
RAMP3	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.967973076	1.172503117	0.495854125
INSR	Gastric cancer	rs144057856	14.48612653	6.15982242	0.018687252
INSR	Gastric cancer	rs4031066	-2.294520548	1.650684932	0.164516278
INSR	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.170220019	4.195526034	0.780305507
INSR	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.170220019	1.594428497	0.462983331
ETFDH	Gastric cancer	Wald_ratio	2.38	3.207142857	0.458030663
GANAB	Gastric cancer	Wald_ratio	-0.709497207	1.430167598	0.619828269
PRKAB1	Gastric cancer	Wald_ratio	-5.442379182	3.464684015	0.116225522

DPP4	Gastric cancer	rs188581353	5.801001252	2.591989987	0.025217844
DPP4	Gastric cancer	rs2080714	0.707792208	3.123376623	0.820726062
DPP4	Gastric cancer	rs4233648	-0.322580645	1.419354839	0.820211679
DPP4	Gastric cancer	rs75850673	1.900621118	1.155279503	0.099936554
DPP4	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.469564897	1.010472547	0.145853642
DPP4	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.469564897	0.81731869	0.072171988
DPP4	Gastric cancer	All - MR Egger	7.255209045	2.866508813	0.127029574
ABCC8	Gastric cancer	rs2074312	-0.456756757	0.427027027	0.284790275
ABCC8	Gastric cancer	rs77023203	-0.647196262	0.369158879	0.079573765
ABCC8	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.565745242	0.094219018	1.92E-09
ABCC8	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.565745242	0.279270527	0.042785648
RAMP1	Gastric cancer	Wald_ratio	-3.303921569	1.715686275	0.054140059
AMY2A	Gastric cancer	rs72681706	-2.557377049	3.142857143	0.4158106
AMY2A	Gastric cancer	rs72692396	-2.890219561	2.902195609	0.319311636
AMY2A	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.737028236	0.165894555	3.75E-61
AMY2A	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.737028236	2.132172468	0.199253767
AMY2A	Gastric cancer	rs72681706	-2.557377049	3.142857143	0.4158106
AMY2A	Gastric cancer	rs72692396	-2.890219561	2.902195609	0.319311636
AMY2A	Gastric cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.737028236	0.165894555	3.75E-61
AMY2A	Gastric cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.737028236	2.132172468	0.199253767
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10305525	7.927341772	10.56487342	0.453044563
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11963172	1.194044444	6.214944444	0.847644514
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12215108	11.35901554	7.368134715	0.123160956
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs142878626	3.447073733	8.128801843	0.671524387
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs228817	0.348276744	7.842635659	0.964579085
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs28360624	-0.924023952	7.824251497	0.905990464
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs880347	-4.579564593	4.69130622	0.328974714
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs9462535	-2.315696774	6.457806452	0.71990276
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.52984588	1.877743446	0.777811931
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.52984588	2.422424063	0.826863895
GLP1R	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	1.750782647	10.32962312	0.870980202

KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766392	1.220268229	2.756614583	0.658005061
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766393	1.209112861	2.78	0.66361129
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766395	0.811576441	2.489503759	0.744424897
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs147673442	-7.709170984	5.423419689	0.155183244
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs189603359	1.933046693	8.351108949	0.816948247
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2285676	1.031658537	2.424143902	0.670416509
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2355016	1.193397222	3.334361111	0.720411556
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs35271178	1.122275969	1.523066667	0.461211858
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4148631	1.28758042	7.792517483	0.868760655
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs5210	1.031039409	2.447724138	0.673591742
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs5219	0.020239704	1.355652759	0.988088139
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs7110037	1.136960526	3.161736842	0.719146294
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs7112030	1.184258065	2.470024814	0.631617186
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs739688	-0.869137725	5.996766467	0.884762669
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs77902362	1.143512987	6.672597403	0.863929311
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs79506407	13.99145985	9.333309002	0.133850573
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.746963173	0.389609191	0.055211083
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.746963173	0.671902135	0.266261034
KCNJ11	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.506557862	1.857662576	0.789075732
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs1078523	-3.5657125	6.0550125	0.555937705
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11654396	6.560573529	8.248088235	0.426377747
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11869741	-1.530657382	6.623175487	0.817232244
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12603201	2.958295547	3.958744939	0.454893857
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12941945	-1.956532751	5.757510917	0.733990072
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs59795094	-5.1366	7.4922	0.492969786
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs9892728	-3.340151316	6.380578947	0.600635266
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs9905939	-2.661857143	6.323590909	0.673798343
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.646027268	1.265155873	0.609609764
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.646027268	2.102898732	0.758685073
RAMP2	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	3.248834574	7.516940815	0.680695823
KCNJ8	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs10841887	3.867382353	3.339617647	0.246851192

KCNJ8	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs117973841	-6.094238411	7.364966887	0.407974622
KCNJ8	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12816749	4.953976331	6.684201183	0.458604253
KCNJ8	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs59406438	-3.806723044	5.230295983	0.466722724
KCNJ8	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs74732083	-4.149596413	5.920403587	0.483366949
KCNJ8	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.448666834	2.132287196	0.833343192
KCNJ8	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.448666834	2.261285523	0.842722504
KCNJ8	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-5.6966687	6.681079711	0.456513175
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs111327339	-1.544274924	5.49641994	0.778740971
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs1373641	2.386351351	4.622792793	0.605704803
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs1699348	5.773144	7.869208	0.463169861
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2120825	-3.959730034	1.782069741	0.026284403
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2881654	-3.570563698	1.660090192	0.031490005
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2920503	5.727936047	6.282848837	0.361938166
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs310752	9.274076923	7.520923077	0.217537134
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4135247	-0.871144772	2.636321716	0.741067916
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4684833	6.320964912	5.116710526	0.216697614
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs76763697	-1.213660714	7.985758929	0.879204184
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.954115146	1.076569717	0.069503769
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.954115146	0.992800777	0.049035224
PPARG	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-5.74307405	1.58146796	0.006670692
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11150624	-9.459754098	8.062237705	0.240659084
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11865835	-8.24786087	9.31426087	0.375882223
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs12448775	2.069397436	7.950865385	0.794653019
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs142133957	-0.43008646	6.135513866	0.944115761
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs34497199	-12.18751938	7.550465116	0.106496729
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4561482	-16.62196581	8.409794872	0.048098092
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8054784	-4.686333333	8.941603604	0.600205964
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057029	-15.58258621	8.795948276	0.076466943
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057326	-13.39457143	9.20827619	0.145773627
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-7.858783503	2.278382711	0.00056208
SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-7.858783503	2.689954011	0.003483158

SLC5A2	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	3.892040781	6.537390058	0.570347035
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs111917515	-15.93402214	6.664280443	0.016804424
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs112898001	-17.1461753	7.204422311	0.017314919
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs112968754	-15.16922764	7.29902439	0.037685958
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs113126535	-17.40696	7.20268	0.015660467
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs1659215	-20.35713514	9.678756757	0.035441304
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs34359922	-7.629237288	7.186144068	0.288390344
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4924660	-10.97724138	8.287873563	0.185338931
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs73402785	-14.44886076	7.447763713	0.05237644
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs8037100	-19.26010256	9.188205128	0.036066509
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-15.05422801	1.283837408	9.38E-32
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-15.05422801	2.545761333	3.35E-09
GANC	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-15.80744032	17.40380226	0.393927301
KCNJ1	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs116842927	-2.615076253	8.213856209	0.750201443
KCNJ1	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4937311	-0.030666349	8.635079365	0.997166424
KCNJ1	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs7110898	4.822382979	12.16961702	0.691910169
KCNJ1	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.188938485	1.917060152	0.921490515
KCNJ1	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.188938485	5.346342335	0.971808815
KCNJ1	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-1.863611712	11.21420605	0.895162628
RAMP3	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs11772021	2.346231884	2.756853002	0.394739133
RAMP3	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4724382	5.413603604	8.865207207	0.541426472
RAMP3	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs73111954	-0.550621277	4.896510638	0.910465211
RAMP3	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs75390434	-6.07942735	10.37504274	0.557898036
RAMP3	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.526610615	1.305169602	0.24213599
RAMP3	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.526610615	2.262828205	0.499899965
RAMP3	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	2.630323201	4.135233838	0.58980697
ETFDH	Hodgkin lymphoma	Wald_ratio	6.950585714	6.620914286	0.293813555
GANAB	Hodgkin lymphoma	Wald_ratio	-6.890614525	6.528379888	0.291203043
PRKAB1	Hodgkin lymphoma	Wald_ratio	2.811877323	7.392416357	0.70366838
DPP4	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs188581353	-0.235966208	7.227897372	0.973956416
DPP4	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2080714	0.198159091	6.573701299	0.975952035

DPP4	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4233648	-0.601798387	8.086612903	0.940676918
DPP4	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs75850673	6.870869565	9.297453416	0.459903634
DPP4	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.01747051	1.524464097	0.504498582
DPP4	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.01747051	3.8030005	0.789050231
DPP4	Hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.252304087	8.648814379	0.979376597
ABCC8	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs2074312	0.551921622	2.838351351	0.845822384
ABCC8	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs77023203	1.07289486	2.346518692	0.647506926
ABCC8	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.861386628	0.255840568	0.000760215
ABCC8	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.861386628	1.808514871	0.633864212
INSR	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs4031066	-5.864972603	6.959657534	0.399390685
RAMP1	Hodgkin lymphoma	Wald_ratio	1.555068627	10.11323529	0.877794486
AMY2A	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs72681706	-0.358866511	7.404449649	0.961344597
AMY2A	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs72692396	3.466287425	6.586007984	0.598672249
AMY2A	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.776718743	1.899530985	0.349610007
AMY2A	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.776718743	4.921032701	0.718065125
AMY2A	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs72681706	-0.358866511	7.404449649	0.961344597
AMY2A	Hodgkin lymphoma	rs72692396	3.466287425	6.586007984	0.598672249
AMY2A	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.776718743	1.899530985	0.349610007
AMY2A	Hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.776718743	4.921032701	0.718065125
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	rs10305525	-4.423172624	4.147392342	0.2862
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	rs11963172	-0.027770836	2.332357627	0.9905
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	rs12215108	0.893800695	2.946138804	0.7616
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	rs142878626	-0.623569575	3.253334583	0.848
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	rs228817	-0.716479176	3.141632939	0.8196
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	rs28360624	-0.991741814	3.159459489	0.7536
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	rs880347	0.259073335	1.894005635	0.8912
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	rs9462535	-0.877871187	2.591521252	0.7348
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.415084846	0.424619946	0.328299713
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.415084846	0.961887413	0.666081857
GLP1R	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	0.987727437	4.138589258	0.819309583
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs10766392	-0.135769975	1.115188342	0.9031

KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs10766393	-0.086757402	1.111771713	0.9378
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs10766395	-0.007519925	1.016945323	0.9941
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs147673442	-4.702639291	1.981303126	0.01762
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs189603359	6.000567035	2.841390084	0.0347
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs2285676	0.158023563	0.987795598	0.8729
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs2355016	0.647939592	1.347002749	0.6305
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs35271178	0.239993346	0.615716517	0.6967
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs4148631	-1.130670011	3.115886344	0.7167
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs5210	0.147341667	0.98674155	0.8813
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs5219	-0.364238487	0.548822702	0.5069
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs7110037	0.636965492	1.280929713	0.619
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs7112030	-0.014892806	1.042310129	0.9886
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs739688	3.457188662	2.750024891	0.2087
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs77902362	0.094292635	2.785936137	0.973
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	rs79506407	4.794305406	4.23939674	0.2581
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.033180784	0.265212879	0.900436465
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.033180784	0.272477136	0.903077561
KCNJ11	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.358516112	0.766952485	0.647366925
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	rs1078523	-0.577661335	2.464771473	0.8147
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	rs11654396	-8.168679964	3.421641473	0.01697
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	rs11869741	-0.404030256	6.469077272	0.9502
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	rs12603201	3.52239043	1.586780607	0.02643
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	rs12941945	-4.014885314	2.374878447	0.09092
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	rs59795094	-0.486148365	3.00785089	0.8716
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	rs9892728	-0.860871023	2.584845723	0.7391
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	rs9905939	2.11860408	2.564873582	0.4088
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.019120898	1.275805313	0.988042299
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.019120898	0.890662521	0.982872191
RAMP2	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	5.551717718	5.059154125	0.314559695
KCNJ8	Kidney cancer	rs10841887	-0.369964183	1.34713352	0.7836
KCNJ8	Kidney cancer	rs117973841	-2.796991941	2.852975541	0.3269

KCNJ8	Kidney cancer	rs12816749	-2.360565897	2.724735468	0.3863
KCNJ8	Kidney cancer	rs59406438	1.335154651	2.05314402	0.5155
KCNJ8	Kidney cancer	rs74732083	3.140515446	2.221753941	0.1575
KCNJ8	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.070091876	0.917314527	0.939093024
KCNJ8	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.070091876	0.895000803	0.937577586
KCNJ8	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	3.773882594	2.659839969	0.250994835
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs111327339	-2.213318016	2.243663208	0.3239
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs1373641	-0.229145903	1.860928591	0.902
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs1699348	-2.510997859	3.153619859	0.4259
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs2120825	-0.123282792	0.705090285	0.8612
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs2881654	-0.170390505	0.659742732	0.7962
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs2920503	1.788868237	2.506966586	0.4755
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs310752	2.406483849	3.002201725	0.4228
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs4135247	-0.147860072	1.047994942	0.8878
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs4684833	-1.040198536	2.039311244	0.61
PPARG	Kidney cancer	rs76763697	0.480252529	3.37964935	0.887
PPARG	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.185598323	0.226244397	0.412019805
PPARG	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.185598323	0.395116213	0.638547236
PPARG	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.320250843	0.628937653	0.624360999
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs11150624	0.964670787	3.238529104	0.7658
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs11865835	4.143187258	3.809701268	0.2768
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs12448775	0.497429861	3.187796892	0.876
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs142133957	-0.217145417	2.614168323	0.9338
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs34497199	3.174417545	3.038833771	0.2962
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs4561482	4.996373468	3.367607363	0.1379
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs8054784	4.738058569	3.564740563	0.1838
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs8057029	5.26681891	3.490281998	0.1313
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	rs8057326	0.862747094	3.699476858	0.8156
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.439159169	0.742317307	0.001016674
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.439159169	1.091546145	0.025444214
SLC5A2	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.026893691	2.736100843	0.718541641

GANC	Kidney cancer	rs111917515	-1.344219801	2.740666214	0.6238
GANC	Kidney cancer	rs112898001	-2.065065683	2.974353614	0.4875
GANC	Kidney cancer	rs112968754	-1.765957636	3.015298304	0.5581
GANC	Kidney cancer	rs113126535	-1.244439801	2.953463214	0.6735
GANC	Kidney cancer	rs1659215	-2.054780659	3.979323684	0.6056
GANC	Kidney cancer	rs34359922	-0.614171447	2.932360243	0.8341
GANC	Kidney cancer	rs4924660	1.334949777	3.31310906	0.687
GANC	Kidney cancer	rs73402785	-1.824938481	3.054492492	0.5502
GANC	Kidney cancer	rs8037100	-1.535583404	3.764015613	0.6833
GANC	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.232537864	0.338623164	0.000272796
GANC	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.232537864	1.043076848	0.237349893
GANC	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.788159776	7.080987676	0.520622287
KCNJ1	Kidney cancer	rs116842927	0.8942477	3.376016868	0.7911
KCNJ1	Kidney cancer	rs4937311	1.345669893	3.460795134	0.6974
KCNJ1	Kidney cancer	rs7110898	3.88519823	4.75210103	0.4136
KCNJ1	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.683693447	0.804313003	0.036319606
KCNJ1	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.683693447	2.154085078	0.434433162
KCNJ1	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	1.549265982	4.573135667	0.792054253
RAMP3	Kidney cancer	rs11772021	-1.182186171	1.0961149	0.2808
RAMP3	Kidney cancer	rs4724382	-0.215957171	3.633069089	0.9526
RAMP3	Kidney cancer	rs73111954	-0.767504787	2.040382847	0.7068
RAMP3	Kidney cancer	rs75390434	-0.196807612	4.141706584	0.9621
RAMP3	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.991352797	0.185607789	9.24E-08
RAMP3	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.991352797	0.910379965	0.276178583
RAMP3	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.475159216	1.654335149	0.466646146
INSR	Kidney cancer	rs144057856	1.465558057	2.191720007	0.5037
INSR	Kidney cancer	rs4031066	3.773285364	2.828524797	0.1822
INSR	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.331328097	1.11731974	0.036930079
INSR	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.331328097	1.732483162	0.178413159
ETFDH	Kidney cancer	Wald_ratio	0.589124972	2.888710127	0.8384
GANAB	Kidney cancer	Wald_ratio	3.096910999	2.676263575	0.2472

PRKAB1	Kidney cancer	Wald_ratio	-1.001263987	3.011179439	0.7395
DPP4	Kidney cancer	rs188581353	-5.266750752	3.564261498	0.1395
DPP4	Kidney cancer	rs2080714	-0.469223707	2.647013759	0.8593
DPP4	Kidney cancer	rs4233648	-0.42629068	6.937077639	0.951
DPP4	Kidney cancer	rs75850673	6.994667352	4.02664111	0.08237
DPP4	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.194150445	2.393927074	0.935361443
DPP4	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.194150445	1.814011997	0.914766605
DPP4	Kidney cancer	All - MR Egger	-6.175861021	5.322006327	0.365664395
ABCC8	Kidney cancer	rs2074312	0.167050245	1.145955611	0.8841
ABCC8	Kidney cancer	rs77023203	0.375471499	0.95632236	0.6946
ABCC8	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.289909502	0.102528452	0.004689829
ABCC8	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.289909502	0.734238664	0.69295825
RAMP1	Kidney cancer	Wald_ratio	8.637494924	8.117463009	0.2873
AMY2A	Kidney cancer	rs72681706	-2.336178762	3.036657742	0.4417
AMY2A	Kidney cancer	rs72692396	0.313831546	2.624009037	0.9048
AMY2A	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.819015504	1.3109973	0.532150203
AMY2A	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.819015504	1.985444279	0.679965695
AMY2A	Kidney cancer	rs72681706	-2.336178762	3.036657742	0.4417
AMY2A	Kidney cancer	rs72692396	0.313831546	2.624009037	0.9048
AMY2A	Kidney cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.819015504	1.3109973	0.532150203
AMY2A	Kidney cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.819015504	1.985444279	0.679965695
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	rs10305525	-8.410253165	9.495506329	0.375774485
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	rs11963172	5.823777778	5.554655556	0.294431397
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	rs12215108	1.077621762	6.559585492	0.869509159
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	rs142878626	0.702158986	7.253317972	0.922881085
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	rs228817	10.83131783	7.001914729	0.121885434
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	rs28360624	-2.788904192	7.012035928	0.69082847
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	rs880347	1.791861244	4.200679426	0.669696468
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	rs9462535	-9.204	5.784929032	0.111602655
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.584814821	2.183781604	0.788853938
GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.584814821	2.166567449	0.787216497

GLP1R	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.202990456	10.04131908	0.984526948
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs10766392	-2.71359375	2.464846354	0.270932342
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs10766393	-2.675748031	2.486244094	0.281828443
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs10766395	0.124246366	2.227646617	0.955521274
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs147673442	-1.380339378	4.919818653	0.779042434
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs189603359	3.60770428	7.519513619	0.631384589
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs2285676	0.215536585	2.1694	0.92085793
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs2355016	-0.172037222	2.98725	0.954074817
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs35271178	0.004679039	1.364088372	0.997263135
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs4148631	-2.75548951	6.97634965	0.692860724
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs5210	0.211235714	2.190440887	0.923174897
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs5219	-0.365841184	1.213429341	0.763038127
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs7110037	0.083386579	2.833605263	0.976523455
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs7112030	-0.060232754	2.210813896	0.978264638
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs739688	-2.212077844	5.356760479	0.679642754
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs77902362	-9.85474026	5.911915584	0.095528634
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	rs79506407	1.425708029	8.428296837	0.865672907
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.514045766	0.354199923	0.146699942
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.514045766	0.601531384	0.392793761
KCNJ11	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.740334578	1.662264115	0.662856485
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	rs1078523	5.50034375	5.4202	0.31020779
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	rs11654396	9.479558824	7.400588235	0.200221893
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	rs11869741	-6.627632312	5.927465181	0.263514669
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	rs12603201	-5.054736842	3.54088664	0.153425969
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	rs12941945	-0.185819651	5.181659389	0.971393168
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	rs59795094	6.646576923	6.706292308	0.321638892
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	rs9892728	5.563513158	5.710927632	0.32996355
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	rs9905939	2.037616883	5.66661039	0.719158983
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.508941341	2.007223901	0.799839487
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.508941341	1.883776986	0.787028935
RAMP2	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-16.66221033	6.731296001	0.048108534

KCNJ8	Laryngeal cancer	rs10841887	-0.205171471	3.004970588	0.945564843
KCNJ8	Laryngeal cancer	rs117973841	3.02402649	6.636059603	0.648608526
KCNJ8	Laryngeal cancer	rs12816749	10.14106509	5.970295858	0.089397086
KCNJ8	Laryngeal cancer	rs59406438	7.934862579	4.667357294	0.089116612
KCNJ8	Laryngeal cancer	rs74732083	-4.396255605	5.189304933	0.39689692
KCNJ8	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.173200777	2.382083686	0.361605108
KCNJ8	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.173200777	2.022178088	0.282516597
KCNJ8	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.228702664	7.07843645	0.592322568
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs111327339	-1.424892749	4.866903323	0.769696474
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs1373641	4.141445946	4.141914414	0.317365247
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs1699348	7.626856	7.039248	0.278597215
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs2120825	0.720813273	1.588166479	0.649925953
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs2881654	-0.336084555	1.478534386	0.820183274
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs2920503	8.936104651	5.620575581	0.111859292
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs310752	0.730311538	6.725746154	0.913532084
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs4135247	3.382252011	2.356072386	0.151131362
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs4684833	2.5235	4.565570175	0.580452448
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	rs76763697	-4.276058036	7.187589286	0.551895328
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.108145295	0.735413451	0.131853455
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.108145295	0.885323979	0.210685265
PPARG	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.721998049	1.410005104	0.622446219
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs11150624	3.223147541	7.217844262	0.655198084
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs11865835	-4.287608696	8.320947826	0.606358154
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs12448775	8.121217949	7.162916667	0.256884131
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs142133957	-0.691013051	5.380929853	0.897817481
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs34497199	-3.79296124	6.74727907	0.574016014
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs4561482	4.125811966	7.519820513	0.583239966
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs8054784	8.430936937	7.997117117	0.291769835
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs8057029	8.541310345	7.871525862	0.277882001
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	rs8057326	-1.554371429	8.24467619	0.850460951
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.133584799	1.678465914	0.203674686

SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.133584799	2.398683109	0.373744238
SLC5A2	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	1.572533873	5.774658378	0.793236421
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs111917515	1.486158672	5.968487085	0.803360083
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs112898001	2.724079681	6.448326693	0.672698392
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs112968754	3.478743902	6.554308943	0.595587334
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs113126535	1.354568	6.45036	0.833668593
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs1659215	0.658210811	8.693837838	0.939649788
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs34359922	5.533262712	6.444661017	0.390571792
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs4924660	4.92512069	7.415287356	0.50657208
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs73402785	2.451772152	6.666075949	0.713023553
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	rs8037100	1.660364103	8.253025641	0.840555896
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.76826468	0.543406126	3.50E-07
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.76826468	2.281506061	0.224996151
GANC	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.727856038	15.59275952	0.964072799
KCNJ1	Laryngeal cancer	rs116842927	-5.650174292	7.425250545	0.446692572
KCNJ1	Laryngeal cancer	rs4937311	-12.10412698	7.730246032	0.117392182
KCNJ1	Laryngeal cancer	rs7110898	0.93552766	10.9073617	0.931649018
KCNJ1	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-6.86669818	3.394873514	0.043107505
KCNJ1	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.86669818	4.806943447	0.153149223
KCNJ1	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.793970486	10.11710465	0.95014152
RAMP3	Laryngeal cancer	rs11772021	-0.418134576	2.457453416	0.864892532
RAMP3	Laryngeal cancer	rs4724382	5.831135135	7.924783784	0.461846336
RAMP3	Laryngeal cancer	rs73111954	1.29267234	4.37212766	0.767488162
RAMP3	Laryngeal cancer	rs75390434	-0.927871795	9.246495726	0.92006767
RAMP3	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.327396705	0.933266277	0.725732854
RAMP3	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.327396705	2.018160348	0.871128423
RAMP3	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.47537347	3.687996677	0.727804613
ETFDH	Laryngeal cancer	Wald_ratio	-2.126157143	5.920614286	0.719512125
GANAB	Laryngeal cancer	Wald_ratio	11.41977654	5.809106145	0.04931703
PRKAB1	Laryngeal cancer	Wald_ratio	2.512921933	6.619814126	0.70423782
DPP4	Laryngeal cancer	rs188581353	-3.031727159	6.309499374	0.630870471

DPP4	Laryngeal cancer	rs2080714	-0.200454545	5.861467532	0.972718706
DPP4	Laryngeal cancer	rs4233648	-1.7805	7.235814516	0.805629851
DPP4	Laryngeal cancer	rs75850673	4.990428571	8.32447205	0.548846912
DPP4	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.501178765	1.546864254	0.745940605
DPP4	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.501178765	3.375680862	0.881973864
DPP4	Laryngeal cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.858970393	7.560598954	0.741688737
ABCC8	Laryngeal cancer	rs2074312	-1.3171	2.53937027	0.603989561
ABCC8	Laryngeal cancer	rs77023203	-0.167957009	2.09992757	0.936251344
ABCC8	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.63464753	0.564352814	0.260776336
ABCC8	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.63464753	1.61827932	0.694929445
INSR	Laryngeal cancer	rs4031066	0.57194589	6.22019863	0.926737941
RAMP1	Laryngeal cancer	Wald_ratio	-0.486332353	9.03995098	0.957096009
AMY2A	Laryngeal cancer	rs72681706	-5.146229508	6.605362998	0.435921595
AMY2A	Laryngeal cancer	rs72692396	-8.320598802	5.877924152	0.156902152
AMY2A	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-6.917768222	1.576441779	1.14E-05
AMY2A	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.917768222	4.391072186	0.115160304
AMY2A	Laryngeal cancer	rs72681706	-5.146229508	6.605362998	0.435921595
AMY2A	Laryngeal cancer	rs72692396	-8.320598802	5.877924152	0.156902152
AMY2A	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-6.917768222	1.576441779	1.14E-05
AMY2A	Laryngeal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.917768222	4.391072186	0.115160304
GLP1R	Liver cancer	rs10305525	1.656359437	7.733553131	0.830408
GLP1R	Liver cancer	rs11963172	-2.691198607	4.63939718	0.561864
GLP1R	Liver cancer	rs12215108	2.48143616	5.39764311	0.645713
GLP1R	Liver cancer	rs142878626	3.256100169	6.242371014	0.60194
GLP1R	Liver cancer	rs228817	-1.77766965	5.766356386	0.757867
GLP1R	Liver cancer	rs880347	3.527035303	3.469028419	0.309286
GLP1R	Liver cancer	rs9462535	2.650603877	4.633468798	0.567284
GLP1R	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.535715868	0.987272229	0.11982368
GLP1R	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.535715868	1.880057976	0.414017039
GLP1R	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	6.334090335	7.79543784	0.4534171
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs10766392	-1.427592963	2.068173602	0.490026

KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs10766393	-1.491951817	2.079184437	0.473025
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs10766395	-0.456715511	1.818795394	0.80173
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs147673442	-2.114426235	3.3941704	0.533312
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs2285676	-0.88449816	1.769347716	0.617145
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs2355016	4.707140567	2.440616412	0.053772
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs35271178	0.802437004	1.087624753	0.460643
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs4148631	7.277794173	5.771677213	0.207327
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs5210	-0.881570544	1.786813107	0.621747
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs5219	0.6451232	0.966835507	0.504611
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs7110037	5.462930682	2.328187708	0.0189542
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs7112030	-1.113829277	1.800154329	0.536087
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs739688	4.369314118	4.373112224	0.317731
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs77902362	0.01330896	5.030318069	0.997889
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	rs79506407	-3.030657419	6.580567639	0.645124
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.39003094	0.499429728	0.434830379
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.39003094	0.487493516	0.423667862
KCNJ11	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.537419001	1.401078808	0.707493062
RAMP2	Liver cancer	rs1078523	-1.506692209	4.508629458	0.738244
RAMP2	Liver cancer	rs11654396	8.188416754	5.951811351	0.168888
RAMP2	Liver cancer	rs11869741	3.73670146	4.81655641	0.437865
RAMP2	Liver cancer	rs12603201	1.529447949	2.983879937	0.608252
RAMP2	Liver cancer	rs12941945	6.204788904	4.191307758	0.138768
RAMP2	Liver cancer	rs59795094	-0.128354392	5.566585875	0.981604
RAMP2	Liver cancer	rs9892728	-1.355672756	4.755981055	0.775609
RAMP2	Liver cancer	rs9905939	-1.067888883	4.560715963	0.814869
RAMP2	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.756281117	1.162467401	0.130833853
RAMP2	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.756281117	1.553563052	0.258271539
RAMP2	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	5.410620396	5.542420574	0.366656907
KCNJ8	Liver cancer	rs10841887	-4.858598609	2.378781883	0.0411046
KCNJ8	Liver cancer	rs117973841	-6.115411501	5.503449972	0.266484
KCNJ8	Liver cancer	rs12816749	2.294574415	5.081782336	0.651608

KCNJ8	Liver cancer	rs59406438	-5.213942217	4.461852834	0.242581
KCNJ8	Liver cancer	rs74732083	-0.293890797	5.836014697	0.959837
KCNJ8	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.786605975	1.316605407	0.004027024
KCNJ8	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.786605975	1.745935047	0.030096912
KCNJ8	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	-9.196033798	5.365679145	0.185068127
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs111327339	4.775503404	3.848086035	0.214603
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs1373641	-0.85931864	3.298873864	0.794487
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs1699348	1.535567948	5.582582405	0.783267
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs2120825	-0.028871802	1.33001651	0.982681
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs2881654	-0.250742153	1.245907137	0.840501
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs2920503	1.260651793	4.440273891	0.776477
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs310752	-4.992568284	5.41375575	0.356424
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs4135247	-0.857648147	1.899948723	0.651697
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs4684833	-5.674849328	3.828616998	0.138282
PPARG	Liver cancer	rs76763697	-10.66566768	6.075766578	0.0791834
PPARG	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.487085276	0.678415902	0.472773048
PPARG	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.487085276	0.733590039	0.50670646
PPARG	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	0.45728824	1.169671958	0.7060367
GANC	Liver cancer	rs111917515	-2.822277309	4.807496143	0.557165
GANC	Liver cancer	rs112898001	-1.08852056	5.253358542	0.83585
GANC	Liver cancer	rs112968754	-1.134046459	5.322336926	0.83127
GANC	Liver cancer	rs113126535	-2.970153158	5.22243927	0.56954
GANC	Liver cancer	rs1659215	-4.064512659	6.962682424	0.559384
GANC	Liver cancer	rs34359922	0.649655254	5.224718867	0.901044
GANC	Liver cancer	rs4924660	-7.481830978	6.109586055	0.220724
GANC	Liver cancer	rs73402785	1.013468995	5.451906619	0.852529
GANC	Liver cancer	rs8037100	-3.474691962	6.485303029	0.592111
GANC	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.11473385	0.832419253	0.011070446
GANC	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.11473385	1.847612446	0.252384617
GANC	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	8.142304433	12.64903352	0.540272257
KCNJ1	Liver cancer	rs116842927	2.218954641	4.780450284	0.642524

KCNJ1	Liver cancer	rs4937311	-1.948115906	6.056685866	0.74772
KCNJ1	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.61944181	2.02653436	0.759859279
KCNJ1	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.61944181	3.752437668	0.868883238
RAMP3	Liver cancer	rs11772021	0.611936278	2.182088675	0.779143
RAMP3	Liver cancer	rs4724382	4.241797072	6.596045535	0.520171
RAMP3	Liver cancer	rs73111954	5.540942127	3.824717657	0.147416
RAMP3	Liver cancer	rs75390434	-3.192614234	7.405629236	0.666391
RAMP3	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.710215829	1.386094001	0.217263175
RAMP3	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.710215829	1.768885665	0.333627865
RAMP3	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	0.879478276	3.202860804	0.809394207
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	rs11865835	3.01965473	6.926761077	0.66288
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	rs12448775	12.49672752	7.072035729	0.0772178
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	rs34497199	5.999629099	5.625920302	0.286231
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	rs4561482	11.53720813	6.026084659	0.0555506
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	rs8054784	10.41467415	6.44836993	0.106292
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	rs8057029	12.39034313	6.303315004	0.0493348
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	rs8057326	13.24959029	6.794842379	0.0511823
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	9.771113239	1.423977579	6.80E-12
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	9.771113239	2.419343582	5.37E-05
SLC5A2	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	11.63600366	10.9103213	0.334958249
GANAB	Liver cancer	Wald_ratio	-7.038014297	5.057731253	0.164063
PRKAB1	Liver cancer	Wald_ratio	-3.318896215	6.384772619	0.603193
ABCC8	Liver cancer	rs2074312	-2.368027754	2.098540248	0.259144
ABCC8	Liver cancer	rs77023203	-1.154193979	1.696814153	0.49637
ABCC8	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.634053941	0.593468319	0.005898031
ABCC8	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.634053941	1.31945612	0.215556691
DPP4	Liver cancer	rs2080714	-6.835682566	4.845292395	0.158307
DPP4	Liver cancer	rs4233648	-2.870986694	5.995791853	0.632057
DPP4	Liver cancer	rs75850673	-6.446165992	6.613226133	0.32969
DPP4	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	-5.557860724	1.243378202	7.82E-06
DPP4	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-5.557860724	3.274256136	0.089613079

DPP4	Liver cancer	All - MR Egger	-20.82389541	29.41358606	0.607807828
RAMP1	Liver cancer	Wald_ratio	2.143056917	7.278522973	0.768425
AMY2A	Liver cancer	rs72681706	-0.31821777	4.874840858	0.947953
AMY2A	Liver cancer	rs72692396	0.56963802	5.36085378	0.915377
AMY2A	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.083647644	0.441930678	0.849875134
AMY2A	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.083647644	3.606642213	0.98149659
AMY2A	Liver cancer	rs72681706	-0.31821777	4.874840858	0.947953
AMY2A	Liver cancer	rs72692396	0.56963802	5.36085378	0.915377
AMY2A	Liver cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.083647644	0.441930678	0.849875134
AMY2A	Liver cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.083647644	3.606642213	0.98149659
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10305525	-1.927594937	1.836708861	0.293955822
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12215108	-1.762227979	1.212279793	0.146043949
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs142878626	-1.307327189	1.457764977	0.369824346
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs228817	-0.878682171	1.318682171	0.505197926
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs880347	0.273349282	0.80062201	0.73278656
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs9462535	-0.762774194	1.067870968	0.475045188
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.702641677	0.359881479	0.050887741
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.702641677	0.473539598	0.137859958
GLP1R	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.403260334	1.810234217	0.834629908
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10766392	0.195416667	0.468671875	0.676708849
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10766393	0.191811024	0.47335958	0.685321621
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10766395	0.109223058	0.419223058	0.794449689
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs147673442	-0.021036269	0.825492228	0.979669466
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs189603359	-2.344046693	1.442762646	0.104227942
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2285676	0.146146341	0.406926829	0.719485506
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2355016	-0.146916667	0.561	0.793411229
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs35271178	0.034728682	0.253193798	0.890902389
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4148631	1.793006993	1.314615385	0.172598306
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs5210	0.150837438	0.411009852	0.713624784
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs5219	0.058034993	0.224468371	0.795986949
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs7110037	-0.031710526	0.535131579	0.952747061

KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs7112030	0.113970223	0.415062035	0.783634324
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs739688	0.422275449	1.01497006	0.677375467
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs77902362	-2.591168831	1.311298701	0.048151098
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs79506407	-2.232749392	1.451313869	0.123942738
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.046042319	0.099194134	0.642530449
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.046042319	0.112411018	0.682107454
KCNJ11	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.157244018	0.310759171	0.620730658
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs1078523	-1.5991875	1.0138125	0.114703592
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11654396	-1.675147059	1.37	0.221429773
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11869741	-2.142395543	1.185264624	0.070680447
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12603201	1.061012146	0.66757085	0.111978552
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12941945	-1.852751092	0.965152838	0.05490272
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs59795094	-2.105076923	1.253	0.092951582
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs9892728	-1.700394737	1.07125	0.112444797
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs9905939	-0.850844156	1.074090909	0.428271567
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.902843863	0.484230773	0.062252801
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.902843863	0.35555657	0.011109323
RAMP2	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.97574309	1.72013262	0.591120125
KCNJ8	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs10841887	0.020382353	0.550647059	0.970472825
KCNJ8	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs117973841	0.989701987	1.388410596	0.475950397
KCNJ8	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12816749	1.361952663	1.138343195	0.231527185
KCNJ8	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs59406438	1.248498943	0.947780127	0.187742263
KCNJ8	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs74732083	0.816457399	1.130515695	0.470172087
KCNJ8	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.564508396	0.286670493	0.048931386
KCNJ8	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.564508396	0.392711403	0.150586273
KCNJ8	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.114552385	1.1710505	0.928244337
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs111327339	-0.675861027	0.928217523	0.466535328
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs1373641	-0.591711712	0.762117117	0.437509761
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs1699348	-2.26536	1.30576	0.082758929
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2120825	0.590224972	0.29727784	0.047096416
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2881654	0.429616685	0.27832018	0.122683824

PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2920503	0.52622093	1.040639535	0.613087835
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs310752	1.373769231	1.264769231	0.277398599
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4135247	0.171662198	0.443217158	0.698527123
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs76763697	-0.307455357	1.470267857	0.834358309
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.32099921	0.174860764	0.066395856
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.32099921	0.169526461	0.058290737
PPARG	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.605263358	0.26584494	0.056908006
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11150624	-0.953114754	1.33704918	0.475938931
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11865835	1.332608696	1.598608696	0.404503433
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs12448775	-2.176923077	1.584326923	0.16943034
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs34497199	0.254651163	1.26744186	0.840763138
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4561482	-0.953675214	1.418376068	0.501347415
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8054784	-0.686486486	1.485585586	0.644010871
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8057029	-0.216551724	1.444568966	0.880837593
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8057326	-0.510666667	1.534857143	0.739351062
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.477350339	0.337958855	0.157817194
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.477350339	0.511279515	0.350490298
SLC5A2	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-2.911019898	2.44498561	0.278771243
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs111917515	-0.133616236	1.110848708	0.904258955
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs112898001	-0.034940239	1.199043825	0.976752866
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs112968754	0.17995935	1.208617886	0.881635057
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs113126535	-0.316	1.20248	0.792712264
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs1659215	-0.196	1.61227027	0.90324139
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs34359922	0.481355932	1.186101695	0.68486734
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4924660	-1.998390805	1.365862069	0.143440416
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs73402785	0.426793249	1.230970464	0.728807073
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs8037100	-0.262102564	1.522307692	0.863300345
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.154111235	0.233432845	0.509128595
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.154111235	0.422385138	0.715216279
GANC	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	2.835793026	2.885501272	0.358459088
KCNJ1	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs116842927	-1.983093682	1.322897603	0.133859871

KCNJ1	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4937311	1.84031746	1.40984127	0.191778244
KCNJ1	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs7110898	1.846680851	2.174765957	0.395803373
KCNJ1	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.142437396	1.344043114	0.915600755
KCNJ1	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.142437396	0.88183636	0.871681014
KCNJ1	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	-2.883651171	1.871627363	0.366505519
RAMP3	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs11772021	0.166169772	0.464720497	0.720665673
RAMP3	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4724382	-1.156576577	1.483693694	0.435670418
RAMP3	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs73111954	0.089787234	0.857446809	0.916602245
RAMP3	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.056814493	0.237275224	0.810760125
RAMP3	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.056814493	0.393908721	0.885316772
RAMP3	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.556110254	0.748242539	0.593105107
GANAB	Lung adenocarcinoma	Wald_ratio	0.307094972	1.146927374	0.788888292
PRKAB1	Lung adenocarcinoma	Wald_ratio	-1.059814126	1.252118959	0.397320446
ABCC8	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2074312	0.232621622	0.482648649	0.629828064
ABCC8	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs77023203	0.012242991	0.399906542	0.975576875
ABCC8	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.101951192	0.108269152	0.346374013
ABCC8	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.101951192	0.307937393	0.740585825
DPP4	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs2080714	2.356948052	1.126168831	0.03635893
DPP4	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4233648	0.524919355	1.413467742	0.710362052
DPP4	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs75850673	-0.33826087	1.629813665	0.835583681
DPP4	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.197140722	0.807935205	0.138412517
DPP4	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.197140722	0.774873377	0.122358327
DPP4	Lung adenocarcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.750550039	9.978548023	0.771118914
INSR	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs4031066	-0.493150685	1.249315068	0.69303711
RAMP1	Lung adenocarcinoma	Wald_ratio	0.829411765	1.67254902	0.6199672
AMY2A	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs72681706	1.45824356	1.253442623	0.244670999
AMY2A	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs72692396	1.072894212	1.235948104	0.385353913
AMY2A	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.262860926	0.192655644	5.56E-11
AMY2A	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.262860926	0.880067332	0.151298656
AMY2A	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs72681706	1.45824356	1.253442623	0.244670999
AMY2A	Lung adenocarcinoma	rs72692396	1.072894212	1.235948104	0.385353913

AMY2A	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.262860926	0.192655644	5.56E-11
AMY2A	Lung adenocarcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.262860926	0.880067332	0.151298656
KCNJ11	Melanoma	rs10766395	-0.002071366	0.002557018	0.417899335
KCNJ11	Melanoma	rs2285676	-0.002428566	0.002491415	0.329672447
KCNJ11	Melanoma	rs35271178	-0.00113544	0.001563922	0.467825996
KCNJ11	Melanoma	rs5210	-0.002465345	0.002515813	0.327115889
KCNJ11	Melanoma	rs5219	-7.19E-04	0.001394415	0.606274996
KCNJ11	Melanoma	rs7112030	-0.002312156	0.002537568	0.362205751
KCNJ11	Melanoma	rs739688	0.006696647	0.00611509	0.27347198
KCNJ11	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.001338673	0.000520357	0.010093586
KCNJ11	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.001338673	0.000796254	0.092721356
KCNJ11	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.002060134	0.00222447	0.396883515
RAMP2	Melanoma	rs1078523	0.003246706	0.00622395	0.601915976
RAMP2	Melanoma	rs12603201	-0.001603785	0.00406498	0.693184524
RAMP2	Melanoma	rs59795094	0.003979154	0.007676869	0.604227844
RAMP2	Melanoma	rs9892728	0.003957934	0.00655702	0.546097737
RAMP2	Melanoma	rs9905939	0.005459799	0.006475948	0.399178831
RAMP2	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	0.001838501	0.001449035	0.204520948
RAMP2	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.001838501	0.002578517	0.475841459
RAMP2	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.009476051	0.011070785	0.454946552
SLC5A2	Melanoma	rs11150624	-0.00784473	0.008280738	0.343462143
SLC5A2	Melanoma	rs34497199	8.56E-05	0.00773762	0.991170439
SLC5A2	Melanoma	rs4561482	-0.002983128	0.008631624	0.729639952
SLC5A2	Melanoma	rs8054784	-0.002243559	0.009156306	0.806434148
SLC5A2	Melanoma	rs8057029	0.002257172	0.009010259	0.802191897
SLC5A2	Melanoma	rs8057326	0.002182343	0.009463695	0.817624358
SLC5A2	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.001592677	0.001571864	0.310945107
SLC5A2	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.001592677	0.003532909	0.652125243
SLC5A2	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.018503531	0.053452819	0.746659652
PPARG	Melanoma	rs1373641	-0.006450045	0.00472991	0.172670864
PPARG	Melanoma	rs1699348	0.004834464	0.00805176	0.548224189

PPARG	Melanoma	rs310752	-0.011712462	0.007707154	0.128589659
PPARG	Melanoma	rs4135247	-0.00384882	0.002696247	0.153443487
PPARG	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.004383598	0.001949227	0.02451948
PPARG	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.004383598	0.002159093	0.042326497
PPARG	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.004221649	0.005534744	0.525294958
DPP4	Melanoma	rs2080714	0.004566234	0.006761883	0.499491375
DPP4	Melanoma	rs4233648	-0.001054008	0.008207097	0.897811523
DPP4	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	0.00229372	0.002758216	0.405637283
DPP4	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.00229372	0.005218735	0.660287309
GLP1R	Melanoma	rs228817	-0.004726023	0.00803907	0.556611596
GLP1R	Melanoma	rs880347	-0.008778612	0.004817225	0.0684037
GLP1R	Melanoma	rs9462535	0.011014903	0.006613097	0.095789216
GLP1R	Melanoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.00245059	0.006045185	0.685199026
GLP1R	Melanoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.00245059	0.0035043	0.484358642
GLP1R	Melanoma	All - MR Egger	-0.02348005	0.037331964	0.642578187
INSR	Melanoma	rs4031066	-0.006773918	0.007143699	0.343008925
RAMP1	Melanoma	Wald_ratio	-0.002318804	0.010151078	0.8193125
RAMP3	Melanoma	rs4724382	0.002215694	0.009102342	0.807679923
ABCC8	Melanoma	rs77023203	-0.002736822	0.002406449	0.255418376
ABCC8	Melanoma	rs77023203	-0.002736822	0.002406449	0.255418376
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	rs10305525	-4.708455696	7.020126582	0.502406508
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	rs11963172	-3.608788889	4.125688889	0.38173072
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	rs12215108	-3.470590674	4.91173057	0.479819917
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	rs142878626	3.085322581	5.422488479	0.569365322
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	rs228817	-4.010829457	5.203914729	0.440865134
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	rs28360624	-5.893497006	5.195892216	0.256685155
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	rs880347	-3.231909091	3.123564593	0.300815496
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	rs9462535	4.347425806	4.290864516	0.310973335
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-2.097235452	1.265786852	0.097547168
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.097235452	1.611066799	0.192995653
GLP1R	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	1.235621715	6.879603214	0.863373526

KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs10766392	-0.22086224	1.835768229	0.904237167
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs10766393	-0.246372441	1.851314961	0.894130349
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs10766395	-2.068681704	1.653982456	0.211033834
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs147673442	-4.23746114	3.580906736	0.236671001
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs189603359	-2.669416342	5.500661479	0.627470605
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs2285676	-1.512353659	1.610741463	0.347773005
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs2355016	0.408458333	2.214130556	0.8536385
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs35271178	-0.713367442	1.010787597	0.480341101
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs4148631	5.795664336	5.165748252	0.261887561
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs5210	-1.538179803	1.626413793	0.34427644
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs5219	-1.219590848	0.900815612	0.175776576
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs7110037	-0.165889474	2.098581579	0.936994142
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs7112030	-0.751627792	1.641759305	0.64708284
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs739688	0.64108982	3.976311377	0.871914405
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs77902362	2.675201299	4.447954545	0.547543443
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	rs79506407	-13.70004866	6.099440389	0.0246966
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-0.973408705	0.355653242	0.006200983
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.973408705	0.446328385	0.029188969
KCNJ11	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-2.174137683	1.233000348	0.099654602
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	rs1078523	-0.40931	4.02045625	0.918909986
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	rs11654396	-5.579426471	5.468992647	0.307637071
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	rs11869741	1.251735376	4.399470752	0.776012265
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	rs12603201	-0.684878543	2.629453441	0.794505711
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	rs12941945	-2.437554585	3.81728821	0.523111422
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	rs59795094	-0.588289231	4.975284615	0.905875653
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	rs9892728	-0.397225	4.236690789	0.925301144
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	rs9905939	-0.896538961	4.200863636	0.831001119
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-0.994595433	0.570448448	0.081240635
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.994595433	1.396178866	0.476235912
RAMP2	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	0.952087524	4.991317423	0.855013033
KCNJ8	Multiple myeloma	rs10841887	-3.2735	2.221105882	0.140531307

KCNJ8	Multiple myeloma	rs117973841	-5.21692053	4.871357616	0.284197442
KCNJ8	Multiple myeloma	rs12816749	-7.046449704	4.440846154	0.112572488
KCNJ8	Multiple myeloma	rs59406438	-1.019321353	3.465285412	0.768641599
KCNJ8	Multiple myeloma	rs74732083	-6.830896861	3.928946188	0.082103757
KCNJ8	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-3.985713204	1.034484583	0.000116751
KCNJ8	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.985713204	1.501412407	0.00793925
KCNJ8	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-0.816981383	4.435338589	0.865605589
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs111327339	-0.269170695	3.669909366	0.941531325
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs1373641	-4.529009009	3.073121622	0.140549264
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs1699348	-1.945688	5.2252	0.709620197
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs2120825	-0.955910011	1.185860517	0.4201911
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs2881654	-1.489627959	1.102087937	0.176489979
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs2920503	-4.038959302	4.172360465	0.33303068
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs310752	-6.837176923	4.995515385	0.17110465
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs4135247	-3.377238606	1.750284182	0.053664195
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs4684833	3.043561404	3.387868421	0.368988002
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	rs76763697	-2.835950893	5.312008929	0.593427743
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-1.706381276	0.526299381	0.001186001
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.706381276	0.659712258	0.009694102
PPARG	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-0.836558236	1.050975378	0.44901451
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs11150624	2.70657377	5.350385246	0.612951275
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs11865835	-4.649121739	6.20526087	0.453723044
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs12448775	-2.195557692	5.276955128	0.677362252
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs142133957	0.025228874	4.113230016	0.995106132
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs34497199	-4.90579845	5.010875969	0.327565102
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs4561482	4.547726496	5.580991453	0.415152472
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs8054784	1.640063063	5.93109009	0.782148955
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs8057029	3.440862069	5.837534483	0.555567788
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	rs8057326	0.197952381	6.114114286	0.974171965
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-9.79E-05	1.102548938	0.999929133
SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-9.79E-05	1.78921021	0.99995633

SLC5A2	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	-1.317326223	4.370224995	0.771842524
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs111917515	-4.092767528	4.442656827	0.356923453
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs112898001	-4.249083665	4.808207171	0.376850208
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs112968754	-3.7555	4.874878049	0.441075554
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs113126535	-4.15156	4.80152	0.387239413
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs1659215	-5.539945946	6.465675676	0.391542173
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs34359922	-2.754004237	4.779364407	0.564460991
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs4924660	-7.497643678	5.507649425	0.173414285
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs73402785	-1.499261603	4.970632911	0.762938799
GANC	Multiple myeloma	rs8037100	-4.931082051	6.138974359	0.421834873
GANC	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-4.09463422	0.539341364	3.15E-14
GANC	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-4.09463422	1.697479897	0.015857267
GANC	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	2.887939848	11.59582988	0.810471714
KCNJ1	Multiple myeloma	rs116842927	3.172723312	5.44496732	0.560102587
KCNJ1	Multiple myeloma	rs4937311	0.602930159	5.729325397	0.916188702
KCNJ1	Multiple myeloma	rs7110898	-6.013659574	8.019489362	0.453326614
KCNJ1	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	0.399720201	2.375765405	0.866387378
KCNJ1	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.399720201	3.541225711	0.910128683
KCNJ1	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	1.929529362	7.431105475	0.838269553
RAMP3	Multiple myeloma	rs11772021	0.905608696	1.831602484	0.620998877
RAMP3	Multiple myeloma	rs4724382	-2.238675676	5.889738739	0.703872953
RAMP3	Multiple myeloma	rs73111954	4.035029787	3.250178723	0.21442872
RAMP3	Multiple myeloma	rs75390434	-3.650820513	6.910076923	0.597268347
RAMP3	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	1.15458774	1.104475986	0.295851295
RAMP3	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.15458774	1.503261958	0.442454559
RAMP3	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	2.334195976	2.748063921	0.485117237
ETFDH	Multiple myeloma	Wald_ratio	6.683528571	4.344471429	0.123951195
GANAB	Multiple myeloma	Wald_ratio	-1.730402235	4.337044693	0.689906558
PRKAB1	Multiple myeloma	Wald_ratio	-4.847843866	4.914423792	0.32391129
DPP4	Multiple myeloma	rs188581353	6.396057572	4.888498123	0.190741374
DPP4	Multiple myeloma	rs2080714	-5.014824675	4.381227273	0.252368087

DPP4	Multiple myeloma	rs4233648	-1.103112903	5.366104839	0.837126416
DPP4	Multiple myeloma	rs75850673	-4.039819876	6.193149068	0.514204667
DPP4	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-0.886920866	2.693549834	0.741947209
DPP4	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.886920866	2.542116431	0.727171342
DPP4	Multiple myeloma	All - MR Egger	7.27190455	5.843073216	0.339364243
ABCC8	Multiple myeloma	rs2074312	-0.884410811	1.889562162	0.639748364
ABCC8	Multiple myeloma	rs77023203	-0.990794393	1.560151869	0.525387467
ABCC8	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-0.947669291	0.052230531	1.43E-73
ABCC8	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.947669291	1.203064598	0.430864762
INSR	Multiple myeloma	rs4031066	-4.833965753	4.623554795	0.295788023
RAMP1	Multiple myeloma	Wald_ratio	1.37595098	6.709382353	0.837510688
AMY2A	Multiple myeloma	rs72681706	-1.544510539	4.90058548	0.752633665
AMY2A	Multiple myeloma	rs72692396	-2.322754491	4.36750499	0.594846231
AMY2A	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-1.978247821	0.3865558	3.09E-07
AMY2A	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.978247821	3.260535322	0.544033525
AMY2A	Multiple myeloma	rs72681706	-1.544510539	4.90058548	0.752633665
AMY2A	Multiple myeloma	rs72692396	-2.322754491	4.36750499	0.594846231
AMY2A	Multiple myeloma	IVW(random effects)	-1.978247821	0.3865558	3.09E-07
AMY2A	Multiple myeloma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.978247821	3.260535322	0.544033525
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10305525	-3.330968354	4.159227848	0.423211427
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11963172	2.940994444	2.443844444	0.228810166
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12215108	3.894678756	2.906668394	0.18027408
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs142878626	1.32837788	3.204124424	0.678446655
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs228817	-3.896937984	3.08520155	0.206550926
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs28360624	5.92802994	3.078041916	0.054115684
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs880347	-0.537947368	1.848956938	0.771092312
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs9462535	3.926258065	2.541574194	0.122391387
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.416818004	1.118663403	0.205324277
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.416818004	0.953922653	0.137476395
GLP1R	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	2.928355491	5.115560157	0.587815288
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766392	0.525895833	1.086692708	0.628427299

KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766393	0.50671916	1.095939633	0.643822844
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10766395	1.26383208	0.980072682	0.197214264
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs147673442	1.302896373	2.131678756	0.541062738
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs189603359	2.095992218	3.264241245	0.520803698
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2285676	1.181209756	0.954382927	0.215838976
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2355016	-2.502752778	1.311363889	0.056325166
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs35271178	-0.224310078	0.599244961	0.708165381
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4148631	-2.936846154	3.062951049	0.33764492
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs5210	1.210369458	0.963665025	0.209113642
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs5219	-0.021950606	0.533693136	0.967192547
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs7110037	-2.319971053	1.243184211	0.062020063
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs7112030	1.121342432	0.972615385	0.248945458
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs739688	-1.646095808	2.358065868	0.485133215
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs77902362	-5.021233766	2.629581169	0.056195244
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs79506407	1.855647202	3.652262774	0.611396178
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.111751434	0.303357423	0.712588367
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.111751434	0.264475925	0.672631525
KCNJ11	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.645034968	0.85412866	0.462647738
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs1078523	1.0955	2.382825	0.645696819
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11654396	-2.72475	3.242779412	0.400767434
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11869741	-1.256746518	2.605027855	0.629499715
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12603201	-2.00811336	1.558149798	0.197474343
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12941945	0.140634934	2.264899563	0.950488587
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs59795094	1.6108	2.9485	0.584851706
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs9892728	1.483519737	2.510927632	0.554637437
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs9905939	0.789883117	2.489409091	0.751017924
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.344441724	0.575845838	0.549740388
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.344441724	0.827489713	0.677227844
RAMP2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-3.417041921	2.957501879	0.291862752
KCNJ8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs10841887	-0.188480294	1.316	0.88611477
KCNJ8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs117973841	-2.112125828	2.890135762	0.464898235

KCNJ8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12816749	7.587455621	2.63464497	0.003978293
KCNJ8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs59406438	-2.670887949	2.052987315	0.193266549
KCNJ8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs74732083	-3.977668161	2.326098655	0.087262736
KCNJ8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.504604873	1.61277243	0.754371534
KCNJ8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.504604873	0.889714285	0.570609667
KCNJ8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-9.056106089	2.629302995	0.041106966
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs111327339	2.534335347	2.167900302	0.2423925
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs1373641	-0.552441441	1.820648649	0.76156134
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs1699348	1.610264	3.096184	0.603007677
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2120825	0.02925928	0.701355456	0.966723353
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2881654	-0.04119549	0.652613303	0.949667851
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2920503	0.192024419	2.47280814	0.938102972
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs310752	-0.243783077	2.959607692	0.93435244
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4135247	-0.889254692	1.037536193	0.391398984
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4684833	-1.646412281	2.009	0.412490761
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs76763697	-0.665866071	3.144388393	0.832291699
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.121194832	0.229318888	0.597152951
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.121194832	0.39057689	0.756335122
PPARG	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.035666425	0.62213595	0.955689177
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11150624	-5.591942623	3.170032787	0.077731725
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11865835	-4.401313043	3.670886957	0.230536464
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs12448775	-2.655705128	3.117355769	0.3942643
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs142133957	1.260451876	2.420375204	0.602528996
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs34497199	-4.493883721	2.969643411	0.130210112
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4561482	-5.477794872	3.308205128	0.097758114
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8054784	-5.12327027	3.515162162	0.144984578
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057029	-6.665784483	3.459508621	0.054004442
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8057326	-4.291171429	3.623180952	0.236268312
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-3.640172235	0.915632618	7.02E-05
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.640172235	1.058363087	0.000582927
SLC5A2	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	1.618465022	2.574800895	0.549577141

GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs111917515	-0.260556827	2.628568266	0.921039024
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs112898001	-0.725087649	2.842904382	0.798683154
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs112968754	0.383386585	2.885471545	0.894297843
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs113126535	-0.553208	2.840544	0.845585344
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs1659215	0.486261622	3.825583784	0.898855061
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs34359922	3.001029661	2.831838983	0.28926023
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4924660	-0.429011494	3.264126437	0.895433375
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs73402785	2.284177215	2.940097046	0.437214596
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs8037100	-0.469195897	3.632312821	0.897220944
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	0.450037385	0.463986228	0.332077923
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.450037385	1.004598087	0.654169402
GANC	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	1.1216143	6.864974373	0.874834536
KCNJ1	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs116842927	1.951864924	3.210827887	0.543253252
KCNJ1	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4937311	1.682555556	3.396190476	0.62030059
KCNJ1	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs7110898	17.06914894	4.817531915	0.000395406
KCNJ1	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	4.721072882	4.229570546	0.26433388
KCNJ1	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	4.721072882	2.099869643	0.02455901
KCNJ1	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	6.004829282	12.42444112	0.713390661
RAMP3	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs11772021	-1.467498965	1.085190476	0.176280577
RAMP3	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4724382	-0.078441081	3.490036036	0.982068478
RAMP3	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs73111954	-2.813029787	1.926561702	0.144254456
RAMP3	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs75390434	-1.361461538	4.08917094	0.739177181
RAMP3	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.65959531	0.398447966	3.11E-05
RAMP3	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.65959531	0.89070006	0.06242735
RAMP3	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	-1.849549378	1.628015309	0.373724614
ETFDH	Non hodgkin lymphoma	Wald_ratio	1.749728571	2.579914286	0.497637348
GANAB	Non hodgkin lymphoma	Wald_ratio	-0.803094972	2.568899441	0.754567717
PRKAB1	Non hodgkin lymphoma	Wald_ratio	-2.381951673	2.912899628	0.41351407
DPP4	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs188581353	0.632529412	2.882215269	0.826292155
DPP4	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2080714	0.452890909	2.592928571	0.861343768
DPP4	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4233648	3.507072581	3.183177419	0.270569436

DPP4	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs75850673	4.196590062	3.669434783	0.252764184
DPP4	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.812577567	0.930418245	0.051399169
DPP4	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.812577567	1.504015976	0.228142138
DPP4	Non hodgkin lymphoma	All - MR Egger	0.098305598	3.446246952	0.979833593
ABCC8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs2074312	0.671164865	1.118702703	0.548540048
ABCC8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs77023203	1.330383178	0.924168224	0.149995731
ABCC8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	1.062984635	0.323685087	0.001023418
ABCC8	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.062984635	0.712491313	0.135718428
INSR	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs4031066	-1.763890411	2.739712329	0.519690075
RAMP1	Non hodgkin lymphoma	Wald_ratio	-0.217138235	3.977127451	0.956459728
AMY2A	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs72681706	2.960913349	2.904028103	0.307923712
AMY2A	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs72692396	1.252596806	2.58738523	0.628302938
AMY2A	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	2.008577488	0.848497209	0.017922394
AMY2A	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.008577488	1.93184372	0.298469781
AMY2A	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs72681706	2.960913349	2.904028103	0.307923712
AMY2A	Non hodgkin lymphoma	rs72692396	1.252596806	2.58738523	0.628302938
AMY2A	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(random effects)	2.008577488	0.848497209	0.017922394
AMY2A	Non hodgkin lymphoma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.008577488	1.93184372	0.298469781
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	rs10305525	-3.481012658	5.886075949	0.554253881
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	rs11963172	-2.277777778	3.555555556	0.521766353
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	rs12215108	2.797927461	4.300518135	0.515303174
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	rs142878626	-0.023041475	5.138248848	0.996422054
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	rs228817	-6.124031008	4.263565891	0.150898895
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	rs28360624	0.119760479	4.311377246	0.97783939
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	rs880347	0.813397129	2.631578947	0.757252374
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	rs9462535	-5.935483871	3.483870968	0.088436456
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.554137644	1.149369466	0.176322404
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.554137644	1.366518357	0.255414021
GLP1R	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	7.656233304	6.14250326	0.259060077
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs10766392	-4.296875	1.536458333	0.00516418
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs10766393	-4.278215223	1.54855643	0.005732335

KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs10766395	-2.255639098	1.353383459	0.095580705
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs147673442	0.259067358	2.720207254	0.924125712
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs189603359	9.416342412	4.221789883	0.025719921
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs2285676	-2.195121951	1.317073171	0.095580705
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs2355016	2.805555556	1.833333333	0.125941739
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs35271178	-0.341085271	0.821705426	0.678072843
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs4148631	5.244755245	4.265734266	0.218881327
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs5210	-2.216748768	1.330049261	0.095580705
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs5219	-0.336473755	0.740242261	0.649436284
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs7110037	2.578947368	1.763157895	0.143553163
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs7112030	-2.05955335	1.339950372	0.12428424
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs739688	7.964071856	3.293413174	0.015598281
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs77902362	2.467532468	3.993506494	0.53665037
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	rs79506407	4.087591241	5.206812652	0.432426171
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.814252375	0.59393311	0.17039066
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.814252375	0.366409376	0.026266574
KCNJ11	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.939099312	1.670765463	0.265211219
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	rs1078523	0.8125	3.3125	0.806237299
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	rs11654396	-2.720588235	4.485294118	0.544144694
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	rs11869741	-1.253481894	4.317548747	0.771569466
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	rs12603201	2.834008097	2.186234818	0.194873424
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	rs59795094	-0.923076923	4.153846154	0.824140896
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	rs9892728	0.592105263	3.486842105	0.865158524
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	rs9905939	-0.584415584	3.506493506	0.867632335
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.659229356	0.735069435	0.36981179
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.659229356	1.264662828	0.602179488
RAMP2	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	4.268245373	4.657339498	0.401469316
KCNJ8	Oral cavity cancer	rs10841887	-1.088235294	1.823529412	0.55065815
KCNJ8	Oral cavity cancer	rs117973841	-8.57615894	4.238410596	0.043028061
KCNJ8	Oral cavity cancer	rs12816749	-0.473372781	3.905325444	0.903523024
KCNJ8	Oral cavity cancer	rs59406438	-1.416490486	2.938689218	0.629795725

KCNJ8	Oral cavity cancer	rs74732083	-2.511210762	3.789237668	0.507508685
KCNJ8	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.933845771	1.085933166	0.074942723
KCNJ8	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.933845771	1.283102265	0.13176858
KCNJ8	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.492891961	3.891205843	0.567329214
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	rs111327339	-1.163141994	3.429003021	0.73445376
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	rs2120825	0.922384702	0.978627672	0.345922006
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	rs2881654	0.868094701	0.91319053	0.341798691
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	rs310752	9.384615385	4.153846154	0.023867263
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	rs4135247	-0.214477212	1.44772118	0.882225852
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	rs4684833	2.01754386	2.807017544	0.47229497
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	rs76763697	5.401785714	4.508928571	0.230909308
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.94372467	0.586723736	0.107733347
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.94372467	0.573582393	0.099904525
PPARG	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.339779738	0.978886915	0.74264248
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	rs11150624	8.114754098	4.508196721	0.071860638
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	rs12448775	13.75	6.442307692	0.032815911
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	rs34497199	1.937984496	4.263565891	0.649436284
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	rs8054784	3.333333333	5.045045045	0.508795561
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	rs8057029	-0.344827586	4.827586207	0.943056671
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	rs8057326	1.142857143	5.142857143	0.824140896
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.013288951	1.902420591	0.034895431
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.013288951	2.006774112	0.045514217
SLC5A2	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	19.57329345	9.767578315	0.115600126
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	rs111917515	2.029520295	3.616236162	0.57464451
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	rs112898001	3.784860558	3.864541833	0.327391543
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	rs112968754	2.967479675	3.943089431	0.451703951
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	rs113126535	2	3.92	0.609908493
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	rs1659215	3.297297297	5.243243243	0.5294368
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	rs34359922	3.389830508	3.855932203	0.379335738
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	rs4924660	-2.298850575	4.540229885	0.612625628
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	rs73402785	2.320675105	4.008438819	0.562624687

GANC	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.279296418	0.624392609	0.00026181
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.279296418	1.432666953	0.111621625
GANC	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	9.256465084	9.930685219	0.387251563
KCNJ1	Oral cavity cancer	rs116842927	3.790849673	4.836601307	0.433166991
KCNJ1	Oral cavity cancer	rs4937311	-3.650793651	4.761904762	0.443279727
KCNJ1	Oral cavity cancer	rs7110898	-1.276595745	6.765957447	0.850344219
KCNJ1	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.246878872	2.379720348	0.917373454
KCNJ1	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.246878872	3.033189629	0.935129817
KCNJ1	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	5.890199369	6.513439649	0.531961079
GANAB	Oral cavity cancer	Wald_ratio	3.463687151	3.631284916	0.340161523
PRKAB1	Oral cavity cancer	Wald_ratio	-3.605947955	4.05204461	0.37351515
ABCC8	Oral cavity cancer	rs2074312	-4.405405405	1.567567568	0.004948845
DPP4	Oral cavity cancer	rs2080714	5	3.636363636	0.169131445
DPP4	Oral cavity cancer	rs4233648	-1.451612903	4.596774194	0.752162308
DPP4	Oral cavity cancer	rs75850673	-7.950310559	5.403726708	0.141219636
DPP4	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.236382186	3.631513603	0.948100815
DPP4	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.236382186	2.522193649	0.92533089
DPP4	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	3.680430131	46.28020587	0.94947918
RAMP1	Oral cavity cancer	Wald_ratio	15.09803922	5.588235294	0.006897469
RAMP3	Oral cavity cancer	rs4724382	6.306306306	4.864864865	0.194873424
RAMP3	Oral cavity cancer	rs73111954	3.191489362	2.723404255	0.241247246
RAMP3	Oral cavity cancer	rs75390434	4.871794872	5.641025641	0.387787682
RAMP3	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.075952313	0.897042621	5.53E-06
RAMP3	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.075952313	2.189986216	0.062719164
RAMP3	Oral cavity cancer	All - MR Egger	0.795971354	6.280157296	0.919740294
AMY2A	Oral cavity cancer	rs72681706	-4.449648712	4.215456674	0.291171315
AMY2A	Oral cavity cancer	rs72692396	-8.76247505	4.710578842	0.06286155
AMY2A	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	-6.36756565	2.143183917	0.002967568
AMY2A	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.36756565	3.141291136	0.042656927
AMY2A	Oral cavity cancer	rs72681706	-4.449648712	4.215456674	0.291171315
AMY2A	Oral cavity cancer	rs72692396	-8.76247505	4.710578842	0.06286155

AMY2A	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(random effects)	-6.36756565	2.143183917	0.002967568
AMY2A	Oral cavity cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.36756565	3.141291136	0.042656927
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	rs10305525	2.912939134	4.546302329	0.5217
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	rs11963172	0.418237023	2.618529639	0.8731
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	rs12215108	0.387151028	3.059377909	0.8993
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	rs142878626	-1.024757836	3.358905206	0.7603
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	rs228817	-3.447634892	3.315445909	0.2984
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	rs28360624	1.124260798	3.266352945	0.7307
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	rs880347	-1.802921864	1.978252692	0.3621
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	rs9462535	1.001278171	2.699473244	0.7107
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.39196923	0.615467746	0.524213456
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.39196923	1.016837482	0.699882756
GLP1R	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.956295481	4.304618494	0.831561447
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs10766392	-0.699412869	1.15813086	0.5459
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs10766393	-0.664509396	1.169198534	0.5698
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs10766395	-0.36352597	1.050884604	0.7294
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs147673442	4.816022935	2.453655606	0.04967
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs189603359	3.580603846	3.144940914	0.2549
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs2285676	-0.368625312	1.02606607	0.7194
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs2355016	-0.740334194	1.38999833	0.5943
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs35271178	-0.381397161	0.643520368	0.5534
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs4148631	-2.371903371	3.245616227	0.4649
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs5210	-0.364756543	1.032569368	0.7239
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs5219	0.177824111	0.567935503	0.7542
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs7110037	-0.70677511	1.317690501	0.5917
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs7112030	-0.640961787	1.041304687	0.5382
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs739688	1.59593	2.869540747	0.5781
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs77902362	-2.759231296	2.976971412	0.354
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	rs79506407	7.921063866	4.661184127	0.08925
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.208634131	0.249918781	0.40382597
KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.208634131	0.283483219	0.461751131

KCNJ11	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	0.235423417	0.797924436	0.772289857
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	rs1078523	1.986832656	2.574662247	0.4403
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	rs11654396	-5.098491035	3.544378221	0.1503
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	rs11869741	1.441175359	6.901995749	0.8346
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	rs12603201	0.534912205	1.665637281	0.7481
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	rs12941945	-1.796591412	2.450143125	0.4634
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	rs59795094	2.817014112	3.16673545	0.3737
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	rs9892728	2.244179581	2.716320949	0.4087
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	rs9905939	2.205877894	2.67681011	0.4099
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.616140701	0.792031176	0.436613342
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.616140701	0.931177179	0.508176748
RAMP2	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.092172983	3.771869236	0.781900257
KCNJ8	Oropharynx cancer	rs10841887	0.044084592	1.429627705	0.9754
KCNJ8	Oropharynx cancer	rs117973841	1.161507504	3.175086321	0.7145
KCNJ8	Oropharynx cancer	rs12816749	6.922092041	2.740107733	0.01153
KCNJ8	Oropharynx cancer	rs59406438	-5.149544034	2.456682429	0.03607
KCNJ8	Oropharynx cancer	rs74732083	0.209495852	2.488170213	0.9329
KCNJ8	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.228171472	1.609083909	0.887236328
KCNJ8	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.228171472	0.976422796	0.815232626
KCNJ8	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-7.660081161	2.850667999	0.074596415
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs111327339	0.394843771	2.159149717	0.8549
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs1373641	-1.492999937	1.92502343	0.438
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs1699348	0.510368557	3.276041915	0.8762
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs2120825	-2.250141312	0.6877018	0.001068
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs2881654	-1.717425719	0.657967763	0.009049
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs2920503	-3.101812529	2.666911948	0.2448
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs310752	-4.016374727	3.159112559	0.2036
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs4135247	-1.698817041	1.107942508	0.1252
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs4684833	1.078952494	2.163587156	0.618
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	rs76763697	-4.501799773	3.699861189	0.2237
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.783795093	0.297146273	1.94E-09

PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.783795093	0.39702564	7.03E-06
PPARG	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.908681115	0.629223061	0.016225456
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs11150624	-4.139588703	3.419093031	0.226
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs11865835	-3.134067074	3.910739076	0.4229
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs12448775	-1.287877873	3.415224424	0.7061
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs142133957	5.619316257	2.316373296	0.01527
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs34497199	-0.732128591	3.183314381	0.8181
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs4561482	-2.506481144	3.545505509	0.4796
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs8054784	-5.144107391	3.772503193	0.1727
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs8057029	-3.026653199	3.705955558	0.4141
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	rs8057326	-2.391685792	3.877888822	0.5374
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.782726706	1.308001282	0.549563509
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.782726706	1.110532586	0.480921628
SLC5A2	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	5.975042601	2.550047026	0.051608113
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs111917515	1.406543251	2.771482372	0.6118
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs112898001	1.821906442	2.981846699	0.5412
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs112968754	0.908449742	3.061906167	0.7667
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs113126535	1.462410212	3.000649444	0.626
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs1659215	1.90651968	4.025767218	0.6358
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs34359922	1.242619889	3.011684723	0.6799
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs4924660	3.651610391	3.406918751	0.2838
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs73402785	0.470973194	3.122285523	0.8801
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	rs8037100	1.630221666	3.84031877	0.6712
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.547382079	0.28420968	5.19E-08
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.547382079	1.060668356	0.144599637
GANC	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.213851683	7.212900312	0.767826264
KCNJ1	Oropharynx cancer	rs116842927	-2.312387714	3.329046624	0.4873
KCNJ1	Oropharynx cancer	rs4937311	-1.239792135	3.603402193	0.7308
KCNJ1	Oropharynx cancer	rs7110898	10.28135981	4.595534452	0.02527
KCNJ1	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.851349897	3.563649907	0.811184445
KCNJ1	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.851349897	2.158676245	0.693296691

KCNJ1	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	0.851432926	10.59048432	0.948928142
RAMP3	Oropharynx cancer	rs11772021	-2.018686985	1.128369617	0.07361
RAMP3	Oropharynx cancer	rs4724382	-1.713333859	3.723328192	0.6454
RAMP3	Oropharynx cancer	rs73111954	1.999437924	2.092882087	0.3394
RAMP3	Oropharynx cancer	rs75390434	-3.729782652	4.302465971	0.386
RAMP3	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.275673232	0.970620076	0.188749681
RAMP3	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.275673232	0.93663974	0.173208025
RAMP3	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.621506752	2.141878328	0.528052509
INSR	Oropharynx cancer	rs144057856	-0.38931772	2.423983194	0.8724
INSR	Oropharynx cancer	rs4031066	-4.094329044	2.90629252	0.1589
INSR	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.909298452	1.822417185	0.294788995
INSR	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.909298452	1.861502379	0.305044296
ETFDH	Oropharynx cancer	Wald_ratio	2.617170632	2.849057611	0.3583
GANAB	Oropharynx cancer	Wald_ratio	5.835201193	2.834942171	0.03956
PRKAB1	Oropharynx cancer	Wald_ratio	1.006056489	3.067101157	0.7429
DPP4	Oropharynx cancer	rs188581353	2.315458754	2.790073289	0.4066
DPP4	Oropharynx cancer	rs2080714	-2.004653485	2.759130105	0.4675
DPP4	Oropharynx cancer	rs4233648	-19.55447416	7.395183431	0.008188
DPP4	Oropharynx cancer	rs75850673	6.582628791	4.202909218	0.1173
DPP4	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.147011179	3.25734631	0.964001942
DPP4	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.147011179	1.728474381	0.932219602
DPP4	Oropharynx cancer	All - MR Egger	4.375718901	7.198777895	0.605120244
ABCC8	Oropharynx cancer	rs2074312	-1.36355523	1.186591927	0.2505
ABCC8	Oropharynx cancer	rs77023203	-0.673156118	0.990845513	0.4969
ABCC8	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.95678801	0.33966477	0.00484957
ABCC8	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.95678801	0.760551817	0.208385183
RAMP1	Oropharynx cancer	Wald_ratio	-10.42755059	8.294607692	0.2087
AMY2A	Oropharynx cancer	rs72681706	1.198783063	2.961176522	0.6856
AMY2A	Oropharynx cancer	rs72692396	-2.167371465	2.888839127	0.4531
AMY2A	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.525911461	1.682562653	0.754610601
AMY2A	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.525911461	2.067818542	0.79923944

AMY2A	Oropharynx cancer	rs72681706	1.198783063	2.961176522	0.6856
AMY2A	Oropharynx cancer	rs72692396	-2.167371465	2.888839127	0.4531
AMY2A	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.525911461	1.682562653	0.754610601
AMY2A	Oropharynx cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.525911461	2.067818542	0.79923944
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	rs10305525	1.831012658	1.499367089	0.222013947
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11963172	-0.127611111	0.863888889	0.882566082
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12215108	0.328134715	1.013989637	0.746235162
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	rs142878626	-1.512903226	1.222580645	0.215913751
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	rs228817	-0.265891473	1.098449612	0.808733136
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	rs28360624	-0.641916168	1.047904192	0.540159755
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	rs880347	-1.261244019	0.66937799	0.059537522
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	rs9462535	-1.783225806	0.88	0.042724532
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.687316517	0.342498063	0.044773636
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.687316517	0.339247137	0.042764235
GLP1R	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.78695428	1.578728119	0.300878445
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs10766392	0.878385417	0.38046875	0.020960641
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs10766393	0.915223097	0.383464567	0.016999367
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs10766395	0.328571429	0.343609023	0.338952852
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs147673442	0.662694301	0.708549223	0.349642286
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs189603359	1.473346304	1.242023346	0.235524823
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2285676	0.333414634	0.333414634	0.317310508
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2355016	0.062611111	0.461388889	0.892057353
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs35271178	0.223255814	0.207906977	0.282900897
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4148631	-0.207272727	1.076223776	0.847278047
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs5210	0.330541872	0.336945813	0.326595625
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs5219	0.271601615	0.184253028	0.140463105
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs7110037	0.041894737	0.436842105	0.923597124
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs7112030	0.357320099	0.340942928	0.294622512
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs739688	-0.02151497	0.828742515	0.979288459
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs77902362	0.38474026	1.01525974	0.704719448
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	rs79506407	0.220875912	1.247201946	0.859432079

KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.342595648	0.063137004	5.76E-08
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.342595648	0.092180356	0.000201938
KCNJ11	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.314929043	0.2546256	0.236496093
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs1078523	1.98	0.825	0.016395072
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11654396	0.7275	1.119117647	0.515649782
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11869741	2.949860724	1.109192201	0.007826426
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12603201	1.207287449	0.54534413	0.026841958
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12941945	0.55720524	0.791703057	0.481553692
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs59795094	2.526153846	1.023076923	0.013542575
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs9892728	2.105263158	0.869736842	0.015495987
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs9905939	1.82012987	0.859090909	0.034118392
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.585065824	0.265864613	2.49E-09
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.585065824	0.292719337	6.13E-08
RAMP2	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.987663835	1.094646109	0.401682039
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs111327339	0.175981873	0.758912387	0.816625826
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs1373641	0.302567568	0.629279279	0.630647253
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs1699348	-0.022672	1.0632	0.982986956
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.193588301	0.237457818	0.414927257
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.072559188	0.223449831	0.745391102
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2920503	0.054930233	0.851744186	0.948578901
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs310752	1.726153846	1.041538462	0.097456479
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4135247	-0.007587131	0.361126005	0.983237957
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4684833	0.259912281	0.702631579	0.711447606
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	rs76763697	-0.371741071	1.167410714	0.750157175
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.03548837	0.089097034	0.69040061
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.03548837	0.134066176	0.791234524
PPARG	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.25180708	0.213006024	0.27108572
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11150624	-0.295737705	1.107377049	0.789421859
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11865835	2.41826087	1.323478261	0.067669546
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs12448775	-0.621474359	1.276282051	0.626299976
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs142133957	-1.876019576	1.063621533	0.077765038

SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs34497199	0.466744186	1.037984496	0.652952785
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4561482	0.625726496	1.170940171	0.593078956
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8054784	-0.093243243	1.223423423	0.939248032
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8057029	0.698448276	1.205172414	0.562223379
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8057326	0.160095238	1.254285714	0.898435004
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.07798164	0.380403938	0.837574523
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.07798164	0.391211398	0.842001671
SLC5A2	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-2.046015882	1.100429639	0.105321467
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs111917515	-0.599261993	0.925461255	0.517290337
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs112898001	-0.836653386	1.002788845	0.404096978
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs112968754	-0.525203252	1.015853659	0.60515141
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs113126535	-0.6436	1.0036	0.521333407
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs1659215	-1.130810811	1.344864865	0.400439809
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs34359922	-0.084533898	0.989830508	0.931941487
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4924660	-0.282873563	1.13045977	0.802410434
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs73402785	-0.440506329	1.032067511	0.66951095
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	rs8037100	-1.194871795	1.273846154	0.348242755
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.592702152	0.112268956	1.30E-07
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.592702152	0.352781834	0.092941504
GANC	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.27207315	2.40151343	0.912979494
KCNJ1	Ovarian carcinoma	rs116842927	0.173660131	1.085185185	0.872858934
KCNJ1	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4937311	0.851587302	1.161904762	0.463605091
KCNJ1	Ovarian carcinoma	rs7110898	-1.805531915	1.806382979	0.317538567
KCNJ1	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.118611206	0.636212625	0.852104997
KCNJ1	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.118611206	0.726172504	0.870252705
KCNJ1	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.567042239	1.682775753	0.793086777
RAMP3	Ovarian carcinoma	rs11772021	-0.314492754	0.385093168	0.414118945
RAMP3	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4724382	-1.588288288	1.214414414	0.190919611
RAMP3	Ovarian carcinoma	rs73111954	-0.276255319	0.690212766	0.688974888
RAMP3	Ovarian carcinoma	rs75390434	-3.501709402	1.447863248	0.015583103
RAMP3	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.544935733	0.42503233	0.199806099

RAMP3	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.544935733	0.316268462	0.084885568
RAMP3	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.350452917	0.575564318	0.604548086
INSR	Ovarian carcinoma	rs144057856	0.336958935	0.939067703	0.719727629
INSR	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4031066	0.070342466	1.001369863	0.943997673
INSR	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.212202213	0.133033669	0.110689526
INSR	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.212202213	0.684988071	0.756720925
ETFDH	Ovarian carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-0.010438571	0.918857143	0.990935919
GANAB	Ovarian carcinoma	Wald_ratio	0.749162011	0.953631285	0.432108456
DPP4	Ovarian carcinoma	rs188581353	-0.609637046	1.221401752	0.617688502
DPP4	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2080714	0.023298701	0.951948052	0.980473915
DPP4	Ovarian carcinoma	rs4233648	-1.474193548	1.17983871	0.211486876
DPP4	Ovarian carcinoma	rs75850673	2.036645963	1.31552795	0.121584107
DPP4	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.086363943	0.674073692	0.898052105
DPP4	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.086363943	0.570726931	0.879721159
DPP4	Ovarian carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.06325352	2.093920014	0.97864446
ABCC8	Ovarian carcinoma	rs2074312	0.674594595	0.391351351	0.084751737
ABCC8	Ovarian carcinoma	rs77023203	0.315654206	0.322429907	0.32758714
ABCC8	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.460785911	0.176154531	0.008901737
ABCC8	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.460785911	0.248849529	0.064073973
RAMP1	Ovarian carcinoma	Wald_ratio	0.584607843	1.37745098	0.671264779
AMY2A	Ovarian carcinoma	rs72681706	1.32763466	0.994145199	0.181727973
AMY2A	Ovarian carcinoma	rs72692396	0.257684631	0.996007984	0.795853266
AMY2A	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.793661119	0.534974077	0.137928181
AMY2A	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.793661119	0.703624481	0.259336303
AMY2A	Ovarian carcinoma	rs72681706	1.32763466	0.994145199	0.181727973
AMY2A	Ovarian carcinoma	rs72692396	0.257684631	0.996007984	0.795853266
AMY2A	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.793661119	0.534974077	0.137928181
AMY2A	Ovarian carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.793661119	0.703624481	0.259336303
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	rs10305525	1.667707299	6.157120357	0.7865
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	rs11963172	-4.337307523	3.631201856	0.2323
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	rs12215108	0.664119363	4.18457179	0.8739

GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	rs142878626	-3.596064185	4.432534281	0.4172
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	rs228817	-3.85392188	4.499414781	0.3917
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	rs28360624	-5.815970702	4.580672443	0.2042
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	rs880347	-1.682970096	2.690973747	0.5317
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	rs9462535	3.383990968	3.667003118	0.3561
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.689993895	1.085577442	0.119525211
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.689993895	1.387096529	0.223084195
GLP1R	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.71150792	5.748708113	0.542409425
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs10766392	2.057187662	1.615235489	0.2028
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs10766393	2.334021239	1.635693991	0.1536
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs10766395	2.002998075	1.446711813	0.1662
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs147673442	2.752593778	3.130183856	0.3792
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs189603359	2.214801876	4.485896586	0.6215
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs2285676	2.180086857	1.409374047	0.1219
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs2355016	-1.136837961	1.881508988	0.5457
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs35271178	1.047522266	0.868933208	0.228
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs4148631	-1.158187993	4.433261591	0.7939
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs5210	2.174521302	1.422693863	0.1264
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs5219	1.209161561	0.766334769	0.1146
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs7110037	-0.964841694	1.786278432	0.5891
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs7112030	2.05174607	1.435077551	0.1528
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs739688	0.668387108	4.02467382	0.8681
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs77902362	1.352456989	3.89321963	0.7283
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	rs79506407	-0.778754164	5.18886131	0.8807
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.347911162	0.244499116	3.53E-08
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.347911162	0.386088942	0.000480868
KCNJ11	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	1.511608852	1.086542631	0.18587622
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	rs1078523	0.985932445	3.506860018	0.7786
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	rs11654396	-12.45626212	4.934369508	0.01159
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	rs11869741	11.82222008	9.503401423	0.2135
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	rs12603201	-1.665366128	2.279329884	0.465

RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	rs12941945	-5.162767745	3.410676886	0.1301
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	rs59795094	0.85674957	4.317400835	0.8427
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	rs9892728	1.05077431	3.689560969	0.7758
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	rs9905939	0.175561791	3.599550771	0.9611
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.506329001	1.48789424	0.311351697
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.506329001	1.273922056	0.237033462
RAMP2	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.178174847	6.530558953	0.862770368
KCNJ8	Pancreas cancer	rs10841887	1.423798212	1.937835204	0.4625
KCNJ8	Pancreas cancer	rs117973841	-3.944418242	3.98200447	0.3219
KCNJ8	Pancreas cancer	rs12816749	-4.361836558	3.887860952	0.2619
KCNJ8	Pancreas cancer	rs59406438	2.187598488	2.869223541	0.4458
KCNJ8	Pancreas cancer	rs74732083	0.49878047	3.389208044	0.883
KCNJ8	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.249942383	1.176603172	0.831773856
KCNJ8	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.249942383	1.286661186	0.845974993
KCNJ8	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	5.420574918	3.8183818	0.250794369
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs111327339	2.110603371	2.755500148	0.4437
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs1373641	-1.684329694	2.612443878	0.5191
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs1699348	0.97799757	4.456597353	0.8263
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs2120825	0.569156949	1.03149501	0.5811
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs2881654	0.663300854	0.967328738	0.4929
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs2920503	-0.509389864	3.578319367	0.8868
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs310752	-2.831844086	4.289114933	0.5091
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs4135247	-2.276260244	1.511198359	0.132
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs4684833	3.628493316	2.987921884	0.2246
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	rs76763697	-1.401864426	4.954113504	0.7772
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.157858143	0.467859218	0.735811449
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.157858143	0.57164082	0.782433489
PPARG	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	0.759849033	0.910816157	0.428345826
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs11150624	1.831792104	4.620912381	0.6918
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs11865835	2.64627888	5.393818409	0.6237
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs12448775	3.178127293	4.388042245	0.4689

SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs142133957	0.992041426	3.719687597	0.7897
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs34497199	11.61227636	4.345255404	0.007531
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs4561482	0.111038951	4.976905359	0.9822
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs8054784	3.550720933	5.068662801	0.4836
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs8057029	1.98557751	4.990075669	0.6907
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	rs8057326	8.573666919	5.261422185	0.1032
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.770114838	1.295308924	0.003607456
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.770114838	1.554258358	0.01528024
SLC5A2	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	1.137428795	3.858873913	0.776729592
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs111917515	0.926667927	3.79720008	0.8072
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs112898001	0.630460173	4.110492814	0.8781
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs112968754	1.020841497	4.143620713	0.8054
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs113126535	0.83668993	4.112940265	0.8388
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs1659215	0.167308373	5.515384191	0.9758
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs34359922	2.811589006	4.031968888	0.4856
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs4924660	-0.693826508	4.755479851	0.884
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs73402785	0.839520326	4.214289088	0.8421
GANC	Pancreas cancer	rs8037100	0.357723781	5.262040328	0.9458
GANC	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.87740869	0.311735367	0.00488388
GANC	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.87740869	1.448024141	0.544557833
GANC	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	4.158704091	9.943436169	0.688306717
KCNJ1	Pancreas cancer	rs116842927	2.198926331	5.195120328	0.6721
KCNJ1	Pancreas cancer	rs4937311	3.569314734	4.939258828	0.4699
KCNJ1	Pancreas cancer	rs7110898	-5.078585431	7.368856186	0.4907
KCNJ1	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.391816672	2.264775152	0.538852205
KCNJ1	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.391816672	3.219817895	0.66554835
KCNJ1	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.640145331	6.97588318	0.941743434
RAMP3	Pancreas cancer	rs11772021	2.279694051	1.650449045	0.1672
RAMP3	Pancreas cancer	rs4724382	-4.472697287	5.076651694	0.3783
RAMP3	Pancreas cancer	rs73111954	-0.212235809	2.902038498	0.9417
RAMP3	Pancreas cancer	rs75390434	-1.787798996	5.895479129	0.7617

RAMP3	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.06015657	1.140451891	0.352581637
RAMP3	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.06015657	1.344225237	0.4303021
RAMP3	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	3.967751848	2.442625841	0.245787629
INSR	Pancreas cancer	rs144057856	3.268649254	2.893969628	0.2587
INSR	Pancreas cancer	rs4031066	-1.093956816	3.981487646	0.7835
INSR	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.760553744	2.074819163	0.396140876
INSR	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.760553744	2.340921208	0.452004563
ETFHDH	Pancreas cancer	Wald_ratio	5.265756334	3.660658014	0.1503
GANAB	Pancreas cancer	Wald_ratio	-0.798982386	3.757265628	0.8316
PRKAB1	Pancreas cancer	Wald_ratio	-3.097754929	4.413974548	0.4828
DPP4	Pancreas cancer	rs188581353	2.398559252	3.950018045	0.5437
DPP4	Pancreas cancer	rs2080714	3.84492595	3.820291805	0.3142
DPP4	Pancreas cancer	rs4233648	-19.61140686	9.128806407	0.03169
DPP4	Pancreas cancer	rs75850673	6.800124883	5.735839098	0.2358
DPP4	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.22013867	3.529356823	0.529316924
DPP4	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.22013867	2.39042251	0.35301134
DPP4	Pancreas cancer	All - MR Egger	4.213624795	8.670913446	0.675031806
ABCC8	Pancreas cancer	rs2074312	1.949583723	1.657827364	0.2396
ABCC8	Pancreas cancer	rs77023203	1.517399267	1.366171957	0.2667
ABCC8	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.692192798	0.212109096	1.49E-15
ABCC8	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.692192798	1.054307777	0.10848779
RAMP1	Pancreas cancer	Wald_ratio	-10.27501121	10.21551098	0.3145
AMY2A	Pancreas cancer	rs72681706	-0.067817403	4.068267136	0.9867
AMY2A	Pancreas cancer	rs72692396	0.622377594	3.641699794	0.8643
AMY2A	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.315349802	0.342991226	0.357880796
AMY2A	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.315349802	2.713391147	0.907478337
AMY2A	Pancreas cancer	rs72681706	-0.067817403	4.068267136	0.9867
AMY2A	Pancreas cancer	rs72692396	0.622377594	3.641699794	0.8643
AMY2A	Pancreas cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.315349802	0.342991226	0.357880796
AMY2A	Pancreas cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.315349802	2.713391147	0.907478337
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal cancer	rs10305525	2.35443038	4.829113924	0.625869222

GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs11963172	8.416666667	5.027777778	0.094124085
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs12215108	2.81865285	5.906735751	0.633224708
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs142878626	-5.237327189	5.052995392	0.299978401
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs228817	0.379844961	4.852713178	0.937609494
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs28360624	4.005988024	6.347305389	0.52795417
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs880347	-4.177033493	2.933014354	0.15440492
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs9462535	-7.709677419	3.774193548	0.041078674
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-1.489225055	1.885280077	0.42957306
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.489225055	1.573291494	0.343859711
GLP1R	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	-6.020556675	8.089716401	0.484856602
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs10766392	-2.252604167	1.544270833	0.144651922
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs10766393	-2.152230971	1.556430446	0.166726406
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs10766395	-1.348370927	1.438596491	0.348613401
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs147673442	-0.124352332	3.593264249	0.972393067
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs189603359	-4.653696498	6.554474708	0.477702296
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs2285676	-1.680487805	1.4	0.230004047
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs2355016	-0.077777778	2.141666667	0.971030016
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs35271178	-1.201550388	0.896124031	0.179975507
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4148631	-2.594405594	4.958041958	0.600784834
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs5210	-1.704433498	1.413793103	0.227981437
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs5219	-1.273216689	0.790040377	0.107052423
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs7110037	0.084210526	1.973684211	0.965967252
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs7112030	-1.851116625	1.426799007	0.194496583
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs739688	0.347305389	3.491017964	0.920752863
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs77902362	-7.37987013	5.350649351	0.167818435
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs79506407	2.068126521	3.00973236	0.491990526
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-1.361391518	0.226220585	1.77E-09
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.361391518	0.391992013	0.000514659
KCNJ11	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	-1.285220473	1.105379556	0.264389432
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs1078523	2.1375	3.60625	0.553367905
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs11654396	6.360294118	5.102941176	0.212618427

RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs11869741	3.116991643	4.913649025	0.525849991
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs12603201	-1.643724696	2.315789474	0.477834241
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs12941945	-3.240174672	4.672489083	0.48802221
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs59795094	4.192307692	4.446153846	0.345728692
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs9892728	1.914473684	3.796052632	0.614027563
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs9905939	2.155844156	3.707792208	0.560946589
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	1.004873571	1.013910398	0.321643025
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	1.004873571	1.311136923	0.443430061
RAMP2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	-5.751582673	4.887781016	0.283868792
KCNJ8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs10841887	-2.447058824	2.155882353	0.256349597
KCNJ8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs117973841	-4.135761589	6.006622517	0.491116802
KCNJ8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs12816749	4.75147929	4.609467456	0.302630524
KCNJ8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs59406438	0.44820296	4.181818182	0.914647
KCNJ8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs74732083	-7.522421525	4.576233184	0.100217096
KCNJ8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-1.902067319	1.613108109	0.238345636
KCNJ8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.902067319	1.591375787	0.231995404
KCNJ8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	-8.427934849	4.814276021	0.178315096
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs111327339	-2.149546828	4.264350453	0.614209601
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs1373641	-0.846846847	2.887387387	0.769299173
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs1699348	-0.52	5.136	0.919355097
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs2120825	0.724409449	1.293588301	0.575479438
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs2881654	0.372040586	1.19729425	0.756002495
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs2920503	-2.029069767	3.494186047	0.561443447
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs310752	-4.946153846	4.476923077	0.269241495
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4135247	-0.605898123	1.528150134	0.691742678
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4684833	0.342105263	3.096491228	0.912027452
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs76763697	-0.120535714	4.53125	0.978777987
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-0.08540102	0.351679035	0.808130926
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.08540102	0.670997711	0.898722998
PPARG	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	0.919373484	1.100745279	0.427826673
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs11150624	7.557377049	4.680327869	0.106373287

SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs11865835	2.756521739	5.782608696	0.633581653
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs12448775	12.00641026	6.467948718	0.063411755
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs142133957	-2.926590538	4.849918434	0.546222086
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs34497199	-1.356589147	5.201550388	0.794243067
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4561482	13.12820513	4.888888889	0.007246155
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs8054784	11.78378378	5.153153153	0.022212564
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs8057029	13.0862069	5.017241379	0.009100715
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs8057326	3.657142857	7.485714286	0.625160589
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	6.702531417	2.178539909	0.002093646
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	6.702531417	1.778914487	0.000164716
SLC5A2	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	-1.202126878	5.977769412	0.846339281
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs111917515	0.099630996	5.357933579	0.985164159
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs112898001	0.211155378	5.784860558	0.97088258
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs112968754	1.056910569	5.894308943	0.857694024
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs113126535	0.188	5.8	0.974142063
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs1659215	-6.491891892	5.789189189	0.262125343
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs34359922	0.970338983	5.792372881	0.86696082
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4924660	-4.33908046	4.833333333	0.36932376
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs73402785	-0.299578059	5.991561181	0.960122388
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs8037100	-5.953846154	5.497435897	0.278798486
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-1.779648359	1.021807325	0.081566685
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.779648359	1.867872671	0.340707889
GANC	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	14.2304729	11.84763952	0.26876303
KCNJ1	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs116842927	-8.810457516	6.718954248	0.189761816
KCNJ1	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4937311	-7.095238095	4.944444444	0.151289385
KCNJ1	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs7110898	3.259574468	4.080851064	0.424436144
KCNJ1	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-2.35293941	3.894962792	0.545778459
KCNJ1	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.35293941	2.850135609	0.409057426
KCNJ1	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	1.441815591	13.67213105	0.93311151
RAMP3	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs11772021	0.666666667	2.144927536	0.755944451
RAMP3	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4724382	4.837837838	5.756756757	0.400697833

RAMP3	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs73111954	1.093617021	2.965957447	0.71233413
RAMP3	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs75390434	2.641025641	5.735042735	0.645152559
RAMP3	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	1.265284605	0.667787829	0.058126797
RAMP3	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	1.265284605	1.597981572	0.428476282
RAMP3	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	-0.413310639	2.997965403	0.902975566
ETFDH	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	Wald_ratio	-8.377142857	5.237142857	0.109695438
GANAB	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	Wald_ratio	6.279329609	4.374301676	0.151143395
PRKAB1	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	Wald_ratio	0.475836431	5.988847584	0.936671713
DPP4	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs188581353	-8.018773467	5.066332916	0.11347688
DPP4	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs2080714	2.123376623	5.311688312	0.689336609
DPP4	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4233648	-3.403225806	4.903225806	0.4876327
DPP4	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs75850673	-4.279503106	4.627329193	0.355053191
DPP4	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-3.556034961	1.995994317	0.074816816
DPP4	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.556034961	2.479171714	0.15146838
DPP4	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	All - MR Egger	-8.556947832	6.000726609	0.289968585
ABCC8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs2074312	-2.732432432	1.594594595	0.08660969
ABCC8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs77023203	-1.570093458	1.348130841	0.244162836
ABCC8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-2.05459103	0.573072869	0.000336797
ABCC8	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.05459103	1.029507915	0.045966367
INSR	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs4031066	-2.301369863	4.828767123	0.633650014
RAMP1	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	Wald_ratio	-5.696078431	6	0.342444459
AMY2A	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs72681706	-4.641686183	5.807962529	0.424178192
AMY2A	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs72692396	-6.251497006	5.325349301	0.240429857
AMY2A	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-5.51624372	0.801886091	6.02E-12
AMY2A	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-5.51624372	3.925137468	0.159913306
AMY2A	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs72681706	-4.641686183	5.807962529	0.424178192
AMY2A	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	rs72692396	-6.251497006	5.325349301	0.240429857
AMY2A	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(random effects)	-5.51624372	0.801886091	6.02E-12
AMY2A	Pharyngeal laryngeal canc	IVW(fixed effects)	-5.51624372	3.925137468	0.159913306
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10305525	19.42367089	10.69563291	0.069364614
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11963172	-0.371625	6.298333333	0.952949157

GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12215108	5.863989637	7.467564767	0.432300379
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	rs142878626	-3.145599078	8.248225806	0.702931129
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	rs228817	-9.871782946	7.926511628	0.21297987
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	rs28360624	3.629982036	7.965508982	0.64859673
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	rs880347	-1.139866029	4.761100478	0.810785891
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	rs9462535	4.813477419	6.549548387	0.462380469
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	1.094615785	2.316043667	0.636482084
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.094615785	2.456736818	0.655917425
GLP1R	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-0.470735959	10.64340467	0.9661579
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10766392	4.817421875	2.795989583	0.084892935
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10766393	4.835065617	2.819527559	0.086372811
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10766395	1.441253133	2.519022556	0.56722187
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs147673442	5.299170984	5.506683938	0.33589081
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs189603359	-12.27453307	8.353657588	0.141735081
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2285676	1.489507317	2.453512195	0.543789942
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2355016	-0.813561111	3.377222222	0.809635312
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs35271178	0.948333333	1.542868217	0.538781869
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4148631	-6.40113986	7.881188811	0.416674091
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs5210	1.493408867	2.477413793	0.546635346
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs5219	1.297987887	1.374522207	0.345006492
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs7110037	-1.284563158	3.200947368	0.688193979
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs7112030	1.855111663	2.501364764	0.458305603
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs739688	-1.71342515	6.052275449	0.777096892
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs77902362	-0.746503247	6.756201299	0.91201954
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	rs79506407	2.753065693	9.448515815	0.770764177
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	1.385602624	0.520873204	0.007810507
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.385602624	0.680626373	0.041772884
KCNJ11	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	2.157946781	1.880450345	0.270379315
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs1078523	5.75535	6.1265625	0.347520622
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11654396	3.316213235	8.338014706	0.690834999
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11869741	7.519164345	6.703481894	0.261998347

RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12603201	-1.409	4.007910931	0.725172229
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12941945	-3.200187773	5.835371179	0.583409016
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs59795094	7.79	7.581523077	0.304186014
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs9892728	5.822598684	6.455835526	0.367103357
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs9905939	7.048636364	6.403707792	0.271022134
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	2.87199913	1.60589469	0.073709783
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.87199913	2.128734434	0.177286216
RAMP2	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-4.639048217	7.608972039	0.564432116
KCNJ8	Pleural mesothelioma	rs10841887	1.797961765	3.393088235	0.59618856
KCNJ8	Pleural mesothelioma	rs117973841	-4.889006623	7.415728477	0.509719
KCNJ8	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12816749	-3.316349112	6.765147929	0.623984683
KCNJ8	Pleural mesothelioma	rs59406438	1.76492389	5.28551797	0.73844225
KCNJ8	Pleural mesothelioma	rs74732083	-2.965695067	5.938318386	0.617485893
KCNJ8	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-0.136727439	1.310834518	0.916926799
KCNJ8	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.136727439	2.287875304	0.952345388
KCNJ8	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	3.016594137	6.752043817	0.685325857
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs111327339	0.839481873	5.561404834	0.880016887
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs1373641	4.43554955	4.69018018	0.344296602
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs1699348	-9.58248	7.956544	0.228453541
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2120825	-2.159550056	1.79928009	0.230050003
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2881654	-1.759278467	1.671319053	0.29251118
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2920503	-1.197662791	6.351860465	0.850443118
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs310752	-0.727324615	7.611753846	0.923875731
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4135247	0.073376944	2.665016086	0.978034304
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4684833	-0.25896886	5.151929825	0.959910115
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	rs76763697	11.00607143	8.12375	0.175480701
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-1.098594	0.790150548	0.164419477
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.098594	1.001931962	0.272870673
PPARG	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-1.825921035	1.595672832	0.285581789
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11150624	1.006967213	8.163959016	0.90183549
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11865835	2.678495652	9.450173913	0.776844569

SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs12448775	-7.417788462	8.016634615	0.354810109
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs142133957	-6.811386623	6.209021207	0.27263503
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs34497199	-3.344511628	7.635821705	0.661384221
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4561482	-0.060205812	8.503452991	0.994350896
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8054784	-1.783666667	9.04963964	0.84375078
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8057029	-0.511726724	8.901724138	0.95415786
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8057326	-7.666695238	9.327771429	0.411121615
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-3.122483423	1.272366301	0.014124718
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.122483423	2.721608263	0.251260347
SLC5A2	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-8.442763967	6.610030266	0.242238836
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs111917515	-4.012214022	6.769409594	0.553383429
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs112898001	-2.827513944	7.324780876	0.699481652
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs112968754	-4.655447154	7.432804878	0.531093354
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs113126535	-4.5544	7.31692	0.533647526
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs1659215	-6.563891892	9.85427027	0.505349619
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs34359922	-0.272060593	7.28190678	0.970197029
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4924660	-4.82345977	8.398103448	0.565730251
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs73402785	-2.477658228	7.571392405	0.743486791
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	rs8037100	-6.149538462	9.358051282	0.511091681
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-3.775138374	0.623108756	1.37E-09
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.775138374	2.586836492	0.144464702
GANC	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	1.547099656	17.67494835	0.932701094
KCNJ1	Pleural mesothelioma	rs116842927	12.71385621	8.326427015	0.126778867
KCNJ1	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4937311	-16.04809524	8.744285714	0.066466202
KCNJ1	Pleural mesothelioma	rs7110898	12.48761702	12.22395745	0.306984896
KCNJ1	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	1.669057488	9.85948483	0.865572905
KCNJ1	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.669057488	5.407814517	0.757596851
KCNJ1	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	26.33541617	11.35759049	0.25921036
RAMP3	Pleural mesothelioma	rs11772021	-2.000080745	2.779627329	0.471802129
RAMP3	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4724382	-0.927468468	8.961963964	0.917574545
RAMP3	Pleural mesothelioma	rs73111954	2.735017021	4.949234043	0.580527615

RAMP3	Pleural mesothelioma	rs75390434	-11.23435897	10.5308547	0.286060307
RAMP3	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	-1.356452343	1.677837352	0.418829954
RAMP3	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.356452343	2.283841447	0.552555889
RAMP3	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	-0.707673032	4.174406057	0.88097866
ETFDH	Pleural mesothelioma	Wald_ratio	13.30668571	6.509	0.040918808
GANAB	Pleural mesothelioma	Wald_ratio	6.527877095	6.592625698	0.322086815
PRKAB1	Pleural mesothelioma	Wald_ratio	12.64312268	7.475836431	0.090798915
DPP4	Pleural mesothelioma	rs188581353	4.64126408	7.363028786	0.528467492
DPP4	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2080714	3.757928571	6.672987013	0.57332908
DPP4	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4233648	9.533467742	8.176693548	0.243641985
DPP4	Pleural mesothelioma	rs75850673	9.262981366	9.445403727	0.326747288
DPP4	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	6.208901479	1.495668073	3.31E-05
DPP4	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	6.208901479	3.861362194	0.107844761
DPP4	Pleural mesothelioma	All - MR Egger	3.634703088	8.806848156	0.719853423
ABCC8	Pleural mesothelioma	rs2074312	3.852108108	2.879432432	0.180961257
ABCC8	Pleural mesothelioma	rs77023203	1.140511682	2.377102804	0.631376267
ABCC8	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	2.23952695	1.331259296	0.092518043
ABCC8	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.23952695	1.833142509	0.221825895
INSR	Pleural mesothelioma	rs4031066	-1.763773973	7.035684932	0.802054
RAMP1	Pleural mesothelioma	Wald_ratio	7.535705882	10.22088235	0.460948895
AMY2A	Pleural mesothelioma	rs72681706	4.338969555	7.449578454	0.560266993
AMY2A	Pleural mesothelioma	rs72692396	10.49125749	6.638403194	0.114017875
AMY2A	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	7.768187008	3.055814262	0.011018848
AMY2A	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	7.768187008	4.956131408	0.117023739
AMY2A	Pleural mesothelioma	rs72681706	4.338969555	7.449578454	0.560266993
AMY2A	Pleural mesothelioma	rs72692396	10.49125749	6.638403194	0.114017875
AMY2A	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(random effects)	7.768187008	3.055814262	0.011018848
AMY2A	Pleural mesothelioma	IVW(fixed effects)	7.768187008	4.956131408	0.117023739
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	rs10305525	-2.907196203	1.817943038	0.109783294
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	rs11963172	0.733088889	1.068566667	0.49268233
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	rs12215108	1.697492228	1.268595855	0.180867922

GLP1R	Prostate cancer	rs142878626	-1.025	1.409947005	0.46723963
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	rs228817	-1.660620155	1.346248062	0.217382859
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	rs28360624	1.844874251	1.348592814	0.171312243
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	rs880347	1.669382775	0.809186603	0.03910901
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	rs9462535	3.09696129	1.113077419	0.005396825
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.949490351	0.622445846	0.127154771
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.949490351	0.417437957	0.022931954
GLP1R	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	1.000323299	2.875614055	0.739821139
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs10766392	0.474356771	0.475640625	0.318618531
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs10766393	0.587385827	0.479750656	0.220817777
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs10766395	0.261062657	0.428238095	0.542113329
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs147673442	-0.540611399	0.934326425	0.562851788
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs189603359	0.65744358	1.439178988	0.647801511
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs2285676	0.28615122	0.417031707	0.492611095
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs2355016	0.398836111	0.572977778	0.486381201
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs35271178	0.235294574	0.261826357	0.36883033
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs4148631	0.470528671	1.339643357	0.725412594
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs5210	0.283800493	0.421083744	0.500326338
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs5219	0.159032301	0.233219381	0.49530217
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs7110037	0.350931579	0.543042105	0.51812865
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs7112030	0.232852109	0.425153846	0.583905427
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs739688	0.597843713	1.028946108	0.561223408
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs77902362	-1.030967532	1.15161039	0.370658877
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	rs79506407	1.559931873	1.597647202	0.328869647
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.263631084	0.058368447	6.28E-06
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.263631084	0.115604717	0.022580855
KCNJ11	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	0.110314781	0.319335017	0.734890547
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	rs1078523	-0.677475	1.04116875	0.515248538
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	rs11654396	0.706600735	1.416742647	0.617955347
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	rs11869741	-0.349988858	1.136724234	0.758164138
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	rs12603201	0.630133603	0.681283401	0.355006789

RAMP2	Prostate cancer	rs12941945	-1.80741048	0.991502183	0.068318362
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	rs59795094	-0.991653846	1.288361538	0.441476963
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	rs9892728	-0.771723684	1.097026316	0.481763702
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	rs9905939	-0.896766234	1.088168831	0.409879451
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.395161077	0.321131458	0.218499651
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.395161077	0.36168757	0.274592248
RAMP2	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	0.304136634	1.292177462	0.821751066
KCNJ8	Prostate cancer	rs10841887	-1.154694118	0.577458824	0.045542079
KCNJ8	Prostate cancer	rs117973841	1.359456954	1.261274834	0.281103578
KCNJ8	Prostate cancer	rs12816749	0.77091716	1.149236686	0.502342852
KCNJ8	Prostate cancer	rs59406438	1.994964059	0.895991543	0.025977805
KCNJ8	Prostate cancer	rs74732083	-0.990067265	1.015818386	0.329733964
KCNJ8	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.075610619	0.659458938	0.908718157
KCNJ8	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.075610619	0.389268143	0.845989623
KCNJ8	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.353012843	2.23896266	0.884732948
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs111327339	-0.144312538	0.947797583	0.878981142
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs1373641	-2.361707207	0.796734234	0.003034368
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs1699348	0.4799232	1.351208	0.722454113
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs2120825	0.099571991	0.306805399	0.745525872
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs2881654	-0.087843743	0.284834273	0.757775703
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs2920503	-0.632290698	1.07902907	0.557888181
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs310752	-1.493961538	1.291876923	0.247506485
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs4135247	-1.076745308	0.453865952	0.017673608
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs4684833	1.667114035	0.874372807	0.056567241
PPARG	Prostate cancer	rs76763697	-0.356280804	1.375575893	0.795631512
PPARG	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.24220885	0.242243661	0.317380057
PPARG	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.24220885	0.170660507	0.15582798
PPARG	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	0.052477763	0.386644748	0.895390941
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs11150624	0.334030328	1.386418033	0.809609017
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs11865835	-1.996982609	1.605165217	0.213463549
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs12448775	-0.589935897	1.370342949	0.666830238

SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs142133957	0.096929853	1.050584013	0.92648922
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs34497199	0.490369767	1.296007752	0.705156144
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs4561482	1.75257265	1.445051282	0.22520247
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs8054784	0.442263964	1.535954955	0.773392122
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs8057029	0.86762931	1.512103448	0.566110153
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	rs8057326	0.835904762	1.583409524	0.597558718
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.257185957	0.318329005	0.419133767
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.257185957	0.462188011	0.57790114
SLC5A2	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.286572646	1.121342371	0.805635718
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs111917515	-0.072849815	1.149147601	0.949452244
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs112898001	0.523501992	1.243258964	0.673702241
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs112968754	0.424280488	1.262134146	0.736749335
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs113126535	0.442076	1.24254	0.722002243
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs1659215	0.36657027	1.672951351	0.826559752
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs34359922	1.155974576	1.237381356	0.350195353
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs4924660	1.795201149	1.424649425	0.207633187
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs73402785	0.424101266	1.284932489	0.741356715
GANC	Prostate cancer	rs8037100	0.602287179	1.588533333	0.704578925
GANC	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.598330807	0.17880222	0.000818896
GANC	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.598330807	0.439172734	0.173070338
GANC	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.681500655	2.999805347	0.592592905
KCNJ1	Prostate cancer	rs116842927	0.343015251	1.409010893	0.80766146
KCNJ1	Prostate cancer	rs4937311	0.266527778	1.483357143	0.857404766
KCNJ1	Prostate cancer	rs7110898	2.887689362	2.079370213	0.164914054
KCNJ1	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.808581297	0.722691194	0.263205168
KCNJ1	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.808581297	0.916909715	0.377855295
KCNJ1	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	1.059568188	2.124860421	0.705519116
RAMP3	Prostate cancer	rs11772021	0.392561077	0.473244306	0.406815651
RAMP3	Prostate cancer	rs4724382	-1.404990991	1.522063063	0.355963798
RAMP3	Prostate cancer	rs73111954	0.225001702	0.84092766	0.789035188
RAMP3	Prostate cancer	rs75390434	-0.452894872	1.78808547	0.800048141

RAMP3	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.199720909	0.266541287	0.453672966
RAMP3	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.199720909	0.388555114	0.607245549
RAMP3	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	0.848606136	0.710180295	0.354601125
ETFDH	Prostate cancer	Wald_ratio	-0.715094286	1.124358571	0.524775127
GANAB	Prostate cancer	Wald_ratio	1.373055866	1.119782123	0.220130468
PRKAB1	Prostate cancer	Wald_ratio	-0.970513011	1.274657993	0.446423614
DPP4	Prostate cancer	rs188581353	-0.973740926	1.263341677	0.44084559
DPP4	Prostate cancer	rs2080714	-0.519440909	1.133766234	0.646840935
DPP4	Prostate cancer	rs4233648	1.365056452	1.389120968	0.325766708
DPP4	Prostate cancer	rs75850673	-0.122203106	1.601043478	0.939158816
DPP4	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.153259411	0.498051057	0.758296715
DPP4	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.153259411	0.657546354	0.815701049
DPP4	Prostate cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.503055979	1.510177596	0.424469107
ABCC8	Prostate cancer	rs2074312	0.678913514	0.489605405	0.165547157
ABCC8	Prostate cancer	rs77023203	0.221727804	0.404114486	0.583228016
ABCC8	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.406984008	0.224447384	0.069789981
ABCC8	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.406984008	0.311663728	0.191605833
INSR	Prostate cancer	rs4031066	2.289219178	1.196780822	0.055771861
RAMP1	Prostate cancer	Wald_ratio	1.546186275	1.737862745	0.373623968
AMY2A	Prostate cancer	rs72681706	0.74552459	1.264037471	0.555327241
AMY2A	Prostate cancer	rs72692396	-0.276053892	1.121758483	0.805612324
AMY2A	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.17402854	0.507168939	0.731495231
AMY2A	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.17402854	0.839015745	0.835681963
AMY2A	Prostate cancer	rs72681706	0.74552459	1.264037471	0.555327241
AMY2A	Prostate cancer	rs72692396	-0.276053892	1.121758483	0.805612324
AMY2A	Prostate cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.17402854	0.507168939	0.731495231
AMY2A	Prostate cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.17402854	0.839015745	0.835681963
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	rs10305525	2.988607595	4.054379747	0.461042899
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	rs11963172	2.133816667	2.379722222	0.36989702
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	rs12215108	-3.792357513	2.825259067	0.179497336
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	rs142878626	5.03343318	3.118156682	0.106476774

GLP1R	Rectal cancer	rs228817	4.253705426	3.000596899	0.156301811
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	rs28360624	-1.97251497	3.002982036	0.511276039
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	rs880347	3.244564593	1.800239234	0.071498793
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	rs9462535	-0.127607742	2.475690323	0.958891797
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.58314777	1.025970356	0.122812919
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.58314777	0.928787979	0.088281956
GLP1R	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	4.307672239	4.584592371	0.383692656
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs10766392	-1.130104167	1.057640625	0.285288569
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs10766393	-1.065065617	1.066695538	0.31805054
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs10766395	-0.93241604	0.953819549	0.328291884
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs147673442	0.612463731	2.085215026	0.768973932
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs189603359	0.703782101	3.19266537	0.825530704
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs2285676	-0.7305	0.928885366	0.431617706
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs2355016	2.266263889	1.276625	0.075864975
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs35271178	0.355316279	0.58360155	0.542634687
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs4148631	5.068552448	2.980986014	0.08907565
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs5210	-0.712046798	0.937918719	0.447746378
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs5219	0.453394347	0.51961642	0.382905214
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs7110037	2.399363158	1.210334211	0.047434802
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs7112030	-0.849776675	0.946808933	0.369443353
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs739688	1.731592814	2.294502994	0.450446948
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs77902362	-1.205594156	2.558175325	0.637447135
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	rs79506407	1.322143552	3.56892944	0.711040203
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.079864731	0.275472111	0.771877841
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.079864731	0.25750349	0.756446823
KCNJ11	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.233440197	0.782688744	0.769889862
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	rs1078523	-1.35126875	2.32014375	0.560292339
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	rs11654396	-3.202602941	3.158448529	0.310592401
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	rs11869741	-3.390584958	2.53478273	0.181019198
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	rs12603201	0.382883806	1.516736842	0.800701619
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	rs12941945	-2.461537118	2.20779476	0.264880321

RAMP2	Rectal cancer	rs59795094	-1.593876923	2.870776923	0.578752729
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	rs9892728	-1.403197368	2.444828947	0.566005015
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	rs9905939	-0.613429221	2.424506494	0.800258945
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.279555721	0.495136493	0.009759146
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.279555721	0.805756104	0.112282122
RAMP2	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.928028712	2.879156451	0.758140525
KCNJ8	Rectal cancer	rs10841887	-0.827255882	1.28315	0.519117031
KCNJ8	Rectal cancer	rs117973841	-8.381125828	2.825211921	0.003011637
KCNJ8	Rectal cancer	rs12816749	0.58550355	2.56283432	0.819289128
KCNJ8	Rectal cancer	rs59406438	1.017917548	1.996581395	0.610170407
KCNJ8	Rectal cancer	rs74732083	1.161524664	2.250538117	0.605777759
KCNJ8	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.734064604	1.304593975	0.573655068
KCNJ8	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.734064604	0.866072915	0.396672867
KCNJ8	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.011893109	4.423434313	0.998023556
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs111327339	-1.660256798	2.10939577	0.431236819
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs1373641	2.646963964	1.772797297	0.135410965
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs1699348	-2.472552	3.01404	0.412019582
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs2120825	0.587030371	0.682482565	0.389712021
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs2881654	0.962859076	0.634815107	0.129328517
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs2920503	0.55254593	2.406122093	0.818370213
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs310752	2.756738462	2.880653846	0.338575537
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs4135247	1.459785523	1.009713137	0.148249348
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs4684833	0.161449123	1.952578947	0.934101958
PPARG	Rectal cancer	rs76763697	5.268973214	3.068276786	0.085934997
PPARG	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.911040648	0.331058469	0.005925015
PPARG	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.911040648	0.380033585	0.01651804
PPARG	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	0.692677635	0.60533774	0.285586658
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs11150624	-1.24157377	3.087893443	0.687626682
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs11865835	-6.368878261	3.572469565	0.074624358
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs12448775	-1.880259615	3.040801282	0.536348953
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs142133957	-0.738477977	2.351631321	0.753499806

SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs34497199	-4.841573643	2.890193798	0.093900359
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs4561482	2.221555556	3.221700855	0.490471024
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs8054784	0.803844144	3.423846847	0.814380992
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs8057029	2.126043103	3.370439655	0.528177169
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	rs8057326	-6.479742857	3.528314286	0.066284007
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.694901455	1.0445937	0.104686466
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.694901455	1.030365937	0.099979921
SLC5A2	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.817918534	2.689711054	0.769898618
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs111917515	0.918557196	2.560313653	0.719769066
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs112898001	0.412737052	2.768876494	0.881503917
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs112968754	1.830300813	2.811743902	0.515079655
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs113126535	0.702348	2.767248	0.799644362
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs1659215	0.501829189	3.727178378	0.892896113
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs34359922	1.919419492	2.758317797	0.48651277
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs4924660	-0.741862069	3.176643678	0.815344873
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs73402785	3.819708861	2.862603376	0.18208986
GANC	Rectal cancer	rs8037100	0.834841026	3.538984615	0.813511462
GANC	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.211028072	0.423743662	0.004264197
GANC	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.211028072	0.978486936	0.215844458
GANC	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	4.529621302	6.685115503	0.519804465
KCNJ1	Rectal cancer	rs116842927	1.815126362	3.150239651	0.564488957
KCNJ1	Rectal cancer	rs4937311	-0.254843651	3.30781746	0.938589465
KCNJ1	Rectal cancer	rs7110898	-9.681276596	4.635702128	0.036760285
KCNJ1	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.218700046	3.01685514	0.686239393
KCNJ1	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.218700046	2.046820639	0.551568604
KCNJ1	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.292346276	8.896386586	0.979087412
RAMP3	Rectal cancer	rs11772021	-0.123886957	1.055809524	0.906591929
RAMP3	Rectal cancer	rs4724382	-1.965171171	3.397243243	0.562953229
RAMP3	Rectal cancer	rs73111954	-1.818689362	1.873285106	0.331620184
RAMP3	Rectal cancer	rs75390434	3.568401709	3.98091453	0.370051248
RAMP3	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.431378578	0.679844298	0.525737897

RAMP3	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.431378578	0.866528019	0.61860799
RAMP3	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.350665402	1.584179128	0.845361411
ETFDH	Rectal cancer	Wald_ratio	-1.733714286	2.511714286	0.490036109
GANAB	Rectal cancer	Wald_ratio	1.065402235	2.497810056	0.669718394
PRKAB1	Rectal cancer	Wald_ratio	6.336654275	2.841211896	0.025729883
DPP4	Rectal cancer	rs188581353	-1.396157697	2.79942428	0.617969399
DPP4	Rectal cancer	rs2080714	-0.277548052	2.522922078	0.912401006
DPP4	Rectal cancer	rs4233648	-4.602830645	3.097395161	0.137270459
DPP4	Rectal cancer	rs75850673	-6.119086957	3.573720497	0.08685143
DPP4	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.526845631	1.313288468	0.05434708
DPP4	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.526845631	1.462948322	0.084126684
DPP4	Rectal cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.808501503	3.423687765	0.835297653
ABCC8	Rectal cancer	rs2074312	-1.376810811	1.088978378	0.20611728
ABCC8	Rectal cancer	rs77023203	-0.702324766	0.899640187	0.434994869
ABCC8	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.975926274	0.331183655	0.003210987
ABCC8	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.975926274	0.69357274	0.159397708
INSR	Rectal cancer	rs4031066	-0.029896644	2.666993151	0.991056006
RAMP1	Rectal cancer	Wald_ratio	4.422647059	3.869931373	0.253112036
AMY2A	Rectal cancer	rs72681706	-2.159316159	2.836978923	0.446578078
AMY2A	Rectal cancer	rs72692396	0.22742515	2.526127745	0.928264045
AMY2A	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.828070712	1.18537929	0.484820639
AMY2A	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.828070712	1.88660813	0.660719247
AMY2A	Rectal cancer	rs72681706	-2.159316159	2.836978923	0.446578078
AMY2A	Rectal cancer	rs72692396	0.22742515	2.526127745	0.928264045
AMY2A	Rectal cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.828070712	1.18537929	0.484820639
AMY2A	Rectal cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.828070712	1.88660813	0.660719247
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10305525	5.224778481	15.06234177	0.728683799
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11963172	7.357	8.900055556	0.40845018
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12215108	-6.957927461	10.56300518	0.510083815
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs142878626	-5.576221198	11.57195853	0.629895748
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs228817	19.72139535	11.23015504	0.07906951

GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs28360624	0.106887425	11.22886228	0.99240506
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs880347	3.898349282	6.710430622	0.561281724
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs9462535	10.57425806	9.237483871	0.252328505
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	4.560071769	2.769741003	0.099683648
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	4.560071769	3.465854294	0.188270174
GLP1R	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-18.47849928	14.73810997	0.256555993
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10766392	3.8509375	3.940078125	0.328383078
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10766393	3.863175853	3.973595801	0.330945301
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10766395	3.864987469	3.561679198	0.277851335
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs147673442	1.669862694	7.793290155	0.83033707
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs189603359	1.699892996	11.76984436	0.885162648
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2285676	4.343585366	3.467780488	0.210367745
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2355016	-6.830444444	4.769972222	0.152153168
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs35271178	0.565454264	2.177829457	0.795140549
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4148631	-16.72426573	11.13916084	0.133253766
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs5210	4.373891626	3.501527094	0.211614492
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs5219	0.502991925	1.938021534	0.795219493
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs7110037	-5.862710526	4.523868421	0.194992464
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs7112030	3.800099256	3.533473945	0.282170178
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs739688	-15.67047904	8.57	0.067470451
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs77902362	1.732185065	9.51711039	0.855576873
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs79506407	17.14218978	13.58985401	0.207166148
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.190773471	1.022371755	0.244133681
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.190773471	0.960871031	0.215247517
KCNJ11	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	4.771484743	2.738523072	0.103359695
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs1078523	-0.099945625	8.670375	0.990802785
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11654396	3.400397059	11.79639706	0.773149823
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11869741	4.282785515	9.469860724	0.651085773
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12603201	-4.438825911	5.665222672	0.433320711
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12941945	4.145183406	8.240960699	0.614965964
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs59795094	-3.105884615	10.72876923	0.772205489

RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs9892728	-0.356398684	9.135986842	0.968882081
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs9905939	-0.52020974	9.053896104	0.954181156
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.3986119	1.259476449	0.751630495
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.3986119	3.009790361	0.894637522
RAMP2	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.283102949	10.75500561	0.97985344
KCNJ8	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs10841887	1.92695	4.778735294	0.686775866
KCNJ8	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs117973841	-2.266960265	10.56966887	0.830174408
KCNJ8	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12816749	8.232485207	9.583905325	0.390345666
KCNJ8	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs59406438	1.401008457	7.43564482	0.850549082
KCNJ8	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs74732083	-6.606636771	8.481255605	0.435997867
KCNJ8	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.912090295	1.986449308	0.646122081
KCNJ8	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.912090295	3.233941677	0.777915356
KCNJ8	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-6.823577608	9.556274803	0.52674294
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs111327339	-3.346510574	7.842477341	0.669586194
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs1373641	3.246896396	6.612252252	0.62339644
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs1699348	2.616368	11.2656	0.816348505
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2120825	0.057437008	2.539898763	0.981958259
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.200054115	2.365862458	0.932612281
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2920503	8.987906977	8.980465116	0.316909645
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs310752	-2.364146154	10.75523077	0.826016316
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4135247	0.549672922	3.772788204	0.884162892
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4684833	-4.733377193	7.299210526	0.516675858
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs76763697	-10.38928571	11.41071429	0.362566719
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.050921449	0.790648809	0.948648038
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.050921449	1.416440791	0.971322001
PPARG	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.48717995	2.255833388	0.834420214
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11150624	-7.190188525	11.52942623	0.532865337
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11865835	7.839591304	13.32052174	0.556173347
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs12448775	-1.684903846	11.27794872	0.881239529
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs142133957	-11.76957586	8.688499184	0.175540086
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs34497199	-22.41883721	10.80209302	0.037947992

SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4561482	-19.95435897	12.02880342	0.097139681
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8054784	-8.628171171	12.78324324	0.499701511
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8057029	-8.949482759	12.57887931	0.476793651
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8057326	-12.85571429	13.17047619	0.329014442
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-10.19195758	2.879547597	0.000400992
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-10.19195758	3.836139721	0.007888003
SLC5A2	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-8.76359157	9.265072424	0.375710216
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs111917515	19.54232472	9.509815498	0.03988252
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs112898001	23.56035857	10.31071713	0.022310724
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs112968754	26.18995935	10.51849593	0.012778053
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs113126535	22.99732	10.29056	0.025430632
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs1659215	30.72021622	13.85978378	0.026657251
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs34359922	20.92855932	10.27491525	0.041664118
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4924660	27.26885057	11.87982759	0.021710721
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs73402785	24.36696203	10.68151899	0.022535059
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs8037100	29.04984615	13.15912821	0.02727347
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	24.24360719	1.166067522	5.23E-96
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	24.24360719	3.645447708	2.92E-11
GANC	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	6.661866153	24.91603357	0.796888619
KCNJ1	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs116842927	-16.04705882	11.77433551	0.172918929
KCNJ1	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4937311	-3.425714286	12.36238095	0.781697202
KCNJ1	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs7110898	18.30919149	17.1506383	0.285722822
KCNJ1	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-4.425247737	8.932790845	0.620322286
KCNJ1	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-4.425247737	7.634664146	0.562167042
KCNJ1	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-12.67683352	24.84459472	0.699636373
RAMP3	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs11772021	-4.321821946	3.943167702	0.273066551
RAMP3	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4724382	7.666882883	12.68531532	0.545584112
RAMP3	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs73111954	0.486723404	7.010893617	0.944652225
RAMP3	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs75390434	-16.8334188	14.85162393	0.257029689
RAMP3	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-3.11009872	2.598896506	0.231423616
RAMP3	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.11009872	3.237493139	0.336728034

RAMP3	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-4.758398795	5.915682187	0.505600426
ETFDH	Salivary gland carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-8.190771429	9.402742857	0.383697108
GANAB	Salivary gland carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-2.143620112	9.325530726	0.818196091
PRKAB1	Salivary gland carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-9.506542751	10.60739777	0.370136246
DPP4	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs188581353	-4.169274093	10.32335419	0.686309669
DPP4	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2080714	16.21279221	9.411818182	0.084960996
DPP4	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4233648	2.118314516	11.58887097	0.854963825
DPP4	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs75850673	5.034652174	13.33745342	0.705815239
DPP4	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	5.571430508	4.724238551	0.238267281
DPP4	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	5.571430508	5.444139071	0.306127564
DPP4	Salivary gland carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-4.563601033	12.35525521	0.747296329
ABCC8	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs2074312	1.892116216	4.057324324	0.64096799
ABCC8	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs77023203	4.614976636	3.356775701	0.169185938
ABCC8	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	3.508549255	1.337335326	0.008702189
ABCC8	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	3.508549255	2.586357127	0.174920981
INSR	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs4031066	5.423815068	9.956506849	0.585924921
RAMP1	Salivary gland carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-5.626421569	14.46911765	0.697381734
AMY2A	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs72681706	4.733512881	10.58309133	0.654679196
AMY2A	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs72692396	6.268862275	9.418283433	0.505663221
AMY2A	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	5.590298569	0.762485195	2.27E-13
AMY2A	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	5.590298569	7.035650325	0.426865173
AMY2A	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs72681706	4.733512881	10.58309133	0.654679196
AMY2A	Salivary gland carcinoma	rs72692396	6.268862275	9.418283433	0.505663221
AMY2A	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	5.590298569	0.762485195	2.27E-13
AMY2A	Salivary gland carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	5.590298569	7.035650325	0.426865173
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10305525	-3.283607595	3.415886076	0.336413663
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11963172	-1.2755	1.970111111	0.517356653
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12215108	4.225181347	2.281865285	0.064078271
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs142878626	0.715414747	2.779769585	0.7968972
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs228817	1.792170543	2.405271318	0.456210544
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs28360624	-3.037125749	2.363892216	0.198862622

GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs880347	-0.999090909	1.471435407	0.497143775
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs9462535	1.911870968	1.95683871	0.328559147
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.056397043	0.833204234	0.946034848
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.056397043	0.758177264	0.940704015
GLP1R	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.79324747	3.995076674	0.849166903
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10766392	-0.3621875	0.846041667	0.668580845
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10766393	-0.369790026	0.854908136	0.665342135
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10766395	-0.475488722	0.763007519	0.533168227
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs147673442	1.173626943	1.566450777	0.453720503
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs189603359	2.44155642	2.291089494	0.286570657
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2285676	-0.287804878	0.738756098	0.696846866
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs35271178	-0.289286822	0.463209302	0.532281394
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4148631	0.43986014	2.409020979	0.855120709
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs5210	-0.313743842	0.746133005	0.674125208
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs5219	-0.112220727	0.410417227	0.78452205
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs7112030	-0.51133995	0.753548387	0.49740647
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs739688	0.934191617	1.870658683	0.617503391
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs77902362	-0.425194805	2.461818182	0.862874853
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs79506407	1.864647202	2.698345499	0.489544473
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.199852556	0.113067751	0.077136678
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.199852556	0.214036736	0.350443103
KCNJ11	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.351596161	0.571849546	0.550141419
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs1078523	-0.7513125	1.857125	0.685803337
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11654396	2.543676471	2.482058824	0.305445666
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12603201	1.649716599	1.222307692	0.177120658
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs59795094	-1.57	2.295461538	0.49400149
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs9892728	-1.203092105	1.963618421	0.540080415
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs9905939	-0.712467532	1.964480519	0.716847844
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.275790253	0.650465109	0.671573609
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.275790253	0.739251215	0.709098559
RAMP2	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	4.129873885	3.189005634	0.264998924

KCNJ8	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs10841887	1.832647059	1.004176471	0.067997272
KCNJ8	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs117973841	0.39089404	2.490993377	0.875305569
KCNJ8	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12816749	-0.767633136	2.124319527	0.717834205
KCNJ8	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs59406438	1.727145877	1.781627907	0.332335635
KCNJ8	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs74732083	2.652107623	2.202488789	0.228534985
KCNJ8	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.47768977	0.478538183	0.002015597
KCNJ8	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.47768977	0.726310362	0.041899636
KCNJ8	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.936849217	2.195605416	0.170864085
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs111327339	-1.59918429	1.879486405	0.394845801
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs1699348	3.724	2.38368	0.11821963
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.248335208	0.524353206	0.635783095
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.440281849	0.498105975	0.376743719
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2920503	2.911395349	1.896627907	0.124774567
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs310752	1.799923077	2.304615385	0.434797783
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4135247	-0.787828418	0.814825737	0.33361034
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs76763697	3.614598214	2.666830357	0.175292974
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.195823832	0.364361572	0.590961162
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.195823832	0.31250495	0.5309042
PPARG	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.068128285	0.482082652	0.068607148
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11150624	1.674672131	2.45295082	0.494785452
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11865835	0.628956522	2.936782609	0.830418263
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs12448775	0.169262821	2.928814103	0.953914094
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs142133957	0.52004894	2.531060359	0.837207414
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs34497199	-0.065581395	2.332015504	0.977564692
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4561482	2.478119658	2.583504274	0.337453641
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8054784	0.405315315	2.73	0.88197411
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8057029	2.001034483	2.644396552	0.449225171
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8057326	1.061238095	2.822380952	0.706910875
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.995281188	0.300911153	0.000941131
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.995281188	0.880028463	0.25806992
SLC5A2	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.081462923	2.585333614	0.975742706

GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs111917515	0.610258303	2.020553506	0.762632767
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs112898001	0.282231076	2.188247012	0.897376737
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs112968754	0.548902439	2.22402439	0.80505841
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs113126535	0.80664	2.186	0.712125679
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs1659215	0.869675676	2.935837838	0.767056408
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs34359922	0.477033898	2.194152542	0.827887704
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4924660	0.226781609	2.50316092	0.927811946
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs73402785	0.209451477	2.266962025	0.926385782
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs8037100	0.442	2.771589744	0.873294447
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.491640907	0.076170674	1.09E-10
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.491640907	0.773057102	0.52479616
GANC	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.739491595	5.270428455	0.892367441
KCNJ1	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs116842927	-1.859956427	2.563965142	0.468193251
KCNJ1	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4937311	0.383412698	2.587619048	0.882207026
KCNJ1	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs7110898	0.393829787	4.021574468	0.92198847
KCNJ1	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.554140704	0.783666958	0.479496567
KCNJ1	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.554140704	1.659090201	0.738377477
KCNJ1	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-2.35153399	3.498845731	0.62328229
RAMP3	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs11772021	1.09863354	0.846086957	0.194119786
RAMP3	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4724382	-4.520990991	2.727567568	0.097414893
RAMP3	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs73111954	0.024851064	1.554553191	0.987245573
RAMP3	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs75390434	1.696666667	3.172136752	0.592742832
RAMP3	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.540914429	0.819740488	0.509343307
RAMP3	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.540914429	0.699367698	0.439265851
RAMP3	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	2.059880144	1.290220395	0.251444632
GANAB	Small cell lung carcinoma	Wald_ratio	0.639776536	2.133351955	0.764259053
PRKAB1	Small cell lung carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-3.648513011	2.356654275	0.121580191
ABCC8	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2074312	-0.839837838	0.871189189	0.335039331
ABCC8	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs77023203	-0.257663551	0.728060748	0.72341089
ABCC8	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.497061724	0.286461123	0.082708859
ABCC8	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.497061724	0.558658464	0.373604605

DPP4	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs2080714	0.02487013	2.077727273	0.990449652
DPP4	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4233648	0.491290323	2.612419355	0.850829995
DPP4	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs75850673	0.095279503	2.977391304	0.974471252
DPP4	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.180244668	0.144779659	0.213147003
DPP4	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.180244668	1.427151122	0.899496963
DPP4	Small cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.584058924	12.87663177	0.922075752
INSR	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs4031066	-0.564931507	2.298424658	0.805844222
RAMP1	Small cell lung carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-4.187745098	3.036666667	0.1678763
AMY2A	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs72681706	5.971194379	2.2735363	0.008629573
AMY2A	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs72692396	2.272215569	2.204650699	0.302706613
AMY2A	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	4.064818984	1.848614358	0.027888848
AMY2A	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	4.064818984	1.58271632	0.010221196
AMY2A	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs72681706	5.971194379	2.2735363	0.008629573
AMY2A	Small cell lung carcinoma	rs72692396	2.272215569	2.204650699	0.302706613
AMY2A	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	4.064818984	1.848614358	0.027888848
AMY2A	Small cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	4.064818984	1.58271632	0.010221196
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	rs10305525	-26.97468354	11.80664557	0.022330224
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	rs11963172	10.28738889	6.947722222	0.138690502
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	rs12215108	9.000259067	8.250466321	0.275326202
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	rs142878626	5.523110599	9.096728111	0.543749027
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	rs228817	-8.905581395	8.766899225	0.309715663
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	rs28360624	9.539221557	8.756946108	0.276007509
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	rs880347	3.646133971	5.256220096	0.487883005
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	rs9462535	-6.724516129	7.223612903	0.351901364
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.691711744	3.571155793	0.63570282
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.691711744	2.710868878	0.532596198
GLP1R	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	20.43173398	14.4415296	0.206870053
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs10766392	4.529791667	3.083229167	0.141786345
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs10766393	4.54648294	3.109370079	0.143689759
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs10766395	1.801869674	2.783082707	0.517349399
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs147673442	-8.034300518	6.069326425	0.185584463

KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs189603359	-2.088891051	9.291712062	0.822125306
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs2285676	2.477	2.71004878	0.360713857
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs2355016	-1.057944444	3.729111111	0.776641194
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs35271178	1.450215504	1.703472868	0.394586734
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs4148631	-10.36769231	8.707202797	0.233770208
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs5210	2.489458128	2.73637931	0.362947227
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs5219	0.147802153	1.516312248	0.922349387
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs7110037	0.845131579	3.535342105	0.811065047
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs7112030	3.0117866	2.761836228	0.275492285
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs739688	-11.21401198	6.700538922	0.094209531
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs77902362	-5.17762987	7.479902597	0.488808272
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	rs79506407	-2.639513382	10.53698297	0.802200767
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.159983002	0.689236311	0.092375572
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.159983002	0.751417188	0.122654483
KCNJ11	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	3.448340716	2.076972233	0.119082594
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	rs1078523	-3.5341625	6.7735625	0.601838622
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	rs11654396	-0.642233824	9.222132353	0.944479808
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	rs11869741	-0.803320334	7.387938719	0.913413452
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	rs12603201	0.792157895	4.426720648	0.85797763
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	rs12941945	5.093930131	6.443187773	0.42918235
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	rs59795094	-6.276484615	8.380076923	0.453871087
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	rs9892728	-2.376763158	7.138289474	0.739164658
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	rs9905939	-1.186168831	7.077272727	0.866895979
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.530202056	1.122562397	0.636702602
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.530202056	2.351648449	0.821621639
RAMP2	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	5.891529558	8.39970866	0.509331425
KCNJ8	Small intestine cancer	rs10841887	5.190088235	3.738823529	0.165088088
KCNJ8	Small intestine cancer	rs117973841	-1.974327815	8.231456954	0.810445332
KCNJ8	Small intestine cancer	rs12816749	8.139349112	7.479704142	0.276510656
KCNJ8	Small intestine cancer	rs59406438	10.27868922	5.84192389	0.078497729
KCNJ8	Small intestine cancer	rs74732083	-5.410403587	6.622264574	0.413927269

KCNJ8	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.258148519	2.560544014	0.096315264
KCNJ8	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.258148519	2.529627445	0.092314993
KCNJ8	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	1.33907891	8.548466549	0.885472385
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs111327339	-0.442438066	6.14847432	0.942634536
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs1373641	-2.279653153	5.172837838	0.659432504
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs1699348	-6.147424	8.79744	0.484693161
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs2120825	2.111507312	1.98984252	0.288624953
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs2881654	1.597857948	1.850834273	0.387962827
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs2920503	6.366453488	7.027267442	0.364954744
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs310752	4.549130769	8.408076923	0.588477977
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs4135247	2.658010724	2.949034853	0.367420613
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs4684833	-0.716447368	5.710307018	0.900154919
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	rs76763697	-1.767410714	8.937589286	0.843240455
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.570677737	0.587979077	0.007555455
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.570677737	1.108520258	0.156508109
PPARG	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	2.161055348	1.765401401	0.255732832
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs11150624	-1.849344262	9.008196721	0.837341085
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs11865835	-18.06504348	10.41469565	0.082816574
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs12448775	0.842727564	8.860833333	0.924229812
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs142133957	0.606730832	6.84040783	0.929321883
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs34497199	-2.561325581	8.435581395	0.761407083
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs4561482	0.144180342	9.406239316	0.987770377
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs8054784	-2.181738739	9.991711712	0.827152639
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs8057029	-2.983060345	9.838275862	0.761730083
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	rs8057326	-10.68380952	10.29447619	0.299354034
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.19063359	1.914619697	0.095622198
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.19063359	3.004340578	0.288232074
SLC5A2	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	3.040791565	7.288585209	0.689030273
GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs111917515	11.31535055	7.460738007	0.129354321
GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs112898001	12.87266932	8.067928287	0.110592446
GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs112968754	15.39260163	8.191788618	0.060240646

GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs113126535	10.32836	8.06312	0.200215305
GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs1659215	13.4472973	10.85832432	0.215555888
GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs34359922	16.04389831	8.04309322	0.046070993
GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs4924660	1.433867816	9.280747126	0.877216158
GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs73402785	15.13586498	8.346624473	0.069768374
GANC	Small intestine cancer	rs8037100	12.82810256	10.31087179	0.213450378
GANC	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	12.2511008	1.405002824	2.79E-18
GANC	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	12.2511008	2.852240028	1.74E-05
GANC	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	26.56677	19.49805834	0.21524208
KCNJ1	Small intestine cancer	rs116842927	-1.097867102	9.192244009	0.904931472
KCNJ1	Small intestine cancer	rs4937311	7.830055556	9.653174603	0.417286496
KCNJ1	Small intestine cancer	rs7110898	16.49897872	13.48829787	0.221251569
KCNJ1	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	5.76287754	4.69365217	0.219521143
KCNJ1	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	5.76287754	5.969466799	0.334348335
KCNJ1	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.592634739	12.53800448	0.969931228
RAMP3	Small intestine cancer	rs11772021	-3.50699793	3.077329193	0.254443019
RAMP3	Small intestine cancer	rs4724382	-1.658612613	9.917837838	0.867184908
RAMP3	Small intestine cancer	rs73111954	-0.870344681	5.476	0.873717694
RAMP3	Small intestine cancer	rs75390434	-5.004145299	11.62410256	0.666833897
RAMP3	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.895935227	0.691801817	2.84E-05
RAMP3	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.895935227	2.527699003	0.251927413
RAMP3	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.503585085	4.619683123	0.527396427
ETFDH	Small intestine cancer	Wald_ratio	15.88157143	7.2056	0.027520157
GANAB	Small intestine cancer	Wald_ratio	-9.038379888	7.302625698	0.21583138
PRKAB1	Small intestine cancer	Wald_ratio	-2.912423792	8.281152416	0.72506847
DPP4	Small intestine cancer	rs188581353	-7.187271589	8.163003755	0.378605302
DPP4	Small intestine cancer	rs2080714	-0.225212338	7.362987013	0.975598839
DPP4	Small intestine cancer	rs4233648	-12.23798387	9.047983871	0.176194726
DPP4	Small intestine cancer	rs75850673	1.932888199	10.44832298	0.853232906
DPP4	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	-4.446576525	3.075445324	0.148224396
DPP4	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-4.446576525	4.270693633	0.297790307

DPP4	Small intestine cancer	All - MR Egger	-5.159352802	9.762578362	0.649949636
ABCC8	Small intestine cancer	rs2074312	5.123621622	3.175027027	0.106587011
ABCC8	Small intestine cancer	rs77023203	3.361004673	2.624135514	0.20026233
ABCC8	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.076370802	0.865544779	2.48E-06
ABCC8	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.076370802	2.02270544	0.043872576
INSR	Small intestine cancer	rs4031066	-15.47883562	7.780479452	0.046652111
RAMP1	Small intestine cancer	Wald_ratio	0.274384314	11.30019608	0.980628168
AMY2A	Small intestine cancer	rs72681706	2.650187354	8.277962529	0.748854839
AMY2A	Small intestine cancer	rs72692396	6.77500998	7.374770459	0.358266106
AMY2A	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.949818848	2.048723264	0.015689885
AMY2A	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.949818848	5.506491742	0.368702695
AMY2A	Small intestine cancer	rs72681706	2.650187354	8.277962529	0.748854839
AMY2A	Small intestine cancer	rs72692396	6.77500998	7.374770459	0.358266106
AMY2A	Small intestine cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.949818848	2.048723264	0.015689885
AMY2A	Small intestine cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.949818848	5.506491742	0.368702695
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10305525	-1.86543038	6.579556962	0.776778906
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11963172	1.953472222	3.861044444	0.612895971
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12215108	4.300751295	4.581435233	0.347867078
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs142878626	7.997396313	5.052281106	0.113437917
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs228817	0.702066667	4.873651163	0.885458198
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs28360624	-0.474424551	4.865161677	0.922317699
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs880347	-0.839033493	2.921349282	0.773953426
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs9462535	-4.442845161	4.016954839	0.268716487
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.549423613	1.263983006	0.663797314
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.549423613	1.506708917	0.715371593
GLP1R	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	9.25648267	6.421997243	0.199562738
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10766392	1.106973958	1.714653646	0.518540869
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10766393	1.641380577	1.729228346	0.342519775
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10766395	0.040804511	1.54762406	0.978965487
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs147673442	1.816054404	3.35880829	0.588725305
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs189603359	2.523715953	5.193385214	0.627003926

KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2285676	-0.206252439	1.507092683	0.891145792
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2355016	-2.112258333	2.074566667	0.308597909
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs35271178	-1.02324186	0.946444961	0.279633736
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4148631	2.096034965	4.84293007	0.665157848
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs5210	-0.124518473	1.521738916	0.934784733
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs5219	-0.528332436	0.843244953	0.530956343
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs7110037	-2.18425	1.967131579	0.266838283
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs7112030	-0.100566998	1.535843672	0.947791854
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs739688	3.700874251	3.724431138	0.320381099
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs77902362	-4.370941558	4.14237013	0.291343512
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs79506407	-8.732214112	5.829002433	0.134116828
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.364124924	0.332121574	0.27292111
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.364124924	0.41776459	0.383424922
KCNJ11	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-1.563398718	1.154713801	0.197213066
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs1078523	1.5566125	3.76533125	0.679308796
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11654396	-1.692801471	5.124375	0.741140797
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11869741	-2.180749304	4.11729805	0.596350849
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12603201	-1.804125506	2.462080972	0.463702083
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12941945	-2.103021834	3.578855895	0.556784657
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs59795094	1.480338462	4.658676923	0.750667437
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs9892728	1.636302632	3.967848684	0.680053312
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs9905939	2.082636364	3.935201299	0.596644184
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.407820314	0.680672303	0.549077266
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.407820314	1.30764863	0.755137035
RAMP2	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-5.261726967	4.673675259	0.303247463
KCNJ8	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs10841887	4.594647059	2.080691176	0.027228164
KCNJ8	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs117973841	-1.251933775	4.583774834	0.784758761
KCNJ8	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12816749	-3.443964497	4.155177515	0.407196699
KCNJ8	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs59406438	2.661627907	3.233150106	0.410376905
KCNJ8	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs74732083	2.971188341	3.669215247	0.418077405
KCNJ8	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	2.522618973	1.360299511	0.063673594

KCNJ8	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.522618973	1.405193852	0.072620144
KCNJ8	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	8.142675102	4.146328444	0.144312356
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs111327339	6.164425982	3.418700906	0.07136487
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs1373641	-1.23745045	2.876247748	0.667027739
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs1699348	-6.150512	4.892488	0.208705192
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.333815523	1.107965129	0.76319563
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2881654	-0.492700113	1.030543405	0.632580889
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2920503	-7.133895349	3.912197674	0.068227585
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs310752	1.379753846	4.677807692	0.768026447
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4135247	-0.201875335	1.63986059	0.902023808
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4684833	6.334824561	3.176776316	0.046140614
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs76763697	7.12375	4.953392857	0.150389891
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.06662026	0.791070122	0.932885201
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.06662026	0.616958055	0.914010105
PPARG	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.159258284	1.332552467	0.907815153
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11150624	8.919590164	5.010122951	0.075024648
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11865835	12.65669565	5.786730435	0.028728446
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs12448775	11.42304487	4.938012821	0.02070682
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs142133957	3.865350734	3.812936378	0.310703751
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs34497199	11.85751938	4.692589147	0.011508712
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4561482	8.527538462	5.228282051	0.102881827
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8054784	13.85504505	5.557594595	0.01266713
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8057029	11.55612069	5.471155172	0.034670133
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8057326	12.33809524	5.723447619	0.03110629
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	9.864045721	1.165343422	2.57E-17
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	9.864045721	1.67177964	3.63E-09
SLC5A2	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	4.466201714	4.062105126	0.307928072
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs111917515	0.887387454	4.141808118	0.830351153
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs112898001	0.682326693	4.480159363	0.878950603
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs112968754	1.086865854	4.543536585	0.810941645
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs113126535	1.1999	4.47512	0.78860165

GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs1659215	0.215295135	6.027405405	0.971506124
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs34359922	2.256271186	4.462372881	0.613122461
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4924660	9.322011494	5.152362069	0.070409146
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs73402785	0.823658228	4.631898734	0.858861967
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs8037100	1.201328205	5.723487179	0.833750052
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.863818513	0.870327084	0.032232529
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.863818513	1.583040145	0.239049235
GANC	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-9.022774398	10.8236445	0.432018626
KCNJ1	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs116842927	-3.598605664	5.175555556	0.486862243
KCNJ1	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4937311	-4.682992063	5.364555556	0.382689997
KCNJ1	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs7110898	8.759659574	7.487702128	0.242052133
KCNJ1	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.56623602	3.64823964	0.667695594
KCNJ1	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.56623602	3.334874216	0.638602451
KCNJ1	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.357325189	10.66788444	0.978684127
RAMP3	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs11772021	1.423128364	1.714604555	0.406536613
RAMP3	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4724382	1.488153153	5.515144144	0.78729079
RAMP3	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs73111954	2.415570213	3.042825532	0.427278328
RAMP3	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs75390434	2.834316239	6.453632479	0.660530001
RAMP3	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.706687336	0.273969264	4.68E-10
RAMP3	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.706687336	1.40713482	0.225175253
RAMP3	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	1.295085894	2.57203123	0.664579346
ETFDH	Squamous cell carcinoma	Wald_ratio	0.798227143	4.100228571	0.845644493
GANAB	Squamous cell carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-6.24424581	4.05972067	0.124024802
PRKAB1	Squamous cell carcinoma	Wald_ratio	0.147380669	4.611784387	0.974506018
DPP4	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs188581353	-1.427008761	4.470175219	0.749553004
DPP4	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2080714	7.444025974	4.088480519	0.068647655
DPP4	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4233648	-1.205491935	5.027217742	0.810490686
DPP4	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs75850673	5.198981366	5.789807453	0.369210018
DPP4	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	2.684886611	2.357312913	0.254719574
DPP4	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	2.684886611	2.361834599	0.255630217
DPP4	Squamous cell carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.842601135	5.92045853	0.899870143

ABCC8	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs2074312	0.969437838	1.766278378	0.583102196
ABCC8	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs77023203	0.265978972	1.459373832	0.855382185
ABCC8	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.551378298	0.345418458	0.110430349
ABCC8	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.551378298	1.125035613	0.62406418
INSR	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs4031066	3.718582192	4.32680137	0.390103415
RAMP1	Squamous cell carcinoma	Wald_ratio	1.789519608	6.279735294	0.775669146
AMY2A	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs72681706	-3.10264637	4.608009368	0.500746285
AMY2A	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs72692396	1.491153693	4.107944112	0.716610343
AMY2A	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.543048417	2.281828117	0.811890161
AMY2A	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.543048417	3.066368599	0.859431241
AMY2A	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs72681706	-3.10264637	4.608009368	0.500746285
AMY2A	Squamous cell carcinoma	rs72692396	1.491153693	4.107944112	0.716610343
AMY2A	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-0.543048417	2.281828117	0.811890161
AMY2A	Squamous cell carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.543048417	3.066368599	0.859431241
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs10305525	0.885949367	2.130886076	0.677581451
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11963172	0.260166667	1.231333333	0.832662097
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12215108	1.054352332	1.417668394	0.457044183
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs142878626	3.371751152	1.774101382	0.057362253
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs228817	0.718527132	1.517984496	0.635968585
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs28360624	-0.084071856	1.485748503	0.954875367
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs880347	-0.581961722	0.923923445	0.528772516
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs9462535	0.019483871	1.237548387	0.987438683
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.355682374	0.379804705	0.349022224
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.355682374	0.476381696	0.455285023
GLP1R	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	2.135325887	2.142506589	0.357415933
RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs1078523	-0.0528125	1.1755625	0.964166849
RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11654396	-2.545294118	1.585661765	0.108451205
RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12603201	1.453643725	0.774534413	0.060545946
RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs59795094	-0.421692308	1.450923077	0.77132876
RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs9892728	-0.111513158	1.241447368	0.928426187
RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs9905939	-0.48974026	1.249350649	0.695061286

RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.172677787	0.522363538	0.740969205
RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.172677787	0.468662744	0.712539313
RAMP2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	4.502008794	2.021235499	0.089874568
KCNJ8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs10841887	-0.324323529	0.635176471	0.609628504
KCNJ8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs117973841	1.046258278	1.630860927	0.52117359
KCNJ8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12816749	1.093313609	1.329053254	0.410720774
KCNJ8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs59406438	1.229196617	1.095412262	0.261806527
KCNJ8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs74732083	-0.539080717	1.359192825	0.691648972
KCNJ8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.196237306	0.366805081	0.59265629
KCNJ8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.196237306	0.456653368	0.667392609
KCNJ8	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.444898088	1.36740855	0.766280665
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs111327339	0.765271903	1.111797583	0.491251635
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs1373641	0.639369369	0.889009009	0.472021795
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs1699348	1.94104	1.5144	0.199940138
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2120825	-0.003723285	0.332103487	0.99105493
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2881654	0.029537768	0.314791432	0.92524196
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2920503	-0.621627907	1.208837209	0.60708683
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs310752	0.117461538	1.458615385	0.935816151
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4135247	0.323646113	0.513646113	0.528632093
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4684833	-0.559473684	1.002982456	0.576974106
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.102840265	0.122788549	0.402289359
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.102840265	0.19032172	0.588955959
PPARG	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	-0.03197932	0.300504779	0.91823577
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11150624	1.476721311	1.545983607	0.339477295
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11865835	-1.06	1.853478261	0.567391266
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs12448775	2.246634615	1.835608974	0.220983214
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs34497199	2.699302326	1.472403101	0.066763449
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4561482	1.228717949	1.642051282	0.454289884
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8054784	1.926576577	1.723693694	0.263694118
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8057029	0.756465517	1.671896552	0.650937974
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8057326	1.68847619	1.782095238	0.343400932

SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.449488273	0.389690392	0.000199547
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.449488273	0.592597907	0.01444552
SLC5A2	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	3.086358285	2.833272425	0.317815985
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs111917515	-0.881254613	1.295756458	0.496435943
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs112898001	-0.967729084	1.394820717	0.487806532
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs112968754	-0.552560976	1.413130081	0.695783053
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs113126535	-0.95712	1.401	0.494499955
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs1659215	-1.447621622	1.877243243	0.440622606
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs34359922	-1.694364407	1.385169492	0.221247327
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4924660	-2.805229885	1.591551724	0.077972132
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs73402785	-0.56371308	1.444894515	0.696432036
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs8037100	-1.147846154	1.771692308	0.517061785
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.171596916	0.225960605	2.16E-07
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.171596916	0.492835012	0.017441793
GANC	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	2.031033989	3.362940323	0.564930665
KCNJ1	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs116842927	-2.358213508	1.574640523	0.134231947
KCNJ1	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs7110898	0.515489362	2.588425532	0.842144075
KCNJ1	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	-1.581986866	1.275976853	0.215040458
KCNJ1	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.581986866	1.345268634	0.239609446
RAMP3	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs11772021	0.156583851	0.531200828	0.768167021
RAMP3	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4724382	0.158018018	1.706846847	0.9262381
RAMP3	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs73111954	-0.211191489	0.983021277	0.829892701
RAMP3	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs75390434	0.882991453	2.011367521	0.660661136
RAMP3	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.117788131	0.13013497	0.365400324
RAMP3	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.117788131	0.439834238	0.788852357
RAMP3	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.039924707	0.797399202	0.964618281
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs147673442	-0.328549223	0.973523316	0.735751545
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2355016	1.059777778	0.656722222	0.106584211
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4148631	-1.104545455	1.515874126	0.466214262
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs5219	0.415235532	0.259690444	0.109828721
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs7110037	1.003473684	0.627710526	0.109903971

KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs739688	-0.272994012	1.178203593	0.816768236
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs77902362	0.163896104	1.540551948	0.915274584
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs79506407	0.618029197	1.738126521	0.722161084
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	0.459683334	0.154147461	0.002862773
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	0.459683334	0.210129301	0.028697199
KCNJ11	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	All - MR Egger	0.692739229	0.410870613	0.142766314
GANAB	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-0.941173184	1.338938547	0.482102581
PRKAB1	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-1.934609665	1.471449814	0.188589133
DPP4	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs2080714	-2.085584416	1.307077922	0.110576267
INSR	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs4031066	0.11630137	1.455205479	0.936300146
RAMP1	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	Wald_ratio	-0.603039216	1.924607843	0.754029234
AMY2A	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs72681706	1.796416862	1.442529274	0.213012541
AMY2A	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs72692396	1.34738523	1.408662675	0.338819906
AMY2A	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.566568178	0.224452472	2.96E-12
AMY2A	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.566568178	1.007835263	0.120091624
AMY2A	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs72681706	1.796416862	1.442529274	0.213012541
AMY2A	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	rs72692396	1.34738523	1.408662675	0.338819906
AMY2A	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(random effects)	1.566568178	0.224452472	2.96E-12
AMY2A	Squamous cell lung carcinoma	IVW(fixed effects)	1.566568178	1.007835263	0.120091624
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	rs10305525	5.970082278	5.503094937	0.277984093
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	rs11963172	-0.658711111	3.236722222	0.838735037
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	rs12215108	3.135968912	3.839243523	0.414031596
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	rs142878626	-7.008778802	4.199792627	0.095149241
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	rs228817	-0.796294574	4.086767442	0.845512689
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	rs28360624	-0.117975449	4.082808383	0.976947806
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	rs880347	-4.468708134	2.443832536	0.067464708
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	rs9462535	-5.348329032	3.358729032	0.111302283
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.110525834	1.329921234	0.112522721
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.110525834	1.260922648	0.094170925
GLP1R	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-8.331268126	5.513014783	0.181488254
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs10766392	0.705322917	1.437380208	0.623638426

KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs10766393	0.68491601	1.449629921	0.636586742
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs10766395	0.525278195	1.297383459	0.685569357
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs147673442	-3.429404145	2.820233161	0.223984838
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs189603359	5.097568093	4.320058366	0.238009493
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs2285676	0.821497561	1.263287805	0.515507914
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs2355016	-0.225280556	1.7361	0.896754388
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs35271178	0.334373643	0.792234109	0.672978169
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs4148631	4.657076923	4.057748252	0.251092507
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs5210	0.820179803	1.275578818	0.520232939
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs5219	-0.093262719	0.704997308	0.89475646
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs7110037	-0.125185526	1.645434211	0.939355021
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs7112030	0.718759305	1.287540943	0.576679211
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs739688	-0.669958084	3.119904192	0.829972569
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs77902362	4.086525974	3.494837662	0.242281366
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	rs79506407	-3.212992701	4.851094891	0.50776411
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.356089617	0.238937952	0.136144947
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.356089617	0.34981395	0.308706464
KCNJ11	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.352887853	0.966494351	0.720477651
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	rs1078523	-2.60418125	3.15175	0.408653687
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	rs11654396	-2.880220588	4.288080882	0.501787077
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	rs11869741	-1.778036212	3.446267409	0.605902598
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	rs12603201	-4.489433198	2.061923077	0.029457899
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	rs12941945	-4.48279476	2.994270742	0.134360981
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	rs59795094	-3.339292308	3.899569231	0.391818932
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	rs9892728	-2.786888158	3.321026316	0.401376875
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	rs9905939	-5.523	3.290642857	0.093269925
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.721697612	0.428725534	3.93E-18
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.721697612	1.094497281	0.000672943
RAMP2	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.894251372	3.912300343	0.35798132
KCNJ8	Testicular cancer	rs10841887	1.559297059	1.738076471	0.369644483
KCNJ8	Testicular cancer	rs117973841	-2.794847682	3.820629139	0.464464621

KCNJ8	Testicular cancer	rs12816749	0.525647337	3.480899408	0.879968571
KCNJ8	Testicular cancer	rs59406438	-4.092389006	2.70744186	0.130652586
KCNJ8	Testicular cancer	rs74732083	-1.493733184	3.092757848	0.629111544
KCNJ8	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.479048634	1.133345641	0.672524823
KCNJ8	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.479048634	1.176038763	0.683757661
KCNJ8	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.821580914	3.590615797	0.48932317
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs111327339	-5.660302115	2.858111782	0.047654768
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs1373641	0.459018018	2.407657658	0.848800437
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs1699348	3.322064	4.096032	0.417340148
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs2120825	-0.401611924	0.924285714	0.663917712
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs2881654	0.066719842	0.860621195	0.938205734
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs2920503	3.373697674	3.266255814	0.301653272
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs310752	-0.917953846	3.918830769	0.814797291
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs4135247	-0.445375335	1.371404826	0.745363877
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs4684833	1.926758772	2.649508772	0.467095126
PPARG	Testicular cancer	rs76763697	-1.092	4.149379464	0.792418103
PPARG	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.150028452	0.439638449	0.732912249
PPARG	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.150028452	0.515279827	0.77092958
PPARG	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.809948037	0.820793089	0.352647991
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs11150624	-2.142385246	4.195639344	0.609615853
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs11865835	-4.790582609	4.85593913	0.32386775
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs12448775	-3.552371795	4.144326923	0.391353728
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs142133957	0.910915171	3.190326264	0.775242611
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs34497199	-3.502341085	3.927085271	0.372477421
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs4561482	-3.544649573	4.374675214	0.417787445
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs8054784	-3.058171171	4.650018018	0.510751058
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs8057029	-4.273275862	4.576913793	0.350479921
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	rs8057326	-0.703405714	4.787209524	0.883183807
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.41110401	0.675072499	0.000354777
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.41110401	1.399727661	0.084969529
SLC5A2	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	0.225587212	3.401327221	0.948974948

GANC	Testicular cancer	rs111917515	3.267494465	3.478826568	0.347601428
GANC	Testicular cancer	rs112898001	1.987756972	3.760836653	0.597123786
GANC	Testicular cancer	rs112968754	3.476345528	3.818597561	0.362626189
GANC	Testicular cancer	rs113126535	4.23092	3.759336	0.260401176
GANC	Testicular cancer	rs1659215	5.619135135	5.062945946	0.267061577
GANC	Testicular cancer	rs34359922	3.092580508	3.748309322	0.409337464
GANC	Testicular cancer	rs4924660	2.692545977	4.316373563	0.532760134
GANC	Testicular cancer	rs73402785	2.365075949	3.89164557	0.543365508
GANC	Testicular cancer	rs8037100	5.043533333	4.807246154	0.294108031
GANC	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.369490719	0.365434904	2.96E-20
GANC	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.369490719	1.329403846	0.011257972
GANC	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	1.020700338	9.082506371	0.913676219
KCNJ1	Testicular cancer	rs116842927	-0.956124183	4.242091503	0.821676041
KCNJ1	Testicular cancer	rs4937311	-3.787777778	4.495174603	0.399434312
KCNJ1	Testicular cancer	rs7110898	2.399042553	6.287617021	0.702794909
KCNJ1	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.380106551	1.588834492	0.385050488
KCNJ1	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.380106551	2.769739501	0.618286511
KCNJ1	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	1.273161592	5.798003776	0.86239109
RAMP3	Testicular cancer	rs11772021	2.065064182	1.434784679	0.150069768
RAMP3	Testicular cancer	rs4724382	4.382783784	4.612459459	0.342007907
RAMP3	Testicular cancer	rs73111954	1.356191489	2.550859574	0.594961097
RAMP3	Testicular cancer	rs75390434	5.834888889	5.411606838	0.280936729
RAMP3	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.2437028	0.605280028	0.000209825
RAMP3	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.2437028	1.178021097	0.056827248
RAMP3	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	1.068019955	2.15255457	0.668942791
ETFDH	Testicular cancer	Wald_ratio	4.316457143	3.419542857	0.206844202
GANAB	Testicular cancer	Wald_ratio	-1.349284916	3.395541899	0.691094975
PRKAB1	Testicular cancer	Wald_ratio	-3.537197026	3.855390335	0.358897486
DPP4	Testicular cancer	rs188581353	-0.205604506	3.779011264	0.956610936
DPP4	Testicular cancer	rs2080714	-0.463874675	3.426584416	0.892315202
DPP4	Testicular cancer	rs4233648	6.686024194	4.205717742	0.111892004

DPP4	Testicular cancer	rs75850673	-0.337485714	4.846571429	0.944485047
DPP4	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.217950497	1.688946733	0.470829411
DPP4	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.217950497	1.983020431	0.539090054
DPP4	Testicular cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.948447402	4.520569024	0.708463665
ABCC8	Testicular cancer	rs2074312	0.514675676	1.479278378	0.727897654
ABCC8	Testicular cancer	rs77023203	0.689985981	1.223285047	0.572724527
ABCC8	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.618788976	0.086096197	6.61E-13
ABCC8	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.618788976	0.94270769	0.51156976
INSR	Testicular cancer	rs4031066	-0.575999315	3.622664384	0.873669814
RAMP1	Testicular cancer	Wald_ratio	-1.838078431	5.267656863	0.727136885
AMY2A	Testicular cancer	rs72681706	-7.54911007	3.855503513	0.050228972
AMY2A	Testicular cancer	rs72692396	-6.443173653	3.422355289	0.059744786
AMY2A	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-6.930553398	0.549064653	1.59E-36
AMY2A	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.930553398	2.55946834	0.006772883
AMY2A	Testicular cancer	rs72681706	-7.54911007	3.855503513	0.050228972
AMY2A	Testicular cancer	rs72692396	-6.443173653	3.422355289	0.059744786
AMY2A	Testicular cancer	IVW(random effects)	-6.930553398	0.549064653	1.59E-36
AMY2A	Testicular cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-6.930553398	2.55946834	0.006772883
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	rs10305525	2.888756828	5.756655281	0.6158
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	rs11963172	-5.627347305	3.401480807	0.09805
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	rs12215108	-3.068360604	3.800003263	0.4194
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	rs142878626	-1.179447852	4.296705264	0.7837
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	rs228817	1.98974781	4.153491183	0.6319
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	rs28360624	-4.452998919	4.225006225	0.2919
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	rs880347	0.172559598	2.538314784	0.9458
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	rs9462535	6.077470671	3.396368515	0.07355
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.42969333	1.398045448	0.758574771
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.42969333	1.295420774	0.740114484
GLP1R	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	-5.231469759	6.058921127	0.421068839
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs10766392	0.405677864	1.487039594	0.785
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs10766393	0.403703466	1.505631314	0.7886

KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs10766395	-0.133185334	1.34294406	0.921
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs147673442	-0.249906141	2.757946293	0.9278
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs189603359	-1.879029141	4.643047952	0.6857
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs2285676	0.075492803	1.317321393	0.9543
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs2355016	0.13854282	1.795635782	0.9385
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs35271178	0.175744336	0.818063028	0.8299
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs4148631	-0.132741069	4.252805414	0.9751
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs5210	0.0836018	1.322622884	0.9496
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs5219	0.091211094	0.725119497	0.8999
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs7110037	-0.259166738	1.684152837	0.8777
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs7112030	0.024801497	1.328025596	0.9851
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs739688	5.312690423	3.837213869	0.1662
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs77902362	-4.75439215	3.952314205	0.229
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	rs79506407	4.814276597	5.409685704	0.3735
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.114728588	0.198054736	0.562402164
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.114728588	0.36224209	0.751457594
KCNJ11	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.306521877	1.031924887	0.770798329
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	rs1078523	2.03524943	3.262990397	0.5328
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	rs11654396	-3.657506757	4.468818565	0.4131
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	rs11869741	-14.30350564	6.306240253	0.02332
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	rs12603201	1.556728193	2.107909515	0.4602
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	rs12941945	-5.356332434	3.184611003	0.09258
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	rs59795094	2.251345975	4.015219907	0.575
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	rs9892728	1.50887969	3.438580297	0.6608
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	rs9905939	3.611585959	3.408961475	0.2894
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.066974895	1.485351222	0.964035353
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.066974895	1.174071203	0.954509347
RAMP2	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	-5.881110837	5.794410605	0.349289931
KCNJ8	Thyroid cancer	rs10841887	-0.723532849	1.770564579	0.6828
KCNJ8	Thyroid cancer	rs117973841	-5.117574829	3.664886119	0.1626
KCNJ8	Thyroid cancer	rs12816749	-2.836251701	3.604801912	0.4314

KCNJ8	Thyroid cancer	rs59406438	-0.550899246	2.851401295	0.8468
KCNJ8	Thyroid cancer	rs74732083	0.76399059	3.135575195	0.8075
KCNJ8	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.179872191	0.818995025	0.149688071
KCNJ8	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.179872191	1.199432843	0.325267098
KCNJ8	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	1.410772537	3.596323364	0.721058723
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs111327339	-0.560469607	2.820729214	0.8425
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs1373641	-2.883204053	2.421066568	0.2337
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs1699348	-1.853302243	4.167059595	0.6565
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs2120825	0.5112628	0.962519417	0.5953
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs2881654	0.896846435	0.911776914	0.3253
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs2920503	-3.008034617	3.377934362	0.3732
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs310752	3.012055015	3.979376523	0.4491
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs4135247	-1.285000905	1.402936084	0.3597
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs4684833	2.769860307	2.777250632	0.3186
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	rs76763697	7.339422156	4.309186977	0.08853
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.284511387	0.527885436	0.589911511
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.284511387	0.536170705	0.595671162
PPARG	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	0.685117329	0.874573557	0.455971403
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs11150624	1.764763816	4.307080788	0.682
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs11865835	7.262052194	5.10289227	0.1547
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs12448775	-8.681617933	4.80405722	0.07074
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs142133957	5.577929646	3.163667195	0.07788
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs34497199	0.924695416	4.038676565	0.8189
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs4561482	0.689518896	4.451375261	0.8769
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs8054784	-0.969158257	4.764118551	0.8388
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs8057029	1.130486133	4.637291344	0.8074
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	rs8057326	2.926016442	4.903569555	0.5507
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.623017706	1.429448024	0.256201191
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.623017706	1.444163732	0.261078342
SLC5A2	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	2.058563777	3.690975682	0.594408124
GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs111917515	-1.539394589	3.635752053	0.672

GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs112898001	-2.234929855	3.95795788	0.5723
GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs112968754	-1.480827505	3.96221817	0.7086
GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs113126535	-1.699384464	3.928237003	0.6653
GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs1659215	-2.150317298	5.242829417	0.6817
GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs34359922	0.959944515	3.824202099	0.8018
GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs4924660	-2.011816621	4.45819083	0.6518
GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs73402785	0.582055317	3.928004841	0.8822
GANC	Thyroid cancer	rs8037100	-1.382573415	4.972997665	0.781
GANC	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.127312824	0.403370186	0.005194225
GANC	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.127312824	1.37580474	0.412567181
GANC	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	0.348720323	9.42309762	0.971512694
KCNJ1	Thyroid cancer	rs116842927	1.698889789	4.557152099	0.7093
KCNJ1	Thyroid cancer	rs4937311	-3.98739813	4.506888152	0.3763
KCNJ1	Thyroid cancer	rs7110898	-2.097671988	6.693926491	0.754
KCNJ1	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.3476632	1.830912353	0.461693568
KCNJ1	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.3476632	2.890356326	0.641028005
KCNJ1	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	3.365833293	6.168789405	0.682023366
RAMP3	Thyroid cancer	rs11772021	-0.359205763	1.480529927	0.8083
RAMP3	Thyroid cancer	rs4724382	-0.341693535	4.745585531	0.9426
RAMP3	Thyroid cancer	rs73111954	-5.523380321	2.814161651	0.04968
RAMP3	Thyroid cancer	rs75390434	-6.11995033	5.402518379	0.2573
RAMP3	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.642850497	1.312175074	0.210567836
RAMP3	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.642850497	1.229846917	0.181609074
RAMP3	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	0.069204253	2.498837427	0.980420729
INSR	Thyroid cancer	rs144057856	5.584774657	2.486818954	0.02472
INSR	Thyroid cancer	rs4031066	0.993471658	3.723237241	0.7896
INSR	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.168393915	2.120589244	0.049335911
INSR	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.168393915	2.067962881	0.043831298
ETFDH	Thyroid cancer	Wald_ratio	1.850562448	3.868624206	0.6324
GANAB	Thyroid cancer	Wald_ratio	3.774591406	3.579107196	0.2916
PRKAB1	Thyroid cancer	Wald_ratio	3.776574564	3.741538045	0.3128

DPP4	Thyroid cancer	rs188581353	3.583850153	3.601589547	0.3197
DPP4	Thyroid cancer	rs2080714	-0.475764635	3.523790469	0.8926
DPP4	Thyroid cancer	rs4233648	7.534834257	7.967440964	0.3443
DPP4	Thyroid cancer	rs75850673	0.21082193	5.12695642	0.9672
DPP4	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.724924541	1.418026373	0.223822579
DPP4	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.724924541	2.174822857	0.427700133
DPP4	Thyroid cancer	All - MR Egger	3.632645748	4.441869361	0.499392948
ABCC8	Thyroid cancer	rs2074312	-0.402989533	1.516188242	0.7904
ABCC8	Thyroid cancer	rs77023203	-0.114767392	1.277207368	0.9284
ABCC8	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.234399616	0.142016854	0.098839564
ABCC8	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.234399616	0.976817751	0.810359339
RAMP1	Thyroid cancer	Wald_ratio	9.424316382	9.371678719	0.3146
AMY2A	Thyroid cancer	rs72681706	1.302539198	3.743785579	0.7279
AMY2A	Thyroid cancer	rs72692396	3.220422164	3.210386022	0.3158
AMY2A	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.407725938	0.947724165	0.011068317
AMY2A	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.407725938	2.437047745	0.323168169
AMY2A	Thyroid cancer	rs72681706	1.302539198	3.743785579	0.7279
AMY2A	Thyroid cancer	rs72692396	3.220422164	3.210386022	0.3158
AMY2A	Thyroid cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.407725938	0.947724165	0.011068317
AMY2A	Thyroid cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.407725938	2.437047745	0.323168169
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	rs10305525	-0.968594937	8.639620253	0.910735536
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	rs11963172	10.64183333	5.080883333	0.036216808
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	rs12215108	-6.349689119	6.01388601	0.291042254
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	rs142878626	2.671958525	6.610115207	0.686048973
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	rs228817	-12.34666667	6.409829457	0.054078371
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	rs28360624	16.76568862	6.409580838	0.008903873
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	rs880347	-1.552038278	3.835837321	0.685760347
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	rs9462535	-4.183025806	5.28036129	0.428252505
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.536551964	3.080233336	0.861714583
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.536551964	1.979597985	0.786359597
GLP1R	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	8.707128857	13.72543276	0.549241053

KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs10766392	0.222758854	2.254130208	0.921279178
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs10766393	0.20032336	2.273419948	0.929784939
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs10766395	-1.939571429	2.035298246	0.340606949
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs147673442	4.578445596	4.452772021	0.303844626
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs189603359	-0.519677043	6.806673152	0.939142103
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs2285676	-2.073380488	1.98182439	0.295469679
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs2355016	-0.196566667	2.722897222	0.942450494
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs35271178	-1.572883721	1.245046512	0.206476636
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs4148631	-1.187258741	6.365041958	0.852030699
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs5210	-2.140236453	2.001091133	0.284828791
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs5219	-0.791822342	1.108238223	0.474925792
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs7110037	0.020634763	2.582021053	0.993623606
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs7112030	-2.620669975	2.019617866	0.194422467
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs739688	0.677922156	4.897892216	0.889915605
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs77902362	2.094574675	5.45474026	0.700984641
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	rs79506407	10.33381995	7.651727494	0.176848868
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.997974444	0.368385695	0.006747663
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.997974444	0.549280497	0.069236133
KCNJ11	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	-1.563182709	1.51808217	0.32060895
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	rs1078523	7.4065625	4.9502375	0.134600642
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	rs11654396	-5.259441176	6.741360294	0.43528784
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	rs11869741	4.610362117	5.419164345	0.394907416
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	rs12603201	-0.579724696	3.234979757	0.857776702
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	rs12941945	0.863366812	4.713231441	0.854657273
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	rs59795094	9.206923077	6.125276923	0.132812445
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	rs9892728	8.810723684	5.216026316	0.091188013
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	rs9905939	7.933506494	5.170922078	0.124967244
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.526814167	1.706621808	0.03877686
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.526814167	1.719434374	0.040252548
RAMP2	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.541824789	6.146965602	0.585435139
KCNJ8	Tongue cancer	rs10841887	1.810361765	2.734226471	0.507900006

KCNJ8	Tongue cancer	rs117973841	6.418708609	6.021887417	0.28647044
KCNJ8	Tongue cancer	rs12816749	8.349881657	5.460911243	0.126257709
KCNJ8	Tongue cancer	rs59406438	-4.627653277	4.274883721	0.279020894
KCNJ8	Tongue cancer	rs74732083	4.560627803	4.814529148	0.343504518
KCNJ8	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	2.195445609	1.975711204	0.266474578
KCNJ8	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	2.195445609	1.848266652	0.234896335
KCNJ8	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	-5.51121703	5.455966501	0.386836059
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs111327339	0.593	4.483232628	0.894770238
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs1373641	-1.530954955	3.781040541	0.685548755
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs1699348	-2.209408	6.434088	0.731304319
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs2120825	-4.973847019	1.470112486	0.000716176
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs2881654	-4.247790304	1.36167982	0.001811447
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs2920503	-4.143453488	5.133075581	0.419547352
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs310752	-3.883269231	6.146707692	0.527541038
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs4135247	-2.83152815	2.15422252	0.188708809
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs4684833	-1.553263158	4.171307018	0.709618536
PPARG	Tongue cancer	rs76763697	-3.275026786	6.544330357	0.616767219
PPARG	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-3.822637018	0.440379805	3.95E-18
PPARG	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-3.822637018	0.814703977	2.70E-06
PPARG	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.638719119	1.29853083	0.00726947
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs11150624	-4.287901639	6.58942623	0.515224291
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs11865835	-9.996695652	7.619008696	0.189495502
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs12448775	6.216442308	6.511089744	0.33970574
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs142133957	6.453752039	5.004991843	0.197237155
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs34497199	-6.431937984	6.16527907	0.296831726
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs4561482	-2.647957265	6.87217094	0.700003325
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs8054784	-8.700900901	7.304828829	0.23360792
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs8057029	-7.938198276	7.190508621	0.269600573
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	rs8057326	-4.4682	7.523504762	0.552579842
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.355147546	2.170049216	0.277790207
SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.355147546	2.197951384	0.283935953

SLC5A2	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	10.28513468	5.338185752	0.09538317
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs111917515	3.72501845	5.464575646	0.495449821
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs112898001	4.388286853	5.906294821	0.457490926
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs112968754	3.804686992	6.001707317	0.526123823
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs113126535	3.755792	5.90424	0.524699662
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs1659215	5.513621622	7.953891892	0.488185329
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs34359922	5.213644068	5.894194915	0.37640543
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs4924660	2.862206897	6.781551724	0.672982819
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs73402785	2.687822785	6.109873418	0.65999893
GANC	Tongue cancer	rs8037100	4.468774359	7.55174359	0.554015341
GANC	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.985530712	0.301129877	5.49E-40
GANC	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.985530712	2.088508386	0.056350588
GANC	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	3.812730785	14.26837906	0.797004877
KCNJ1	Tongue cancer	rs116842927	-2.341263617	6.668823529	0.725531363
KCNJ1	Tongue cancer	rs4937311	3.258015873	7.057214286	0.644326956
KCNJ1	Tongue cancer	rs7110898	16.43255319	9.922297872	0.09769676
KCNJ1	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	3.408136575	4.836759987	0.481039187
KCNJ1	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	3.408136575	4.355189164	0.433893666
KCNJ1	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	-0.051157798	13.76537935	0.997634071
RAMP3	Tongue cancer	rs11772021	0.577238095	2.25436853	0.79790982
RAMP3	Tongue cancer	rs4724382	-0.040387117	7.244738739	0.99555207
RAMP3	Tongue cancer	rs73111954	4.555404255	3.99853617	0.254591396
RAMP3	Tongue cancer	rs75390434	-4.919179487	8.480059829	0.561855392
RAMP3	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.126787073	1.231120977	0.360058867
RAMP3	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.126787073	1.849726669	0.542415676
RAMP3	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	1.685932397	3.380925519	0.667461082
ETFDH	Tongue cancer	Wald_ratio	3.854642857	5.388157143	0.474367044
GANAB	Tongue cancer	Wald_ratio	5.680782123	5.326368715	0.286179875
PRKAB1	Tongue cancer	Wald_ratio	0.619416357	6.056877323	0.918545052
DPP4	Tongue cancer	rs188581353	1.440525657	5.926245307	0.80794683
DPP4	Tongue cancer	rs2080714	-7.148571429	5.376038961	0.183613921

DPP4	Tongue cancer	rs4233648	-0.080621129	6.609435484	0.990267738
DPP4	Tongue cancer	rs75850673	8.227391304	7.625217391	0.280600488
DPP4	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.64624016	3.086554125	0.834157305
DPP4	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.64624016	3.113415267	0.835567602
DPP4	Tongue cancer	All - MR Egger	1.889306885	8.374091544	0.84245943
ABCC8	Tongue cancer	rs2074312	-2.177116216	2.320381081	0.348111815
ABCC8	Tongue cancer	rs77023203	-2.0685	1.918689252	0.280998175
ABCC8	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	-2.112607296	0.053341485	0
ABCC8	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-2.112607296	1.478656157	0.153080513
INSR	Tongue cancer	rs4031066	-7.958835616	5.69440411	0.162215467
RAMP1	Tongue cancer	Wald_ratio	3.457186275	8.263186275	0.675666264
AMY2A	Tongue cancer	rs72681706	2.541850117	6.047587822	0.674260397
AMY2A	Tongue cancer	rs72692396	-0.119599401	5.381936128	0.98227057
AMY2A	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.056647386	1.321728013	0.424033069
AMY2A	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.056647386	4.020428032	0.792689609
AMY2A	Tongue cancer	rs72681706	2.541850117	6.047587822	0.674260397
AMY2A	Tongue cancer	rs72692396	-0.119599401	5.381936128	0.98227057
AMY2A	Tongue cancer	IVW(random effects)	1.056647386	1.321728013	0.424033069
AMY2A	Tongue cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	1.056647386	4.020428032	0.792689609
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	rs10305525	-14.22265823	14.55196203	0.328385768
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	rs11963172	10.87316667	8.572388889	0.204657282
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	rs12215108	-0.075948705	10.16932642	0.994041126
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	rs142878626	1.851981567	11.16861751	0.868298507
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	rs228817	15.2644186	10.81317829	0.158053166
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	rs28360624	6.087664671	10.78670659	0.572504176
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	rs880347	7.755023923	6.47138756	0.230778586
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	rs9462535	17.6543871	8.903548387	0.047384361
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	7.647606516	2.830166394	0.006888737
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	7.647606516	3.339703393	0.022026772
GLP1R	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.554586255	14.2143331	0.759513832
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs10766392	-0.650195313	3.803020833	0.864248835

KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs10766393	-0.673716535	3.834698163	0.860537817
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs10766395	0.333446115	3.434185464	0.922650055
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs147673442	-7.300647668	7.491787565	0.329814918
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs189603359	0.80305642	11.33649805	0.943526578
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs2285676	0.327912195	3.344487805	0.921896112
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs2355016	-1.510066667	4.592805556	0.74231473
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs35271178	0.048046667	2.099906977	0.981745692
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs4148631	9.914125874	10.7465035	0.356244718
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs5210	0.320665025	3.377044335	0.924351092
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs5219	-1.050160162	1.868438762	0.574080438
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs7110037	-0.876726316	4.356552632	0.840508463
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs7112030	0.247767742	3.405980149	0.942009105
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs739688	7.822095808	8.282994012	0.344987714
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs77902362	6.445909091	9.122045455	0.479796569
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	rs79506407	11.37547445	12.75819951	0.372596285
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.144160044	0.508807374	0.776924409
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.144160044	0.926268324	0.876320503
KCNJ11	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-2.968356978	2.561657931	0.265936594
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	rs1078523	2.78044375	8.356375	0.739335654
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	rs11654396	0.600738235	11.36904412	0.957859535
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	rs11869741	-3.671281337	9.174568245	0.689039789
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	rs12603201	0.310540486	5.455708502	0.954608695
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	rs12941945	-15.46122271	7.931048035	0.05124109
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	rs59795094	4.770946154	10.34561538	0.644686441
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	rs9892728	2.698671053	8.807368421	0.759292038
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	rs9905939	9.933441558	8.733311688	0.255362838
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.209745841	2.611933804	0.935996357
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.209745841	2.901561083	0.94237332
RAMP2	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-12.99967047	10.38074918	0.257066301
KCNJ8	Vulvar cancer	rs10841887	-9.251529412	4.600411765	0.04432313
KCNJ8	Vulvar cancer	rs117973841	-9.940927152	10.26764901	0.332954737

KCNJ8	Vulvar cancer	rs12816749	5.541331361	9.204911243	0.54717596
KCNJ8	Vulvar cancer	rs59406438	-2.174291755	7.273276956	0.764983902
KCNJ8	Vulvar cancer	rs74732083	-5.741300448	8.118901345	0.479471785
KCNJ8	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	-5.791077387	2.464096366	0.018764183
KCNJ8	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-5.791077387	3.121767134	0.063587108
KCNJ8	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-13.80748614	9.216835316	0.231047077
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs111327339	-7.795453172	7.66429003	0.309099419
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs1373641	6.26454955	6.381351351	0.326249447
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs1699348	3.90056	10.87048	0.719728761
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs2120825	-1.186434196	2.439178853	0.626678475
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs2881654	-0.516257046	2.27848929	0.820751389
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs2920503	23.08534884	8.686627907	0.007870551
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs310752	14.62776923	10.34846154	0.157502548
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs4135247	1.531549598	3.63538874	0.673543999
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs4684833	1.862631579	7.072587719	0.792273676
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	rs76763697	-12.87892857	11.0490625	0.243771034
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	0.456903945	1.637839463	0.780269783
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	0.456903945	1.364391494	0.737717533
PPARG	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-3.435577987	2.171914865	0.15234744
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs11150624	-3.615057377	11.10270492	0.744725877
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs11865835	-5.58913913	12.86078261	0.663861657
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs12448775	-4.365576923	10.78403846	0.685611021
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs142133957	1.390331158	8.539477977	0.870666306
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs34497199	1.679550388	10.4151938	0.871888911
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs4561482	4.014205128	11.60393162	0.729391627
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs8054784	-3.187306306	12.31972973	0.79585468
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs8057029	-8.113439655	12.12784483	0.503500135
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	rs8057326	-3.159809524	12.6987619	0.80349371
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	-1.816299698	1.289735619	0.159050282
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-1.816299698	3.708690971	0.624316866
SLC5A2	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	0.508128627	9.037777663	0.956735499

GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs111917515	4.191439114	9.260110701	0.650812454
GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs112898001	2.117163347	10.01067729	0.832504529
GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs112968754	1.666215447	10.16235772	0.869762999
GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs113126535	4.22936	10.00044	0.672355533
GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs1659215	8.878702703	13.47178378	0.50985777
GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs34359922	2.707525424	9.97779661	0.786117976
GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs4924660	16.90758621	11.49781609	0.141425264
GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs73402785	-0.226723629	10.35670886	0.982534525
GANC	Vulvar cancer	rs8037100	8.23225641	12.78851282	0.519755247
GANC	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.765508292	1.643708315	0.00374066
GANC	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.765508292	3.538210174	0.178022182
GANC	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-21.66636936	24.1789451	0.39997282
KCNJ1	Vulvar cancer	rs116842927	10.39921569	11.34989107	0.359541423
KCNJ1	Vulvar cancer	rs4937311	34.27134921	11.95920635	0.004161047
KCNJ1	Vulvar cancer	rs7110898	-3.869251064	16.85893617	0.818474549
KCNJ1	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	16.78622987	10.40340056	0.106628765
KCNJ1	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	16.78622987	7.397667091	0.023260738
KCNJ1	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	-4.683417175	18.81277558	0.844671767
RAMP3	Vulvar cancer	rs11772021	4.333457557	3.762277433	0.249396013
RAMP3	Vulvar cancer	rs4724382	0.79038018	12.22801802	0.948463169
RAMP3	Vulvar cancer	rs73111954	3.392404255	6.727319149	0.614069669
RAMP3	Vulvar cancer	rs75390434	11.5508547	14.27384615	0.418381646
RAMP3	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.246576256	1.070043638	7.23E-05
RAMP3	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.246576256	3.09581362	0.170151948
RAMP3	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	4.037553779	5.659432518	0.549600569
ETFDH	Vulvar cancer	Wald_ratio	21.601	9.372342857	0.021180024
GANAB	Vulvar cancer	Wald_ratio	-14.15877095	9.032011173	0.116969594
PRKAB1	Vulvar cancer	Wald_ratio	7.121375465	10.1360223	0.482316982
DPP4	Vulvar cancer	rs188581353	11.35249061	10.01072591	0.256780828
DPP4	Vulvar cancer	rs2080714	-0.338827273	9.073701299	0.970212571
DPP4	Vulvar cancer	rs4233648	11.10096774	11.19790323	0.321517915

DPP4	Vulvar cancer	rs75850673	-6.642670807	12.88447205	0.606164335
DPP4	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	4.365118131	4.129145399	0.290444011
DPP4	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	4.365118131	5.261468085	0.406743026
DPP4	Vulvar cancer	All - MR Egger	10.04947477	11.97858426	0.489792142
ABCC8	Vulvar cancer	rs2074312	-2.344097297	3.91472973	0.549313565
ABCC8	Vulvar cancer	rs77023203	1.195114486	3.235864486	0.711878852
ABCC8	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	-0.241486133	1.737990938	0.889493164
ABCC8	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	-0.241486133	2.494115337	0.922867467
INSR	Vulvar cancer	rs4031066	-2.787671233	9.61239726	0.771810187
RAMP1	Vulvar cancer	Wald_ratio	20.98666667	13.91411765	0.131477708
AMY2A	Vulvar cancer	rs72681706	19.28002342	10.06737705	0.055479883
AMY2A	Vulvar cancer	rs72692396	4.459161677	9.096127745	0.623973723
AMY2A	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	11.12036265	7.372458223	0.131460973
AMY2A	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	11.12036265	6.749255588	0.099425984
AMY2A	Vulvar cancer	rs72681706	19.28002342	10.06737705	0.055479883
AMY2A	Vulvar cancer	rs72692396	4.459161677	9.096127745	0.623973723
AMY2A	Vulvar cancer	IVW(random effects)	11.12036265	7.372458223	0.131460973
AMY2A	Vulvar cancer	IVW(fixed effects)	11.12036265	6.749255588	0.099425984